

Development and demonstration of an automated, modular and environmentally friendly multi-functional platform for open sea farm installations of the Blue Growth Industry

D4.1 – Environmental impact assessment for the representative sites report

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

The aim of the **Blue Growth Farm project** is to develop and demonstrate an automated, modular and environmentally friendly multi-functional platform for open sea farm installations of the Blue Growth Industry. Therefore, this project can be a driver on designs a system to produce food and energy at the least environmental load.

The BGF platform design is based on the following aims:

- Ensuring a nominal 2.000t/y fish production, operating with advanced automation and remote control capabilities;
- Avoid or minimize the pollution to the surrounding marine ecosystem, at the same time exploiting the marine natural resources in a sustainable way;
- Maximize the electricity production in the BGF potential installation area, dispatching produced electric energy to the grid and providing a maritime electric station service to shipping.

In particular, WP4 aims to carry out the Environmental Impact Assessment studies for the Blue Growth Farm concept and potential exploitation. In this respect, the present report of the Task 4.1 performs an assessment of all the main environmental components possibly impacted by the BGF installation, as a farm located in open sea. The outcome of this study has to be intended as a decision-making support tool for the development, designing and exploitable phases of the project, aiming at avoiding/reducing/compensating any likely environmental negative effect.

IDENTIFICATION OF THE DOCUMENT AND ITS STRUCTURE

The present document is a WP4 deliverable of the European Commission funded project The Blue Growth Farm (under Grant Agreement no.774426, in the framework of H2020 programme). The deliverable D4.1 “Environmental Impact Assessment” is the first step to the assessment of the overall environmental sustainability of the BGF system.

The document is organised in the following chapters:

- Chapter 1 introduce and specifies the structure of the document;
- Chapter 2 describes programmatic framework, starting form the international legal context to the local;
- Chapter 3 describes the environmental characteristic of the selected site;
- Chapter 4 outline the Project and the features of its main operational life;
- Chapter 5 provides the assessment of the impacts on the main components, taking into account the sensitive receptors, and including mitigation measures;
- Chapter 6 reports the final reccomendations
- Chapter 7 is the conclusions of the document;
- Chapter 8 lists the quoted references.

Within this document, the international legal framework and all the methods used to assess the environmental impacts are not described, as well detailed informations on generic impact on main group of receptors as mammals, birds, fish etc. The reader is thus diverted to the D 4.1 – France document for all informations.

CHAPTER 2: PROGRAMMATIC FRAMEWORK

2.1 INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

The Canary Islands, an archipelago of volcanic origin located in the Atlantic Ocean, is located just 95 kilometers northwest of the coast of the African continent and about 940 kilometers from the European continent. Politically, the Canary Islands are part of the Spanish State since its conquest by the Crown of Castile in the fifteenth century and are one of its 17 Autonomous Communities since the publication of its Statute of autonomy, approved by Organic Law 10/1982. This Statute has undergone a major reform through Organic Law 4/1996.

As part of the Spanish territory, in the international field the Canary Islands belong to the European Union, although with a special status. From the accession of Spain to Europe, an exception was made with respect to the application of the Community tax, customs, commerce, fisheries and agriculture rules in Article 25 of the Act of Accession of the Kingdom of Spain to the European Community and its Protocol number 2. Following this, Regulation 1911/1991 and Decision 91/314 / EC were approved, stating the Program of Specific Options for the Distance and Insularity of the Canary Islands. Finally, and due to the importance of the status of the Outermost Regions, the outermost statute was established in the European Union by virtue of Article 299.2 of the Amsterdam Treaty. Likewise, in the Treaty of Lisbon, which modifies the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community, numerous references are established to the Outermost Regions. As for its territorial delimitation, since they are islands that have their 1,583 kilometers of coastline as a natural border, there is no complication to establish the land space that comprises this Community. Thus, the surface of the archipelago is 7,446.95 square kilometers, distributed between the islands of El Hierro, La Palma, La Gomera, Tenerife, Gran Canaria, Lanzarote and Fuerteventura, in addition to the Chinijo Archipelago and Isla de Lobos.

Nine regions of the European Union far from the European continent receive the denomination of Outermost Regions: Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Reunion, Martinique, Mayotte and San Martin (France), the Azores and Madeira (Portugal) and the Canary Islands (Spain).

2.1.1 The International Law of the Sea

At the international level, the III UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) is the most important legal text that regulates the seas and oceans. It was approved on April 30, 1982 in New York and opened for signature on December 10, 1982 in Montego Bay. Despite being signed that same year by Spain, the Convention was not ratified by the General Courts and sanctioned by the King until 1997.

The 12-mile maritime space is commonly accepted to delimit continental states and archipelagic states, but it creates difficult to understand situations in mixed states, as is the case in Spain. One of these situations may be the space of high seas between the islands of Tenerife and Gran Canaria or between El Hierro, La Gomera and La Palma.

The Part IV of the UNCLOS regulates the ownership of the waters of the archipelagic States. First, it indicates a definition of "Archipelago State" and the term "archipelago" only for the purposes of the application of the Convention, stating that the sea that connects the islands is included in the archipelago concept.

Article 47 introduces the concept of "archipelagic baselines": these lines may not exceed 100 nautical miles and from them the width of the territorial Sea, the contiguous Zone, the exclusive economic Zone and the Continental Shelf will be measured.

Article 49 states that the Archipelagic State will extend its sovereignty over the waters that are enclosed by these archipelagic baselines. This establishment of sovereignty will not affect existing agreements with other States or traditional fishing rights or respect for existing submarine cables.

Part V of UNCLOS deals with the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). This zone is the result of negotiations in the elaboration of the Convention by the States that intended to include it in the High Seas regime by its geostrategic interests, on the one hand, and of the states that claimed their inclusion as territorial sea, on the other.

Article 56 of this text states that in this area the coastal State has "sovereign rights for the purposes of exploration and exploitation, conservation and administration of natural resources, both living and non-living, of the overlying waters to the bed and of the seabed and the subsoil of the sea, and with respect to other activities with a view to economic exploration and exploitation of the area "in addition to jurisdiction over the establishment and use of artificial islands, facilities and structures; marine scientific research; the protection and preservation of the marine environment as well as other rights and duties provided for in the Convention.

In this exclusive economic Zone, under Article 58 CDM, all States enjoy freedom of navigation and overflight, laying of cables and pipes and other uses of the sea related to such freedoms taking into account the rights and duties of the coastal State.

If there are two States with adjacent or opposite coasts, the delimitation of the exclusive Economic Zone shall be carried out by agreement between them as indicated in Article 74.

At the moment, after the accession of Spain to the European Community, the Spanish exclusive economic zone is subject to the common fisheries policy, which is why the principle of free access for fisheries from any other Member State without discrimination is governed.

Part VI of the UNCLOS refers to the continental shelf. In spite of the definition established in article 76 that establishes the 200-mile general limit, it allows countries with a wide geological platform and acquired rights with respect to the previous regulations to extend it to this real limit of the same. In this zone, the coastal State exercises sovereignty rights for the purpose of its exploration and exploitation of its natural resources, as indicated in article 77. If this State does not perform such actions, no one can undertake these activities without the express consent of the same state.

If there are two States with adjacent or opposite coasts, the delimitation of the continental shelf will be made by agreement between them under Article 83. With respect to the Continental Platform, it is worth noting that Spain has presented to the UN a demand for the expansion of the Canary Continental Platform beyond the 200 miles of exclusive economic zone, extending it up to about 350 miles west of El Hierro. To support this demand, Spain has developed oceanographic studies, concluding that the sea floor of that area has the same volcanic origin of the archipelago and is part of the same geological complex. However, this demand coincides in part with that raised by Portugal, in the northern zone, with respect to the Madeira and Azores continental shelf and, in turn, Morocco has submitted a letter rejecting this proposal of delimitation in its southern zone.

The high seas area is regulated in the UNCLOS in its part VII establishing a principle of restricted freedom. It recognizes the freedom of navigation and overflight, of fishing, of placement of cables and submarine pipes and, as article 87 of the Convention adds, there will also be freedom of scientific research and freedom to build artificial islands and other facilities permitted by International Law. Furthermore, in this area, all States have the right to fishing, adopting in any case measures for the conservation of living resources.

Part VIII of the UNCLOS establishes the regime of the islands, the definition of which is established in article 121. The Convention states with respect to the islands that "the territorial sea, the contiguous zone, the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf of an island shall be determined in accordance with the provisions of this Convention applicable to other land extensions." However, "rocks that are not suitable for maintaining human habitation or their own economic life will not have an exclusive economic zone or continental shelf."

Finally, the final provision established in article 305 e) that the opening of the Convention to the signature of "All territories that enjoy full internal autonomy recognized as such by the United Nations, but have not reached the full independence in accordance with General Assembly resolution 1514 (XV), and that they have jurisdiction over the matters governed by this Convention, including the conclusion of treaties in relation to them."

Since the adoption of the Convention, several interpretations of the different principles established by it have been raised. One of the discrepancies raised has been the archipelagic principle and its possible application not only to the archipelagic States but also to the mixed States.

This principle obtained the support of all the mixed States, including Spain, Canada, India, Greece or Portugal among others, however the III UNCLOS is silent in relation to the extension of this principle to those States. For some jurists this silence is clearly a refusal to its application, establishing a literal interpretation and reducing its application exclusively to the Archipelagic States.

In this regard, it is pointed out that there are several mixed States that have established this principle in their archipelagos. Thus we find the precedents of the islands Houtman (Australia), Madeira and Azores (Portugal), Faroe (Denmark), Spitzberg (Norway) and Galapagos (Ecuador).

Actually, these States establish very large baselines, being in some cases over 100 nautical miles that in practice imply an application of the archipelagic principle.

With regard to the Canary Islands, it indicates that the problems of this Community must be addressed through the socio-economic development of the archipelago taking care of sectors such as fishing, tourism, the environment, as well as promoting transport and communications, being essential for this purpose the use and economic, political and ecological control of archipelagic waters.

In another order of things, the application of the Convention regarding the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Canary Islands has a clear problem. In the areas to the west and north there are waters facing Morocco or the Sahara and Portugal, so it is necessary to carry out an international delimitation, which must be carried out in accordance with article 74. This article points out the need to reach an agreement between the States with adjacent or opposite coasts in order to reach an equitable solution. In addition, it indicates the possibility of concluding provisional arrangements of a practical nature that in any case prejudice the final delimitation.

Spain established the equidistance rule in Law 15/78, on the delimitation of the Exclusive Economic Zone and Continental Shelf. In addition, this method has been applied unilaterally, as has happened in the case of oil surveys, pending the establishment of a cartographic delimitation of the median line between the two States.

For its part, Morocco had already established in 1981, prior to the Convention, the principle of equidistance along with that of equity, in its Royal Decree no 1.81.179 of 08 April 1981 on Exclusive Economic Zone. Based on that equity, Morocco has been arguing the need to obtain a greater exclusive economic zone since it considers as fundamental the Canary Island's insular factor against the Moroccan mainland, as well as the remoteness of the Canaries with respect to Europe or its defragmentation, as well as the concavity of the African coastline.

Figure 1: Exclusive Economic Zone of the Canary Islands (Source: *Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE) n.119/2017*)

2.2.2 Transposition in domestic law

At the end of the 70s, Law 10/1977 on territorial Sea was approved. This law starts from the island to establish the layout of the straight baselines, each island therefore consisting of its 12 miles of inland sea, constituting inland waters those that remain inside these baselines

This law establishes the existence of zones of High Seas between some islands, and the overlap of the territorial sea of others states due to the lack of delimitation of the exclusive economic Zone.

The State has slightly mitigated this situation in Law 27/1992, establishing a contiguous area of 24 miles, in which it may only exercise oversight functions, to prevent and punish violations of laws and customs, tax, immigration or health and contraband regulations.

Subsequently, Law 15/1978 is passed on the delimitation of the exclusive economic zone. This law establishes as a limit to measure the beginning of said area the archipelago perimeter, drawn with straight baselines that join the extreme points of the islands, following the general configuration of the archipelago. This law has not been developed since it has not been established by the Government through Royal Decree the layout of the baselines, despite the continuous proposals and requests made in the Cortes. After the entry into force of the III Convention on the rights of the sea and the treatment established in it about the State Archipelagos and the archipelagic States, the development of this law becomes even more complicated, since it could contradict the above in international law.

The Supreme Court ruled again in 1993 under the same terms, stating that “from the point of view of domestic law it could be understood that the exclusive economic zone of the 200 miles measured according to the bases of the archipelago principle is understood, since it may be assumed tacitly repealed by Law 10/1977; interpreting at the same time art. 2nd of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands (Organic Law 10/1982, of August 10) as an expression of a unitary whole described by the relation of its components, within a comprehensive space of soil, subsoil, airspace and territorial waters that surround the archipelago perimeter "also in relation to international law, despite not being in Spain yet the III UNCLOS notes that" sitting the above, abounds in the archipelagic conception art. 40, part IV of the text of the III Conference of the Sea, which defines the archipelago as a group of islands, including parts of islands and the waters that connect them, whose related natural characteristics form an intrinsic economic and political geographical entity or that historically it has been considered as such; all of them predicable notes of the archipelago that constitutes the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands.

In 1998, with the UNCLOS in force, the Supreme Court once again reaffirmed the application of the archipelagic principle of straight baselines provided by Law 15/1978, which would have tacitly repealed Law 10/1977. It takes as arguments the contradiction between both laws, as well as the concept of the archipelago that introduces the 1996 reform of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands and the numerous cases of comparative law in which mixed states use the archipelago principle. Even the Court uses the lack of contradiction between the 1978 law and the Montego Bay Convention, since it is not expressly prohibited therein.

The Law 44/2010, of December 30, on Canarian waters, represents an advance regarding the parliamentary initiatives on the delimitation of the Canarian waters and comes to complete the concept of the archipelago contained in article 2 of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands. It consists of a single article under the name of "Aguas Canarias" and which states the following:

1. Among the most protruding extreme points of the islands and islets that make up, according to article 2 of its Statute of Autonomy, the Canary Islands, a perimeter contour will be drawn that follows the general configuration of the archipelago, as established in the Annex of this Law. The waters that are integrated within this perimeter contour will receive the denomination of Canary waters and constitute the special maritime area of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands.

2. The exercise of state or regional powers over the Canarian waters and, where appropriate, over the remaining maritime spaces surrounding the Canary Islands over which the Spanish State exercises sovereignty or jurisdiction will be carried out taking into account the material distribution of established powers constitutionally and statutory for both such spaces and for land.

It also incorporates an additional provision entitled "Respect for International Law" which indicates that the outline of the perimeter contour will not alter the delimitation of the maritime spaces of the Canary Islands as established by the Spanish legal system under current International Law.

The law establishes two final provisions. In the first one, the Government is empowered to develop this law through regulations after a report from the Government of the Canary Islands, while in the second; a period of 3 months is established for its entry into force.

Finally, two annexes are incorporated, in order to establish the extreme points of the islands for the establishment of perimeter baselines and their representation on a map.

Article 132.3 of the Spanish Constitution establishes that "State-owned assets are those determined by law and, in any case, the maritime-terrestrial zone, the beaches, the territorial sea and the natural resources of the economic zone and the platform continental" which grants the State's competence for its delimitation but is not, in any case, establish a competence criterion. The true competence distribution is established in articles 148 and 149 CE and the respective Statutes of Autonomy.

Regarding the latter, article 147.2.b) EC indicates that the delimitation of its territory will be necessary content of the Statutes of Autonomy, since it will be limited to the effectiveness of its rules and the exercise of its powers.

As stated in STC 38/2002, "in the competence distribution set up by the Constitution and the respective Statutes of the Autonomous Communities, the exercise of a competence attributed to one of them must have as support and budget the territory in which that Community exercises its powers, so that it operates as a limit for that, since if such an area of competence were not respected it could unduly invade that of another community"

This is established by Article 40 of the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands: "All the powers contained in this Statute are understood as referring to the territorial scope of the Autonomous Community defined in Article 2, without prejudice to the exclusive competence of the State over water of Spanish jurisdiction." This article 2 makes no reference to the maritime territory, although after the 1996 reform the term "archipelago" was introduced.

The jurisprudence has been pronounced in recent times in the same sense, rejecting that the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands includes in the definition of its territory the sea, not even implicitly in the term "archipelago". For jurisprudence this is fundamental since it has established

as a criterion for the exercise of autonomous powers the express attribution by the Statute or that derives from the nature of those competences.

The inclusion of waters in the Canarian territory by the Statute, in order to be able to exercise its powers over them, is part of the reform that is currently being processed. On April 9, 2015, the Canary Islands Statute Reform Proposal was approved at the Plenary of the Canary Islands Parliament.

Article 4 of this reform, signed as a “spatial scope”, exposes the following text:

1. The space area of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands includes the Canary archipelago, composed of the sea and the seven islands with own administration of El Hierro, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, La Gomera, Lanzarote, La Palma and Tenerife, as well as the island of La Graciosa and the island territories of Alegranza, Lobos, Montaña Clara, Roque del Este and Roque del Oeste.
2. Canary waters are defined from the perimeter of the Archipelago, delimited according to the polygon of straight baselines that join the extreme points of the islands, in accordance with international conventions signed by Spain.
3. The Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands shall exercise the powers attributed by this Statute in the space of the archipelago, defined in section 1 above.
4. State powers that, by their nature, can be exercised by the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands in the territorial sea and exclusive economic zone, as well as on the seabed and in the subsoil of these maritime spaces, they may be transferred or delegated to it, through the procedures constitutionally provided.

It also adds article 97 includes the principle of territoriality, stating that “the exercise of the autonomous competences will display its effectiveness in the spatial scope of the Canary Islands established in article 4 of this Statute, without prejudice, where appropriate, of the possible effects that reason for the competition exercised may have outside its territory.”

This totally exceptional possibility of extending the autonomic competences outside the territory of the Autonomous Community has been admitted by the Constitutional Court “when the nature of the competition so demands, although the autonomous title does not include express reference to its projection on the sea” as It may be in the field of aquaculture or the management of the fishing and shellfish sector, whose nature obviously leads to a projection towards the sea, or in terms of environment or protected natural areas if it is essential for the exercise of these powers.

Figure 2: Canarian waters jurisdiction (Source: BOE 38120140)

The Spanish Constitutional Court has been using a strict and restricted conception of the territory, limited to the terrestrial space, excluding maritime spaces, unless, as previously indicated, an express statutory attribution is established or derives from the nature of the competition. A theory that has served as a basis for rejecting any type of claim of the Community in relation to being able to decide on authorizations of power generation facilities in the territorial sea or the permits granted to Repsol to explore and investigate in the seabed. However, if the current reform of the Statute mentioned above is approved with the inclusion of the waters in the territory of the Community, the Canary Islands may claim those powers that are currently denied.

Conclusions

The Spanish regulations in charge of delimiting the maritime zones in Spain are scarce and not fully developed. There is a difficult fit between the aforementioned Law 10/1977 and Law 15/1978, which present a clear inconsistency, nor have agreements been reached regarding this delimitation with those countries with which the Canary Islands have opposite coasts, such as Morocco or Portugal.

This lack of delimitation implies for the islands an enormous legal uncertainty that has been revealed in the claims by the Government of the Canary Islands

Although the UNCLOS has established the treatment of the Archipelagic States, it has remained silent regarding the State Archipelagos, something that has generated different doctrinal opinions, among which are in favor of the application of the archipelagic principle in the mixed States and those who reject it categorically. This silence may be due to the fact that the regional model established by the Spanish Constitution of 1978 did not begin to develop until the early 1980s, so it

could not be taken into account in the debates of the III Conference from which it emerged the 1982 Convention on the Law of the Sea.

Therefore, the currently applicable international and national norms on marine space are:

- 1- The currently existing delimitation of the maritime waters of the Canary archipelago is correct and in accordance with International Law of the Sea.
- 2- The archipelagic statute provided for in Part IV of the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea is not applicable in the Canary Islands.
- 3- A system of straight baselines is not applicable in the waters of the Canary archipelago that intends to establish for these waters the regime of internal waters.
- 4- The issues that really arise, whether of legislative competence, of executive competence, must and can be resolved by application of Articles 148.11 and 150.2 of the Spanish Constitution.
- 5- By virtue of the provisions of Art. 132.2 of the Constitution, it does not seem appropriate that the delimitation of the maritime spaces of the Canary Islands expressly appears in the statute of autonomy of the Community, which does not mean the impossibility of transferring competences to the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands.

Figure 3: Inland waters extension of the autonomous community of the Canary Islands
(Source: BOE 38120140)

2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 The MSFD application

The development of the Marine Strategies of Spain (EsMaRES) is required by the Directive

2008/56 / EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, which establishes a framework for community action for policy of the marine environment, the so-called Framework Directive on the Marine Strategy (MSFD). This Directive introduces, in its article 5, the obligation to achieve the good environmental state of European marine waters, at the latest in 2020, through the development of Marine Strategies, with the final objective of maintaining biodiversity and preserving diversity and the dynamism of oceans and seas that are clean, healthy and productive, and whose use is sustainable.

The MSFD was transposed into the Spanish legal system through Law 41/2010, of December 29, on the Protection of the Marine Environment (LPMM), which includes planning, conservation, protection and improvement of the marine environment, with the aim of achieving or maintain its good environmental condition. The MSFD establishes a series of actions that must be carried out by the Member States for the preparation of the Marine Strategies, as well as cooperation between different States when they share marine regions or subregions.

The development of the Marine Strategies follows a consecutive steps approach and has to be developed for each of the five Marine Demarcations (DM) into which the marine regions and subregions that are under Spanish sovereignty or jurisdiction have been divided, which are, as established in Article 6 of the LPMM:

1. Noratlantic Marine Demarcation (NOR).
2. South Atlantic Marine Demarcation (LDS).
3. Marine Demarcation of the Strait and Alboran (ESAL).
4. Marine Demarcation Levantino-Balear (LEBA).
5. Canary Island Demarcation (CAN).

Figure 4: The five Marine Demarcations (Source: Abramich et al., 2018)

The development of the Marine Strategies begins with an initial evaluation (phase 1) of the current environmental status and the impact of human activities on the marine environment, based on the indicative list of characteristics, pressures and impacts of Annex I of the LPMM. Subsequently, each DM defines the good environmental status (BEA) of the marine environment (phase 2) for the qualitative descriptors described in Annex II of the LPMM. The procedure continues by establishing a series of environmental objectives (phase 3) and associated indicators, in order to achieve the BEA of the marine environment. The process continues with the development and implementation of monitoring programs (phase 4) that permanently assess the environmental status of the marine environment and the effectiveness of the measures implemented. This monitoring is carried out considering the initial evaluation and in accordance with the provisions of Annex IV of the LPMM. And, finally, the programs of measures are elaborated (phase 5), which will be necessary to achieve or maintain the BEA of the marine environment.

The LPMM, which incorporates MSFD into the Spanish legal system, has as its ultimate objective, to achieve or maintain the good environmental status of the marine environment by 2020. To do so, it establishes the EsMaRES as essential instruments for planning the marine environment. Therefore, they constitute the general framework to which the different sectoral policies and administrative actions with an impact on the marine environment must necessarily conform according to what is established in the corresponding sectoral legislation.

To achieve the BEA of the marine environment it is necessary to carry out a coherent planning of the activities that are developed under an ecosystem approach, which guarantees the protection of

the goods and services provided by the seas and oceans and taking into account the necessary integration of the social and economic variables inherent in the development of activities. Objectives of the EsMaRES:

- a) Protect and preserve the marine environment, including its biodiversity, prevent its deterioration and recover marine ecosystems in areas that have been negatively affected.
- b) Prevent and reduce discharges into the marine environment, with a view to progressively eliminating pollution of the marine environment, to ensure that there are no serious impacts or risks to marine biodiversity, marine ecosystems, health human or the permitted uses of the sea.
- c) Ensure that activities and uses in the marine environment are compatible with the preservation of its biodiversity.

Measures contemplated: The Measurement Programs are established in the last phase of the development of the EMEs. These programs include the specific proposal of actions to be carried out by all competent administrations, in order to maintain or achieve the BEA previously defined for the marine environment.

Bearing in mind all the starting information, the program of measures to achieve the environmental objectives is developed, taking into account the following areas:

- Rules applicable to activities with an impact on the marine environment;
- Guidelines on the uses of the marine environment;
- Action projects;
- Geographical or temporary restrictions on uses;
- Control measures and pollution reduction, among others.
- Spatial protection measures, to contribute to the constitution of coherent and representative networks of marine protected areas that adequately cover the diversity of the ecosystems that compose them.
- Specific measures for the protection of species and types of habitats, in particular, the development and application of Strategies and Plans for recovery and conservation of marine species of the Spanish Catalog of Endangered Species, as well as Strategies and Plans for conservation and restoration of marine habitats included in the Spanish Catalog of habitats in danger of disappearance, defined in Law 42/2007, on natural heritage and biodiversity.

The programs of measures are classified into existing measures: those that have already been defined in the framework of other environmental policies by the different competent authorities (both at the level of the General State Administration –AGE– and the Autonomous Communities –CC.AA.–), and are totally or partially implemented, and new measures: that can be framed in the community regulations or in existing international agreements, but that go beyond the obligations that the States have according to these norms, and those that do not rely on those norms, for addressing aspects not covered by previous normative tools.

Conceptually, the new measures are those that are proposed after applying the process of rational analysis of the starting situation, the objectives to be achieved, and how close or far it is so that these objectives can be achieved. This analysis is known as the "gap analysis" and the way in which it should be carried out has been widely discussed and finally agreed between the Member States within the framework of the MSFD's Common Implementation Strategy.

The proposal of the EME measurement programs has been structured in nine themes, taking into account the descriptors of Annex II of the LPMM:

- 1- Biodiversity (Descriptors 1, 4, and 6).
- 2- Marine protected areas.
- 3- Alloctone species (Descriptor 2).
- 4- Commercially exploited species (Descriptor 3).
- 5- Eutrophication, Contaminants and their effects, Contaminants in the products of the fishing (Descriptors 5, 8 and 9).
- 6- Permanent alterations of hydrographic conditions (Descriptor 7).
- 7- Marine litter (Descriptor 10).
- 8- Underwater noise (Descriptor 11).
- 9- Horizontal measures: includes measures related to public participation, governance, knowledge improvement, etc., or measures that encompass several descriptors.

The overall proposal includes 97 new measures.

On the other hand, Spain shares several marine subregions with three Member States: Portugal, Italy and France, so that cross-border effects could occur with the application of the new EME measures. The MSFD establishes in its article 6 that the Member States in each marine subregion will do everything possible to coordinate their actions. In this regard, Spain regularly participates in regional and subregional coordination processes through the two Regional Seas conventions: OSPAR in the Atlantic and Barcelona in the Mediterranean, as well as through other coordination mechanisms.

The actions that derive from the Program of Measures of the EsMaRES and are applied in a general way for all the Spanish marine environment or in particular for each Marine Demarcation, will take into account, in addition to the environmental objectives that were defined in 2012 during the preparation of the EsMaRES, the following community and international objectives:

- Sustainable development, as a horizontal principle applicable to all policies developed by the Member States, according to Article 3 of the Treaty on European Union.
- The sustainable use of natural resources. (Europe 2020 Strategy [COM (2011) 571]).
- The impulse of renewable energies and at the same time an energy saving. (European Strategy 2020 [COM (2010) 2020]).
- The reduction of air pollution (Thematic strategy regarding air pollution [COM (2005) 446].
- The arrest of the loss of biodiversity. (EU strategy on biodiversity until 2020 [COM (2011) 244]).

- The protection of biodiversity and ecosystem services. (EU strategy on biodiversity until 2020 [COM (2011) 244 final]).
- The protection, management and planning of the landscape and promotion of actions that involve the protection and revaluation of cultural heritage (European Landscape Convention 2004, ratified by Spain in 2007).
- The protection of the coast by promoting sustainable development and integrated management of coastal areas [COM (2000) 547 final].
- The prevention of marine pollution, minimizing the effects of ocean acidification and regulating fishing activity to sustainably protect marine and coastal ecosystems. (Objective 14-United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, 2015).
- The protection of inland waters when actions derived from EMEs have direct or indirect effects on coastal, transitional, river and groundwater (Water Framework Directive, 2000).

The marine protected areas and spaces of the Natura 2000 marine network: Before implementing any measure or action derived from the EsMaRES, the list of protected areas of the territorial area where the measure / action is applied will be updated for consideration, including those that are in the processing phase for their declaration.

The actions that affect spaces cataloged with some protection figure, such as Natura 2000 Network (SCI, SAC and SPA), Marine Protected Areas (OSPAR Agreement), list of Wetlands of International Importance (RAMSAR list), Marine Reserves and the rest of figures included in Law 42/2007, of December 13, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity, will be subject to a specific evaluation that will be carried out in accordance with the corresponding legislation, without compromising the conservation objectives of the places.

In any case, for those actions that arise from being located in these spaces and still not having an impact on them (after a detailed analysis of the environmental risk and its corresponding environmental assessment), the following determinations will be taken into account:

- Within the scope of the Special Bird Protection Areas (SPA), the effects of the actions on the bird colonies during the breeding and breeding periods will be analyzed and, if necessary, the work will be restricted.
- In spaces that are migratory corridors of marine species (cetaceans, sea turtles or others), it will be avoided to act during their migration periods.
- On seabed with phanerogams, the installation of any structure that involves the degradation of the prairie will be avoided.

They will opt for those actions or alternatives that minimize the presence of permanent elements within the scope of the Natura 2000 Network and in no case if they involve a significant deterioration of unique fauna or communities (gorgonians or others).

The permanent condition and occupation in the types of habitats of community interest outside the spaces of the Natura 2000 Network will be avoided or minimized, where some of the measures proposed in the EsMaRES will be applied.

The following environmental criteria and principles that affect Marine Protected Spaces of the different DMs will be included:

- To the extent possible, limit the expansion of activities and / or uses, already authorized, located in areas declared Special Marine Conservation Areas (SAC).
- Prioritize the recovery and restoration of marine spaces of environmental interest, officially declared, that are in the process of degradation, compared to the creation of new ones.
- To the extent possible, limit activities that may involve conditions in areas with proven ecological importance and presence of cetaceans.
- Before authorizing any type of installation or activity, or the extension of existing ones, a zoning and determination of compatible uses must be carried out and incompatible within the already declared marine SAC.
- Possible extensions of SAC areas will be studied as a compensatory mean when, for reasons of general interest of the first order, maritime uses and / or activities must be implemented within them that imply significant impacts on the pre-existing environmental values that it propitiates with its declaration as SAC.
- The declaration of the SPAMI of the Migratory Corridor of cetaceans of the western Mediterranean will be analyzed as a concrete objective.

On the protection and conservation of marine protected species: The actions derived from the development of the EsMaRES have to be compatible with:

The plans and / or measures for conservation and management of marine species (European cloth, spiny fish, cormorant, Balearic shepherd, Audouin gull, etc.) that at the time of implementing the measures contemplated in the EsMaRES are in vigor or in process.

Within the framework of the BIO10 measure, some of the proposals made by the administrations consulted regarding the establishment of areas or perimeters to exclude the use of fishing gear and longline fishing in the vicinity of the colonies breeding cormorant, that are located in the coastal areas of both Biscay and the rest of the Spanish coast. In this regard, the recommendation of non-use of gill at depths less than 30 meters and at a distance of not less than 500 meters around the colonies of cormorant will be analyzed.

In spaces that are migratory corridors of protected marine species (cetaceans, sea turtles or other species), it will be avoided to act during their migration periods.

Regarding the Prospecting and Data Processing Program of the seabed (measure BIO34), it will be verified that the methodology that will be used in the seabed prospecting campaigns will imply the absence or minimization of the impact on the marine fauna.

Hydrological planning and protection of the continental water environment: Taking into account, that the EsMaRES will not be applicable in coastal waters, in those aspects that are already regulated by the regulations derived from the Water Framework Directive and that their scope of action does not affect, in any case, the public hydraulic domain, it should be added that the

measures and actions derived from the EsMaRES:

They must be compatible with hydrological planning (National Hydrological Plan and hydrological plans of the basin).

The hydrological dynamics will not be affected and the water environment will be protected from any alteration (contamination, degradation, etc.), maintaining the good state of the waters that can be intercepted by future actions within the framework of the EsMaRES.

Relationship of actions with adaptation and mitigation against climate change: The Spanish MAPAMA Office of Climate Change agrees with the treatment given to this aspect in the EsMaRES, therefore, in the selection and application of the actions derived from them will take into account their contribution to mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

Protection of underwater cultural heritage: Ensure that the measures collected under the EsMaRES do not have negative effects on the underwater Cultural Heritage. In the actions derived from these measures, therefore, the preservation of underwater cultural heritage will be considered in accordance with the international, national and regional legislation applicable.

Once the actions derived from the EsMaRES and their locations are defined, their viability will be checked in relation to the possible impact on the Underwater Historical and Cultural Heritage and, where appropriate, corrective measures will be established in the framework of the evaluation corresponding environmental.

Eradication and control of invasive alien species: In the implementation of measures related to the control and eradication of invasive alien species, the coordination and participation of the authorities of bordering countries is considered especially relevant.

Dissemination and awareness among administrations involved in the implementation of EME measures and society: The dissemination of the EsMaRES will be promoted among all the entities involved in the application of the same, in order to take them into consideration in their fields competencies For this, it would be convenient to prepare informative and training campaigns to be developed among the population sectors, companies and other entities involved in their application in each DM.

On Environmental Monitoring: Within the framework of the monitoring programs of the EsMaRES and of this environmental assessment, the MAPAMA General Directorate of Sustainability of the Coast and the Sea, as a substantive body, will periodically monitor the main effects of the application of these produces in the environment.

In this area of environmental monitoring, it would be advisable not only to have the participation of the Autonomous Communities with powers in the planning and execution of the measures envisaged in the EsMaRES, but also to involve the agencies, public and private entities, social agents, scientific entities, etc. that have participated in the elaboration of the same and that collaborate in the execution of the proposed actions and measures.

2.2.2 The Strategic Environmental Assessment application

The Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) or environmental evaluation of plans and programs represents a step forward in the protection of the environment, since it contributes to the integration of environmental considerations in the preparation and preparation of plans and programs. It is a prevention instrument that allows the integration of environmental aspects into public plans and programs.

The SEA is regulated by Directive 2001/42 / EC; this regulation was transposed into the Spanish law through Law 9/2006 on the evaluation of the effects of certain plans and programs on the environment. This law has been repealed by Law 21/2013, on environmental assessment, BOE No. 296, of December 11, 2013. The strategic environmental assessment is defined in Title II, Chapter I of said law.

Law 14/2014, of December 26, on Harmonization and Simplification in the Protection of the Territory and Natural Resources, regulates in its title I the strategic environmental evaluation of plans and programs with territorial or urban effects and the environmental evaluation of Projects.

As already indicated, Title I, whose content will be studied from this moment, regulates the strategic environmental evaluation of plans and programs with territorial or urban effects and the environmental evaluation of projects.

As in Law 21/2013, of December 9, on basic state environmental assessment by stating, in its article 20.2, that the purpose of this Law is “to achieve a high level of environmental protection, to contribute, in accordance with the principle of sustainable development, to integrate environmental aspects into plans, programs and projects that may have significant effects on the environment in the territorial scope of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, as well as establishing the appropriate mechanisms that allow the effectiveness of protective, corrective and compensatory measures”.

Regarding the environmental body, section 4 indicates that the competent environmental body for the strategic environmental assessment will be “the Canary Islands Territorial and Environmental Planning Commission”. This decision also deserves some comment, since a large part of the management plans that make up the Canary planning system are approved by the Commission itself or with its previous and mandatory report. That is, on many occasions the aforementioned Commission will act as an environmental body and as a sector body.

The SEA has as its priority objectives:

- Contribute to decision-making from the perspective of sustainability,
- Improve the quality of policies, plans and programs,
- Strengthen and facilitate the EIA of projects,
- Promote new ways of making decisions taking into account the Environment.

The main characteristics of SEA is the ability to influence the highest levels of decision at the institutional level that allows dialogue between the various public and private actors, and when applied at the early stage of decision-making it is a preventive instrument.

The SEA is a process that is ahead of the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), detecting the environmental impacts derived from the policies, plans and programs. These two environmental analysis tools complement each other, resulting in the creation of a series of generic corrective

measures for groups of projects with similar characteristics, thus simplifying the EIA process and reducing the number of projects submitted to this procedure.

Plans and Programs to which the law applies

According to article 3, plans and programs, as well as their modifications, that may have significant effects on the environment and that meet the following two requirements will be subject to environmental assessment, in accordance with this law:

- a) That they are drawn up or approved by a public Administration.
- b) That its preparation and approval is required by a legal or regulatory provision or by agreement of the Council of Ministers or the Governing Council of an autonomous community.

Law 9/2006 establishes in the same article two groups of plans and programs that should be subject to environmental evaluation since it is assumed that they can have significant effects on the environment. These are the plans and programs:

- That they establish the framework for the future authorization of projects legally subject to environmental impact assessment, in certain subjects.
- Those who require an evaluation in accordance with the regulatory regulations of the Natura 2000 Network.

In the rest of the cases, it will be the environmental body, according to article 4, which will determine whether a plan or program or its modification should be subject to environmental assessment. They are included in this determination (Article 3 (3)):

- Plans or programs that establish the use of areas of reduced territorial scope.
- Minor modifications of plans and programs.
- Other plans and programs.

However, there are exceptions to the general rule. The following plans and programs will not be subject to environmental assessment:

- Those whose sole purpose is national defense or civil protection in cases of emergency.
- Those of financial or budgetary type.
- Plans co-financed by the EU under the respective programming periods in force by Regulations 1257/1999 and 1260/1999.

The incorporation into the Spanish legal system of Directive 201/42 / EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, of June 27, 2001, regarding the evaluation of the effects of certain plans and programs on the environment, through the Law 9/2006, of April 28 and Decree 55/2006, of May 9, which approves the regulation of procedures of the planning instruments of the Canary Islands planning system, establishes the need to carry out an environmental assessment on establishment and management plans of protected areas.

An Environmental Sustainability Report is prepared in compliance with the application of said Law on land management plans, specifically on the Master Plan of any protected areas, the Island Planning Plan of Gran Canaria and the General Management Guidelines. Its wording is based on the Reference Document to prepare sustainability reports of the Plans and Norms of Protected Natural Areas prepared by the Ministry of Environment and Territorial Planning of the Government

of the Canary Islands, applying the methodological principles contained in Annex I of the Law 9/2006. The purpose of the Master Plan is the detailed planning of the space and the establishment of determinations, directive standards and criteria, as established in article 22 of the Consolidated Text of the Laws of Planning of the Territory of the Canary Islands and Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands, approved by Legislative Decree 1/2000, of May 8. This Master Plan is in accordance with the provisions of the current General Management Guidelines of the Canary Islands and the Island Management Plan of the island of Gran Canaria according to article 14.4 of Legislative Decree 1/2000.

It is the main objective of the Plan to guarantee the protection of the environment and the rational use of natural resources through the regulation of uses, especially those related to environmental conservation, public use and research.

In addition, other documents included in ESA are:

- Justification report: develops the environmental diagnosis of the reserve. In addition to an analysis of alternatives that culminates with the description and justification of the proposed arrangement.
- Normative document: it constitutes the legal-administrative framework through which the proposed activities and actions are regulated. It includes zoning and categorization of space.
- Economic-financial document: it consists of the economic valuation of the different action programs, as well as a list of financial aid.
- Cartographic Annex: includes the information plans and regulations of the space.

Figure 5: Summary procedure for the environmental plan evaluation

2.2.3 The Environmental Impact Assessment application

The Law 21/2013, of December 9, on environmental impact assessment (EIA) of projects has entered into force on December 12, 2013 in case of evaluations processed by the State Administration, and on December 12, 2014 for evaluations processed by the Autonomous Communities.

In the tenth final provision, concerning the entry into force, it was specified that the standard would enter into force the day after its publication, that is, on December 12, 2013, however, when it deepens more in its application (final provision eleventh and the single repeal provision) it is observed that the autonomous communities are given a period of one year to adapt their regulations to this Law.

Regulatory repeal:

1. All provisions of equal or lower rank that oppose this law and, in particular, the following are repealed:

- a) Law 9/2006, of April 28, on the evaluation of the effects of certain plans and programs on the environment.
- b) The Consolidated text of the Project Environmental Impact Assessment Law, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2008, of January 11.
- c) Royal Decree 1131/1988, of September 30, which approves the Regulations for the execution of Royal Legislative Decree 1302/1986, of June 28, on Environmental Impact Assessment.

2. The repeal of the norms provided for in the previous section, in their condition as basic regulations and with respect to the Autonomous Communities, will occur, in any case, within one year of the entry into force of this law. However, if before the end of this period, the Autonomous Communities approve new regulatory texts adapted to this law, the derogation provided for in the previous section will occur at the time the new regional regulations come into force.

3. The first additional Provision of Law 11/2005, of June 22, which modifies Law 10/2001, of July 5, 2001, of the National Hydrological Plan is repealed.

In summary, if any autonomous community before December 12, 2014 published its own regulations adapted to this Environmental Assessment Law 21/2013, when said regulation enters into force, the following regulations would automatically be repealed in that autonomous community:

- Law 9/2006, of April 28, on the evaluation of the effects of certain plans and programs on the environment.
- The Consolidated text of the Project Environmental Impact Assessment Law, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2008, of January 11.
- Royal Decree 1131/1988, of September 30, which approves the Regulations for the

execution of Royal Legislative Decree 1302/1986, of June 28, on Environmental Impact Assessment.

If not, until December 12, 2014 these rules will remain in force in that autonomous community and Law 21/2013 will not be applicable.

The aforementioned Law presents the main novelty of unifying in a single legal text the legal regime of the environmental evaluation of plans, programs and projects, which, until now, was regulated and in Law 9/2006, of April 28, on the evaluation of the effects of certain projects, which was regulated in Royal Legislative Decree 1/2008, of January 11, by which approves the consolidated text of the Law on Environmental Impact Assessment of projects.

Substantial modifications have not been made regarding the scope of the law in relation to the laws that are now repealed. However, certain sections of Annexes I and II of the consolidated text of the Law on Environmental Impact Assessment of projects, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2008, of 11 of December 11, have been incorporated within the scope of this law. It has also included the possibility that projects subject to a simplified environmental impact assessment undergo the ordinary procedure when requested by the promoter.

This law is based on the exclusive competence of the State in matters of basic legislation on environmental protection, without prejudice to the powers of the autonomous communities to establish additional protection standards.

Regarding structure and content, this law consists of 64 articles distributed in three titles:

Title I: establishes the principles and provisions of a general nature, applicable to both the strategic environmental assessment and the environmental impact assessment.

Title II: is dedicated, in separate chapters, to strategic environmental assessment and environmental impact assessment, establishing a basic regulation, applicable, therefore, to the entire territory of the State with the exceptions established in the eighth final provision, which determines the articles that do not have a basic character (Art. 3.3, 8.3, 8.4.11.1; Chapter III of Title III; the sixth additional provision; paragraphs 2 and 3 of the seventh additional provision; and the ninth additional provision; deadlines established in Arts. 17, 18, 19, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47 and in the tenth additional provision.)

Title III: regulates the monitoring and the sanctioning regime.

Law 21/2013 has, therefore, as its main objective and purpose to subject to an adequate environmental evaluation any plan, program or project that may have significant effects on the environment, before its adoption, approval or authorization, or, if it is appropriate, in the case of projects, before submitting a responsible statement or prior communication.

Chapter I of Title II contains the provisions related to strategic environmental assessment, regulating ordinary and simplified procedures.

Chapter II of Title II regulates the environmental impact assessment of projects. It may be, like the strategic, ordinary or simplified.

The following projects will be subject to an ordinary environmental impact assessment (Art.7.1):

- a) Those included in ANNEX I, as well as projects that, being presented in fractional terms, reach the thresholds of ANNEX I through the accumulation of the magnitudes or dimensions of each of the projects considered.
- b) Those submitted to a simplified environmental impact assessment, when the environmental body so decides on a case-by-case basis, in the environmental impact report in accordance with the criteria of ANNEX III.
- c) Any modification of the characteristics of a project consigned in ANNEX I or in ANNEX II, when said modification meets, by itself, the thresholds established in ANNEX I.
- d) Projects submitted to a simplified environmental impact assessment, when requested by the developer.

The following projects will be subject to a simplified environmental impact assessment (Art.7.2):

The projects included in ANNEX II.

Projects not included in ANNEX I or ANNEX II that may significantly affect, directly or indirectly, Red Natura 2000 Protected Areas.

Any modification of the characteristics of a project of ANNEX I or of ANNEX II, other than the modifications described in article 7.1.c) already authorized, executed or in process of execution, which may have significant adverse effects on the environment. It will be understood that this modification may have significant adverse effects.

The Law 14/2014 of December 26, issued by Canarian Government on Harmonization and Simplification in the Protection of the Territory and Natural Resources, regulates in its title I the strategic environmental evaluation of plans and programs with territorial or urban effects and the environmental evaluation of Projects.

The regulation of project evaluation is much simpler than that of plans and programs and follows both the provisions of the corresponding Directive and the basic state regulations.

Thus, article 23.1 provides that the following projects will be subject to an ordinary environmental impact assessment:

- a) Those included in Annex I of this law, such as projects that, being presented in installments, reach the thresholds of Annex I by means of the accumulation of the magnitudes or dimensions of each of the projects considered.
- b) Those included in annex II of this law when the environmental body in the environmental impact report so decides, on a case-by-case basis, in accordance with the criteria in annex III.

- c) Any modification or extension of a project listed in Annex I or Annex II, when said modification or extension meets the possible thresholds established in Annex I.
- d) Projects that should be subject to a simplified environmental impact assessment, when requested by the promoter.
- e) The projects and activities included in annex II of this law when they are intended to be carried out in critical areas of cataloged species, as established in article 56.1 of Law 41/2007, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity, or in areas or surfaces that are part of the Natura 2000 Network.
- f) The singular projects not expressly listed in Annex I or II, but in which extraordinary circumstances concur that, in the opinion of the Canary Islands Government, have a high ecological or environmental risk. In such cases, the Governing Council will take a specific reasoned agreement. Said agreement must be made public.

The competent environmental body for the evaluation of ordinary environmental impact will be the Canary Islands Territorial and Environmental Planning Commission. The competent environmental body for the simplified environmental impact assessment will be the competent substantive body to decide on the approval of the project or, where appropriate, to control the activity through the responsible declaration or prior communication.

Figure 6: Strategic Environmental Assessment and Environmental Impact Assessment

Environmental impact assessment of projects

Chapter III of this title II regulates the procedure for assessing the environmental impact of projects.

The Law states in its article 31 the modalities and procedures of environmental impact evaluation of projects: *“The promoters of projects that must be subject to environmental evaluation, as the provisions of this law may apply, may choose to submit the project to the public modality of environmental impact assessment through administrative bodies, included in sections 1 and 2 of this chapter, or submit the project to the modality of environmental impact assessment through the accreditation system provided for in article 42 of this law ”.*

The public assessment of environmental impacts

Regarding the public modality of ordinary evaluation of environmental impact of projects, article 32 regulates the study of environmental impact, following what is established in article 34 of Law

21/2013 and annex VI of this. Regarding the procedure, Article 33 of the Autonomous Law contains the regulation of the procedure for the ordinary evaluation of the environmental impact of projects. Here, in addition to the reference to the regulation, as in relation to the strategic evaluation, there are rules that in any case must be observed. However, these rules do, in this case, provide for the intervention of the substantive body in relation to the processing of the procedure.

Indeed, when the scope and content of the environmental impact assessment of the corresponding project is regulated by regulation, the Law provides that the substantive body “shall submit it to public information and to inquiries of the affected public administrations and interested persons, for a term of forty-five days the study of environmental impact. After the analysis of the allegations made in the consultations and in the process of public information, the complete environmental impact assessment file will be sent by the substantive body to the Canary Islands Territorial and Environmental Planning Commission, so that it may formulate the declaration of environmental impact within two months from the receipt of the complete file, or in the extension that may be available for one more month when duly justified reasons concur.” This regulation, as long as the regulatory development is not carried out, must be understood as completed by the provisions of articles 33 and 34 and 36 to 38 of Law 21/2013 for constituting said basic regulatory requirement of mandatory compliance by the Autonomous Community. For the same reason, the regulatory development carried out by the Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands must also respect these precepts.

Article 33.d) of the Autonomous Law regulates the referral of the file to the environmental body, following in this case the provisions of article 39.1 of Law 21/2013. Once the file has been received, in accordance with article 33.f) of the Autonomous Law, the environmental body will carry out a technical analysis of the complete environmental impact file, evaluating the environmental effects of the project. However, if once the technical analysis of the environmental impact file has been carried out, the environmental body concludes that additional information is required, it will request the substantive body to require the promoter, only once, to complete the impact study. This regulation must be completed by the provisions of article 40 of Law 21/2013, which regulates this technical analysis in a much more precise and detailed manner, so it must be understood as applicable in any case.

Finally, the environmental impact assessment procedure concludes with the impact statement, regulated in article 33.g, which states: “The ordinary environmental impact assessment procedure will conclude by means of an environmental impact statement, which will have the nature of a report mandatory and decisive, in which it will be established whether or not to carry out the project and, where appropriate, the conditions under which it can be developed, the corrective measures and the compensatory measures. In any case, it must include the identification of the project promoter and of the substantive body, as well as the description of the project, the summary of the result of the process of public information and of the consultations with the affected public administrations and interested persons, the summary of the technical analysis carried out by the environmental organ, and the program of environmental monitoring”. Again, this regulation is much more sparing than that contained in article 41 of Law 21/2013, so that provision must be

understood as applicable in the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands.

Article 2.1 of Directive 2011/92 / EU of December 13, 2011, regarding the evaluation of the impact of certain public and private projects on the environment, states the following: “Member States shall take the necessary measures so that, before the authorization is granted, projects that may have significant effects on the environment, by virtue, inter alia, of their nature, dimensions or location, are subject to the authorization requirement of their development and an evaluation with respect to their effects on the environment. These projects are defined in article 4”.

Following this mandate, article 38.1 of the Autonomous Law establishes that the declaration of environmental impact and the report of environmental impact “constitute mandatory and determining procedures, the omission of which results in the nullity of the substantive authorization of the project and, shall determine if appropriate or not, for the environmental effects, the realization of the project and, where appropriate, the conditions under which it can be developed, the corrective measures and the compensatory measures ”. In this regard, it should be remembered that section 3.d) of article 5 of Law 21/2013 defines the declaration of environmental impact as the “mandatory and determining report of the environmental body with which the ordinary environmental impact assessment concludes, which evaluates the integration of environmental aspects in the project and determines the conditions that must be established for the adequate protection of the environment and natural resources during execution and exploitation and, where appropriate, the dismantling or demolition of the project ”.

Faced with this “determining” nature of the environmental impact statement, the Autonomous Law, in its article 38.2, establishes the binding nature of the declarations “when the actions are planned to be carried out in national parks, natural parks, natural reserves, marine protected areas, natural monuments, protected landscapes and sites of scientific interest”. And then it adds the consequences that this binding nature has: “[...] when the environmental impact statement or the environmental impact report is unfavorable, the project will be returned to its origin for review unless the substantive body considers that it must deny authorization. ”

The accreditation system

In a novel way, article 42 regulates a voluntary procedure for evaluating the environmental impact of projects. According to its first section, the promoter of a project “may choose, as an alternative to the ordinary or simplified processing of the project impact evaluation procedure, for submitting the project to a voluntary impact evaluation procedure”. The novelty of this procedure is that it involves a “collaborating entity in environmental quality matters”.

First, the promoter will present, before an accredited collaborating entity in environmental quality matters, the study or the environmental impact document, as appropriate. It is up to said entity to analyze the documentation presented, as well as verify that it meets the required content in accordance with the law. If so, it proceeds to transfer the working documentation, with the certificate of the indicated points, to the competent environmental body, giving an account of it to the substantive body.

The environmental body proceeds to notify the substantive body, the promoter and the accredited collaborating entity of the initiation of the administrative environmental assessment procedure.

It is the responsibility of said collaborating entity to carry out the procedures for public information and consultation of the affected public administrations for a period of forty-five days, through the publication of the corresponding announcements, making available to interested parties and administrations consulted on Environmental document and the environmental study of the project. The collaborating entity must respond in a motivated manner as many allegations were presented. Likewise, it will request as many reports as necessary according to the type of project.

The collaborating entity will also carry out the technical analysis of the complete environmental impact file, evaluating the environmental effects of the project. If it concludes that additional information is required, it will require the developer, once, to complete the environmental impact study.

Next, the collaborating entity will formulate the proposal for an environmental impact statement or an environmental impact report, as appropriate, with the structure and contents established in the law, which will be sent to the management center responsible for submitting the proposals to the environmental body for to issue the declaration or environmental impact report that may apply. Likewise, once the declaration or the environmental impact report has been issued, it will send the file to the substantive body to resolve on the granting of the authorization.

2.2.6 Protected areas

In 1978, the National Institute for the Conservation of Nature (ICONA) carried out the Open Inventory of Natural Spaces of Special Protection of Gran Canaria.

In 1986, the Island Council of Gran Canaria initially approved the Special Plan for the Protection of Natural Areas of Gran Canaria (PEPEN). This Plan, although never approved, because its processing did not reach beyond public information, served as the basis for the design of Protected Natural Spaces.

Law 12/1987, of June 19, on the Declaration of Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands, in its article 2, in accordance with the provisions of article 5 of Law 15/1975, of May 2, on Protected Natural Spaces declares several natural spaces as Protected Space.

Law 4/1989, of March 27, on the Conservation of Natural Spaces and Wild Flora and Fauna that repeals the previous Law 15/1975 on Protected Natural Spaces, constituted a new framework of basic state legislation in which they should be framed the conservation and use of natural areas. In accordance with the provisions of the same in its Second Transitory Provision, the spaces declared by Canarian law are pending reclassification, to adapt to the new protection figures: Parks, Nature Reserves, Natural Monuments and Protected Landscapes.

A first Draft Law on the Protection of Natural Spaces is prepared, which is approved by the Canarian Government on October 15, 1990, thus acquiring the character of a Bill (PL-52). As an annex to it, the Phoenix Project is prepared, which cartographically defines (at a scale of 1: 5,000) the limits of the protected areas included in the cartography of Law 12/87, accompanied by a literal

description of them. When there is a change in the legislature, the parliamentary process cannot be completed and the Project is not approved.

Subsequently, another Draft Law on Protected Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands is prepared, which is approved by the Government in March 1993 and admitted for processing by the Parliament of the Canary Islands in December of the same year. Next to it, they return to redefine the technical contents of the Phoenix Project, adjusting to the new established categories, as well as establishing the new contents of the planning and management instruments.

Law 12/1994, of December 19, on Natural Areas of the Canary Islands, unanimously approved on November 16 of that same year by the Parliament of the Canary Islands, and published in the B.O.C. on December 24, it reclassifies and delimits the several Natural Space.

And, finally, the Consolidated Text, which continues to maintain the reclassification made by the previous Law 12/1994, which today articulates next to Law 9/1999 of May 13, on Territorial Planning of Canary Islands.

Law 12/1987, of June 19, on the Declaration of Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands, following this guideline includes several areas, and reclassified some protected areas already existing by Law 12/1994, of December 19, on Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands, now consolidated with Law 9/1999 on the Planning of the Canary Territory by Legislative DECREE 1/2000, of May 8, which approves the Consolidated Text of the Laws of Planning of the Territory of the Canary Islands and Natural Areas of the Canary Islands, also called as TRELOTENC'00.

According to the terrestrial zoning of the Natural Resources Management Plan and the Island Planning Plan of Gran Canaria —DECRETO 277/2003, of November 11, which definitively approves the Island Planning Plan of Gran Canaria, subject to the deficiencies noted by the Canary Islands Territory and Environment Planning Commission are resolved at a meeting held on May 20, 2003 and DECREE 68/2004 of May 25, on the Remediation of non-substantial deficiencies of the Island Planning Plan of Gran Canaria – some Special Natural Reserve has been incorporated in areas of very high natural value. These areas constitute the highest quality for conservation and naturalness because of the value, conservation status, uniqueness and fragility of biotic and abiotic elements.

The Master Plan for the Reserves management and use TRELOTENC'00 in its article 21.1.b. establishes that the basic planning and management instrument for Special Natural Reserves is the Master Plan, which will include all land uses throughout their entirety, establishing zoning, classification, land categorization, destination and use regulation permissible and pre-existing facilities, the management and action standards necessary for the conservation of its values, and criteria to evaluate the suitability and timing of its review, and may also include the regulations for scientific use of the Reserve or for public use if any, guidelines or determinations for wildlife action programs, biological sanitation, environmental monitoring, restoration of the environment, studies of interpretation of nature if necessary and any other necessary aspect aimed at fulfilling the purpose for the that was.

In addition, Guideline 16 of Law 19/2003 of April 14, which approves the General Management Guidelines and the Canary Islands Tourism Management Guidelines, establishes in section 6, which “within two years, the Administration of the Autonomous Community will write all the Plans and Norms of the Protected Natural Areas of the Canary Islands”. In this sense, the present Master Plan

constitutes the instrument defined by the regulations that must be provided by the administrative legal framework with which to regulate the uses and the development of activities carried out within the Special Natural Reserves and constitutes, at it is, the management plan referred to in article 6 of Royal Decree 1997/1995, of December 7, which establishes measures to help ensure biodiversity by conserving natural habitats and flora and fauna wild.

The Master Plan of the Special Natural Reserves displays the following effects since its approval and publication in the Official Canary Islands Bulletin:

- a) Their determinations will be mandatory and executive for the Administration and individuals.
- b) The enforceability of its determinations for the purposes of application by the Public Administration of any means of forced execution (Article 44.1.c of the TRELOTENC'00).
- c) It regulates in a binding way the use of the natural resources contained in the scope of the Reserve.
- d) Their ordination determinations prevail over territorial and urban planning which they substitute without the need for express adaptation, in accordance with the provisions of article 22.5 and the Fifth Transitory Provision. 3 of TRELOTENC'00.

Species Protection involves two major categories: (i) protection of endangered species, and (ii) protection of exploited species. Law 4/1989 represents the general and basic legal framework on nature conservation for the whole Spanish state, including guidelines for a legal regime on protected areas. Endangered species of the Canary Islands are listed in a catalog, following *Decreto 151/2001*. The catalogue includes a total of 104 marine species, 17 plants, 42 invertebrates and 45 vertebrates. In accordance with the state legislation, species are grouped in four different categories: “endangered”, “sensitive”, “vulnerable”, and “of special interest”. For the protection of species different conservation measures and recovery and handling plans, which can be specified in individualised plans and strategies, have been established. *Decreto 151/2001* also specified additions and deletions of species names in the catalogue, as well as breaches and approvals.

Table 1: Species protected under Bird and Habitat directives

	Species present in the canary islands	Endemic species	Species included in the Directives
Invertebrates	6706	3225	0
Amphibians	2	0	0
Reptiles	18	14	3
Birds	83	4	44
Mushrooms	1153	96	0
Lichen	1100	1	0
Mosses	500	6	2
Ferns	60	2	4
Superior Plants	1932	530	60

Figure 7: Areas including protected species in Gran Canaria. (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

The declaration of protected areas is regulated in the Canary Island by several different norms. There is a consolidated version of the “Ley de Espacios Naturales de Canarias” (Law of Nature Reserves) and the “Ley de Ordenación del Territorio” (Law on Spatial Planning), approved in legislative Decree 1/2000 (May 8), defining an area to be protected as “those of the terrestrial or marine territory that contain elements or natural systems of special interest or value”.

Currently, there are three large-scale protected areas, which have been created by Decree of the Government of Canarias and Ministerial Order of the State Department of Marine Fishing (Table 2).

Table 2: Marine Protected Areas of the Canary Islands

Marine reserve	Latitude	Longitude	Area (ha)	Management
Isla de la Graciosa	29°27'N	13°34'W	70.700	Administración del Estado Comunidad Autónoma Canaria
Islotes al Norte de Lanzarote	29°12'N	13°17'W		
La Restinga-Mar	27° 38,38'	17°58,59' W	750	Administración del Estado Comunidad Autónoma Canaria
De Lascalmas	N27° 36,30'	17°58,90' W		
Isla de El Hierro	N27° 40,35' N 27° 38,85' N	18°02,24' W 18°00,20' W		
Isla de La Palma	28° 34,2N	Perpendiculares	3.791	Administración del Estado

	28° 28,2N	atierra		
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In each of the reserves at least two areas are established: (i) an area of integral protection, in which no type of activity, except for scientific studies, is allowed; and (ii) an area of restricted uses, where activities such as sports diving or fishing with hook are allowed.

Natura 2000 Network in the Canary Islands

The Canary Islands presents numerous spaces that are already part of Natura 2000 and, together with Madeira and Azores, has been the starting point of the development of the Habitats Directive.

On December 28, 2001, the European Commission approved the declaration of the 174 Places of Community Importance (SCI) that had been proposed by the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, through the Spanish state. This decision was published in the DOCE L5 / 16 of January 9, 2002, which includes an annex listing the 208 Sites of Community Importance of the Macaronesian region, of which 34 correspond to the Azores and Madeira archipelagos and the remaining 174 to the Canary Islands. Subsequently, in the first half of 2006, the Canary Islands Government proposed the designation of three new SCIs (BOC n° 85, of May 4, 2006). On January 25, 2008, the European Commission approved the first update of SCIs from the Macaronesian region, which includes the proposed new locations and adjusts the surfaces of those that were already approved (DOCE L31 of February 5, 2008).

Prior to the designation of SCI, 28 Special Protection Areas for Birds (SPA) had been declared in the Autonomous Community. At the end of 2006, by agreement of the Government of the Canary Islands, the proposal of 15 new areas for designation as a SPA was approved, also expanding the areas of 12 of the previously designated (BOC n°226, of November 21, 2006).

At the end of 2009, Decree 174/2009 was passed declaring the Special Conservation Areas (ZEC) (BOC n° 7 of January 13, 2010). As stated in this text, it should be noted that the terrestrial ZECs coincide in 89% with the Protected Natural Areas provided in the Consolidated Text of the Laws of Planning of the Territory of the Canary Islands and of Natural Spaces of the Canary Islands, approved by Legislative Decree 1/2000, so they already have the protection measures included in the planning instruments of the aforementioned Natural Spaces, in addition to those established in the species recovery or conservation plans. For those Sites of Community Importance that do not coincide geographically with Protected Natural Areas of the Canary Network, this Decree provides for them to provide specific conservation provisions that complement their current protection measures before the end of 2010.

The Natura 2000 network spaces in the Canary Islands have management plans that contribute to the conservation of their natural habitats and their species habitats.

Table 3: List of habitats included in Directive 92/43/CEE

Habitats of community interest present in the canary islands		Habitat surface in the canary islands	
Code	Denomination	(ha)	%
1100	Sandbars permanently covered by seawater, shallow	476	0,064
1150	Coastal lagoons	0,2	0,000
1210	Annual vegetation on accumulated marine debris	24,6	0,004
1250	Cliffs with endemic vegetation of the macaronesian coasts	266,3	0,036
1420	Mediterranean and thermo-elastic halophilic scrubs	78	0,010
2110	Embryonic mobile dunes	4.123,20	0,554
2130	Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation	646,1	0,087
3150	Natural eutrophic lakes with magnopotamion or hydrochariton vegetation	0,1	0,000
4050	Endemic macaronesian heaths	14.501,50	1,947
4090	Endemic oro-Mediterranean heaths with gorse	16.323,70	2,192
5330	Thermomediterranean scrub and pre-steps	16.336,80	2,194
5335	Thermomediterranean broom	2.310,80	0,310
6420	Mediterranean wet grasslands of tall grasses of molinion-holoschoenion	35,80	0,005
7220	Petrifying springs with tufa formation	58,50	0,008
8220	Siliceous rocky slopes with chamosphtytic vegetation	143,10	0,019
8310	Caves not exploited by tourism	0,10	0,000
8320	Lava fields and natural excavations	5.192,10	0,680
8330	Submerged or semi-submerged sea caves	0,00	0,000
9200	Galleries and thickets of thermomediterranean rivers	226,90	0,030
9320	Olea and Ceratonia forests	461,50	0,062
9363	Canary laurel	7.052,60	0,947
9370	Phoenix palm trees	661,20	0,089
9550	Canarian endemic pine forests	44.868,10	6,025
9565	Juniperus sp. endemic forests	1.294,30	0,174
	Totals	115.081,50	15,545

2.2.5 Protected species

Law 42/2007, of December 13, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity creates, in article 53, the List of Wild Species under Special Protection Regime, which includes species, subspecies and populations deserving of particular attention and protection, depending on its scientific, ecological, cultural value, for its uniqueness, rarity or degree of threat, as well as those that appear as protected in international Directives and conventions ratified by Spain.

The inclusion of species in the List entails specific additional prohibitions to the general

protection regime, mainly aimed at their collection or capture of the wild, as well as transport and commercialization, both of the individuals and their remains or parts.

Within the List of Wild Species under Special Protection Regime, the Spanish Catalog of Endangered Species is established, which will include, when there is technical or scientific information to advise it, taxa or populations of threatened biodiversity. The Catalog integrates species into the categories:

- Endangered: taxa or populations whose survival is unlikely if the causal factors of their current situation continue to act.
- Vulnerable: taxa or populations that are at risk of becoming endangered in the immediate future if the adverse factors acting on them are not corrected.

Royal Decree 139/2011, of February 4, develops the List of Wild Species under Special Protection Regime and the Spanish Catalog of Endangered Species, specifying the species, subspecies or populations that comprise them, the inclusion procedure category change or species exclusion, the creation of a scientific advisory committee as well as the management of the information it contains.

The Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, under the protection of the exclusive powers in the field of nature conservation and natural resources regulation, has been provided with its own rules on the subject, such as Decree 151/2001, BOC No. 97 of August 1, by which the Catalog of Endangered Species of the Canary Islands is created, and the Order of July 13, 2005, BOC No. 143 of July 22, which determines the criteria that will govern the evaluation of the species of the threatened wildlife.

The Law of the Canary Islands Protected Species Catalog includes, in its article 3, the categories of the species, subspecies or populations of threatened biodiversity, or of interest for the Canarian or special protection ecosystems: 1) Endangered species (a. Species “ Endangered ”(Annex I); b. “ Vulnerable ”species (Annex II) 2) Species of “ interest to the Canarian ecosystems ”(Annex III). 3) “Special protection” species (Annex IV).

Annexes V and VI of this law include the categories "sensitive to the alteration of their habitat" or "special interest", and in annex VII those species, present in the Canary Islands, that have some type of protection for Community legislation or by international agreements, which are not included in Law 4/2010, BOC No. 112 of June 9, of the Canary Islands Catalog of Protected Species.

Tursiops truncatus (bottlenose dolphin) and *Caretta caretta* (loggerhead turtle) are the only two species protected by the Habitats Directive that have been able to have an impact when it comes to protecting the Canary Islands. With the criterion of the protection of one or both species, the ZECs declared by the presence of these priority species are: Marine Strip Santiago - Valle Gran Rey in La Gomera and Marine Area of La Isleta in Gran Canaria. Other areas, protected at the same time by their presence of habitat 1110 and one or both species are: Sebadales of the South of Tenerife, Marine Strip of Teno-Rasca, Mar de Las Calmas, Marine Strip of Fuencaliente, Bay of Gando,

Seadales de Playa del Inglés, Marine Strip from Mogán, Bahía del Confital, Cueva de Lobos, Jandía leeward beaches, Seadales de Corralejo and Seadales de La Graciosa.

Protected Seabird

In the particular case of seabirds, the seven species of the order Procellariiformes that breed in the Canary Islands are threatened (due to loss of habitat, predation of introduced mammals, artificial lights, etc.), so, except for the shearwater pichoneta, all are included in Annex I of the Birds Directive.

In the Canary Islands, 10 Important Areas for the Conservation of Seabirds (IBA) have been identified, most of which are marine extensions of breeding colonies (6 species, 10 IBA). Some areas of concentration in the sea have also been identified (1 species, 3 IBA), but most of the breeding birds in the

Archipelago they feed in waters of the continental shelf of the NW of Africa, or in strictly oceanic waters, in a very dispersed way.

The IBA ES389 (western coast of El Hierro) is a marine extension to the important colonies of petrel de Bulwer and Cinderella shearwater of the western sector of El Hierro, while in the surroundings of the Roques de Salmor the ES387 is located, also as an extension marine to them, and in which there are important colonies of petrel de Bulwer, small pardela, European cloth and cloth of Madeira. In the waters and cliffs of the north of La Palma, the IBA ES381 is located, a marine extension defined for the colonies of petrel de Bulwer, cinderella and small shearwater.

The coastal waters of La Gomera and the inter-island between it and the northwest of Tenerife (western coast of the Teno massif and cliffs of Los Gigantes) define the IBA ES381, which constitutes an important marine area with a marked summer presence of cinderella shear and, in lesser extent, from Bulwer's petrel; This IBA also concentrates a high percentage of the Canarian breeding population of these species together, in passing birds that frequent these waters to feed or rest. Tenerife hosts 3 marine IBAs, the ES364 (Cliffs of Santo Domingo and Roque de Garachico), the ES361 (Roque de La Playa) and the ES356 (Roques de Anaga). All of them are identified as marine extension to breeding colonies of petrel de Bulwer, and colonies of small shed and cloth of Madeira in ES364 and ES356.

In Gran Canaria, and more specifically from the Punta de la Aldea to the Port of Mogán, the ES395 is located, which constitutes a marine extension to important colonies of Cinderella and Petrel de Bulwer. ES401, includes the waters of the Bocaina Strait, as the channel between Lanzarote and Fuerteventura is known locally, and includes the surroundings of the islet of Lobos. This area acts as a funnel for the world's largest breeding population of Cinderella shearwater (that of the Wild Islands), on its feeding trips to the northwest African continental shelf. Also, on the coasts and islets adjacent to this IBA, there are several breeding colonies, of regional importance, of this species of shearwater, as well as small shearwater, common cloth and cloth of Madeira. Finally, the marine IBA of the islets of Lanzarote (ES327), constituted by La Graciosa, Montaña Clara and

Alegranza and the marine area around them, is one of the best nesting places for seabirds in the Macaronesian region. It combines important feeding areas as well as marine extensions of nesting colonies. In this area, 6 of the 7 species of Canarian Procellariiformes nest: Bulwer Petrel, Cinderella Pardela, Small Pardela, Pechialbo cloth, European cloth and Madeira cloth.

Protected Bats

All bats are regarded as species of special interest in the National Catalogue of Endangered Species (MMA, 2006), created according to paragraph 30.1 of Law 4/89 (“Conservation of habitats and wild flora and fauna”) and the Royal Decree 439/90 of 30th March 1990.

All species in the catalogue are subject to protection in the whole Spanish territory: killing, disturbing or capturing bats is forbidden, as it is the possession, traffic or trade of live or dead specimens or their body parts (Paz and Benzal, 1991). According to the law, bat species listed in the group of special interest species require particular attention due to their scientific, cultural or ecological role, and management plans are needed to preserve their populations.

The Autonomous Communities are responsible for the development of these plans: some of the protection measures established by section III of Law 4/89 can be applied to all, or some, of the habitats used by the target species (Paz and Benzal, 1991). The Federal organization of Spain is such that regional institutions promulgate environmental regulations. For instance, Asturias and Catalonia have developed their own regulations on bat protection.

Because of their legal status, *M. myotis* and *M. blythii* roosts, reproduction, wintering or rest sites are strictly protected, and all unauthorised actions (capture, killing, disturbance, etc.) are forbidden.

For migratory species, all sites used for reproduction, hibernation or rest are protected by this law, which defines Nature Reserves for Wildlife, to protect species at risk, and Wildlife Reserves, to protect wildlife in general.

Regulations promulgated by the Autonomous Communities may be even stricter than national ones and include harder penalties.

As far as international laws are concerned, Spain has approved and ratified the Bonn and Bern Conventions, which explicitly refer to all bat species occurring in the country, but do not include endemics of the Canary Islands and Macaronesia.

The Habitats Directive has been ratified through the Royal Decree 1997/1995 of 7th December, providing the basis for the development of the Natura 2000 network in the country. Spain has not yet joined the Bat Agreement.

2.2.6 Renewable energies

At European level, the renewable energy objectives were defined in Directive 2009/28 / CE10 concerning the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.

This Directive aims to establish a common framework for the production and promotion of energy from renewable sources. It sets, for each Member State, an objective relating to the share of energy obtained from renewable sources in gross final energy consumption by 2020.

For Spain, two mandatory objectives are assigned. On the one hand, it required to increase the use of renewable energy sources up to 20% by 2020 compared to 2005, when the share of renewables was 8.7%, which means doubling the current production capacity. The figure includes the production of biofuels, so that by 2020 10% of the fuel consumption needs in the transport sector can be met. On the other hand, Spain must reduce its level of greenhouse gas emissions by 10% in sectors such as transport or housing.

In November 2011, the Spanish central government approved the Renewable Energy Plan (PER) 2011-2020, which includes energy scenarios and establishes objectives in accordance with Directive 2009/28 / EC. The overall objective of the PER 2011-2020 is to achieve a renewable energy share of 20.8% in 2020. Additionally, it also contemplates that 38.1% of electricity consumption and 11.3% of consumption in Transport is renewable, emphasizing that 35,000 MW are on-shore wind, 750 MW offshore, and 12,050 MW solar.

During the last twenty years there has been a very important development of electric energy production technologies in Spain from renewable energy sources, cogeneration and waste, which were part of the previously called “special regime”. This growth has been possible, in part, thanks to the existence of successive regulatory support frameworks that established economic incentives for electricity production with these technologies.

However, these favorable support frameworks led to the rapid overcoming of the forecasts that had presided over its approval, which forced the Spanish legislator to undertake successive corrections of the regulatory framework to guarantee the financial sustainability of the system.

In this context and given the need to guarantee and maintain over time the economic and financial sustainability of the electricity system, the so-called “Energy Reform” began in 2013, which has led to a significant change in the remuneration regime for renewable energy in Spain.

Canarian Energy policy

The guidelines of the Canarian energy policy have been reflected since the late 80s in the various energy planning documents that have been prepared to date.

The last energy planning document -PECAN 2006-, approved by the Parliament of the Canary Islands in March 2007, defined the Canarian energy policy until 2015 through the establishment of four basic principles:

- Guarantee the supply of energy to all consumers in optimal conditions in as for regularity, quality and price.
- Maximize the rational use of energy.
- Promote the maximum possible use of renewable energy sources, especially wind and solar, as a means to reduce external vulnerability and improve protection and the environment.

- Integrate the environmental dimension in all energy decisions.

Similarly, it set a set of objectives, most of them aimed at promoting electricity generation through clean technologies and favoring the diversification of conventional energy sources through the incorporation of natural gas, in order to displace excessive employment and dependence of petroleum products, with the consequent positive effect on the environment. It also contemplated a very ambitious objective of reducing energy intensity by 25% in 2015, compared to the value of 2004.

Basic principles for 2025 ENERGY STRATEGY

In order to move forward in the transition towards a sustainable energy model, which contributes to the change towards a low carbon economy in a manner compatible with the preservation of the environment, the energy model proposed by the *Energy Strategy for Canarian 2015-2025 (EECan25)* is based on the following basic principles:

- Guarantee the security of the energy supply for the different sectors of activity and for citizens in general, through the diversification of energy sources.
- Achieve maximum penetration of renewable energies, in a manner compatible with the preservation of the natural environment, especially wind and solar in its different modalities, but also encouraging the implementation of other alternative energies: biomass, low temperature geothermal or through the energy use of waste.
- Contribute to alleviate the vulnerabilities of the Canary electricity sector, which suffers the consequences inherent in the condition of the Canary Islands as an outermost region (remoteness, isolation of the European continent and fragmentation of its territory), reinforcing its island electrical systems, by incorporating electrical interconnections between islands, improving its transport and distribution networks and providing it with energy storage infrastructures, which allow increasing the penetration of indigenous energies, thus contributing to improve the guarantee of supply.
- Promote sustainable mobility through the promotion of vehicles that use alternative fuels instead of petroleum products (biofuels, propane gas, compressed natural gas, etc.), and with special support for the development of the electric vehicle.
- Strengthen the strategies for managing electricity demand, fundamentally associated with sustainable mobility and desalination of water, which allow greater penetration of renewable energies and, in addition, contribute to the development of energy distributed generation.
- Introduce natural gas as transition energy between the current energy model, based on fossil fuels and the new model based on renewable energy.
- Use the energy sector as an engine for sustainable tourism development in the Canary Islands strategic and primary sector of regional economic growth.
- Contribute to the improvement of the competitiveness of companies and industries in the Canary Islands, especially SMEs, through the application of energy saving and efficiency measures and the promotion of renewable energies in the buildings of the service sector and the industrialists, as well as in the productive processes of the industries.

- Promote a strategy of saving and energy efficiency in building and residential housing and especially in social housing, which contribute to reducing energy poverty.

Strategic objectives of the Canary Energy Strategy 2025.

The strategic objectives of the EECan25 for the 2015-2025 period are specified in the following:

- Take advantage of the opportunities of the Canary Islands as a natural laboratory for research, development and testing of green technologies and intelligent distribution networks.
- Achieve, through measures to promote energy saving and efficiency, of energy diversification through the maximization of renewable energies and the entry of natural gas, a considerable reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, thus contributing to the mitigation of climate change.
- Increase the participation of renewable energies in final energy consumption from 2% in 2015 to 15% in 2025.
- Increase the share of renewable energy for electricity generation from 8% in 2015 to 45% in 2025.
- Reduce tons of CO2 equivalent by 21% in 2025 compared to 2014.

Specific objectives are:

- Increase the participation of terrestrial wind energy in the power generation park, so that in 2025 there is an installed capacity of 1,025 MW, compared to 164 MW installed in 2015.
- Set the goal of reaching 310 MW of offshore wind power in the power generation park in 2025.
- National objective: The final energy saving objective for Spain, reaches 15,979 ktoe for the whole period between January 1, 2014 and December 31, 2020.
- European objective: Increase in energy efficiency by 20%, which implies a reduction in primary energy consumption of 368 million tons of oil equivalent.

The Canary Energy Strategy 2025 also proposes seven flagship initiatives to catalyze progress on each priority issue, which must be materialized both in the EU and by the Member States. One of these initiatives, related to sustainable growth, is "A Europe that effectively uses resources", to help unleash economic growth and overexploitation of resources, support the shift towards a low carbon economy, increase use from renewable energy sources, modernize the transport sector and promote energy efficiency.

Initiative E1_1.2: Promote the development of marine renewable energy, especially offshore wind.

Taking into account the evolution of recent years, offshore wind power must become an essential element for the development of the renewable sector in the islands. So far, the main obstacle to the implementation of offshore wind farms in the Canary Islands lay in the depth of its waters. However, the new foundation techniques and the possibility of using floating platforms, together with the evolution of wind turbines with greater installed power per unit area, translates into a reduction in investment costs for this type of projects, in such a way that technical solutions are

already being promoted that are intended to be installed in the short term in areas close to the island of Gran Canaria.

For the establishment of offshore wind power objectives in the islands, its implementation has been taken into account on the coasts of those islands where the incorporation of energy storage systems or interconnections between islands is also planned, infrastructure that will allow greater integration of the generation of renewable origin not manageable.

Within this initiative, in addition to those already mentioned for the promotion of renewable energy facilities in general, the following concrete actions may be contemplated:

- Enable tools for: identification of coastal areas with greater resources, selection of possible offshore sites, etc.
- Simplify and / or coordinate the administrative procedures related to the interconnection of offshore wind farms with Canarian electrical systems that take into account the particularities associated with this type of facilities, and especially with the procedures of the State's competence regarding authorization of production facilities located in the territorial sea and coasts.

2.2.7 Aquaculture

The Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment (MAGRAMA) has recently developed the Multiannual Strategic Plan for Spanish Aquaculture (PEPAE). After several consultations with the Autonomous Communities and contributions of specific information by them, MAGRAMA has approved the PEPAE. The Deputy Ministry of Fisheries and Water of the Government of the Canary Islands, has made many contributions to the different drafts of the PEPAE, also providing information, diagnosis and proposal of specific actions for the Canary Islands.

However, the Vice Ministry has requested the preparation of a Strategic Plan for Aquaculture of the Canary Islands (PEACAN) agreed with the sector, based on the diagnosis of own needs and the consequent proposal and prioritization of specific measures that will serve as a framework for the development of aquaculture in the Canary Islands during the period 2014-2020. The Canary Islands Strategic Aquaculture Plan (PEACAN) is a planning document for the development of aquaculture for the period 2014-2020, in line with the European guidelines, the principles of the CFP, the FEMP and, of course, the Multiannual Strategic Plan for Spanish Aquaculture.

The PEACAN contributes to the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, consistent with the Common Strategic Framework (CSF). It also includes measures that guarantee the effective, efficient and coordinated execution of FEMP funds, as well as actions aimed at reducing the administrative burden. For this purpose, specific objectives are defined with the corresponding measures and a budgetary approximation, at the expense of the distribution of the financial credits of the FEMP assistance for the Canary Islands. Each measure is accompanied by indicators to assess how the execution of the Plan progresses in achieving the objectives, as the basis for monitoring. The Canary Islands Strategic Plan for Aquaculture - 2014-2020, is based on the priorities and objectives defined in the Europe 2020 Strategy, the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), the PMI, the FEMP and the Strategic Guidelines for Development Sustainable Aquaculture

of the European Union. Likewise, the PEACAN establishes the necessary synergies with other European, national and regional public actions, guaranteeing coherence with other instruments and regulations of sector, territorial, environmental and financial application, especially:

- Multiannual Strategic Plan for Spanish Aquaculture
- FEMP Operational Program
- Natura 2000 Network and Marine Strategy
- Regional Plan for the Management of Aquaculture of the Canary Islands.

The achievement of the objectives of the FEMP is linked the EU Guidelines for the Sustainable Development of Aquaculture, which PEACAN assumes. In this way, PEACAN assumes as its own the priorities of the EMFF directly related to aquaculture:

Priority 2) Promote sustainable aquaculture from an environmental point of view, efficient in the use of resources, innovative, competitive and knowledge-based:

- a) Support for the consolidation of technological development, innovation and knowledge transfer;
- b) Promotion of competitiveness and viability of aquaculture companies, including improved safety and working conditions, in particular SMEs;
- c) The protection and recovery of aquatic biodiversity and the enhancement of ecosystems related to aquaculture and promotion of aquaculture efficient in the use of resources;
- d) The promotion of aquaculture with a high level of environmental protection, and the promotion of animal health and welfare, and public health and protection;
- e) The development of vocational training, new professional competencies and continuing education.

Regulations and competences

Law 17/2003, of April 10, on Fishing in the Canary Islands, includes in its article 20.2.a) that corresponds to the island councils: “Grant the concessions and administrative authorizations for the exercise of the aquaculture activity”. However, the Second Additional Provision of Decree 182/2004, of December 21, which approves the Regulation of the Canary Islands Fisheries Law, establishes that: “All references made to the Island Councils in Law 17 / 2003, of the Canary Islands Fisheries and in the Regulation that is approved with this Decree in the field of aquaculture, in relation to the matters that will be transferred, will be understood as made to the Ministry of the Canary Islands Government competent in matters of fishing, until moment in which the transfer of powers to the Cabildos in this matter becomes effective, in accordance with the procedure established in the Third Transitory Provision of Law 14/1990, of July 26, on the Legal Regime of the Canary Islands Public Administrations ”.

According to the above, the competences in marine aquaculture correspond to the Deputy Ministry of Fisheries and Waters, Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Waters of the

Government of the Canary Islands, Fisheries Structures Service. Similarly, Law 23/1984, of June 25, on Marine Crops should be taken into account.

Granting Procedure

The procedure for granting marine aquaculture licenses in the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands starts by submitting the request by the promoter, until the final granting of the same by the Fisheries Structures Service of the Vice Ministry of Fisheries and Water. The procedures take about 50 months and are granted for terms of 10 years, up to a maximum of 30 years. It should be taken into account that this 30-year term may be increased to 75 years if the provisions of the recent modification of the Coastal Law apply.

What described above represents the terms for aquaculture licenses in the open sea, because in the case of authorizations for marine aquaculture on land the term is considerably reduced, being in about 6 months, as long as it does not affect the Terrestrial Maritime Public Domain, and granted for an indefinite term.

The number of Public Administrations involved in the procedure for granting aquaculture concessions is between 10 and 13, including substantive and environmental bodies, Administration with powers in the Public Domain (Coasts or Port Authority), as well as other Public Administrations consulted in the period of allegations.

Figure 8: The procedure for granting aquaculture sites

Site planning and selection

The Vice Ministry of Fisheries and Water has been developing since 1999 a series of aquaculture planning initiatives at the regional level. Prior to the entry into force of Law 17/2003, of April 10, on Fisheries of the Canary Islands, which establishes the obligatory nature of the formulation of the Regional Plan for the Management of Aquaculture of the Canary Islands (PROAC), it is recognized, on the part of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries of the Canary Islands Government, the need to formulate an activity planning instrument. To this end, a compilation of all the existing information of the coastal areas of the Canary Islands (data and bibliography) was carried out, developing a computerized and digitalized database with which the so-called “Basic Document of Coastal Planning for Aquaculture in the Canary Islands was prepared with the collaboration of the Canary Islands Institute of Marine Sciences and the University of La Laguna.

In the aforementioned document a delimitation of the areas not suitable for the location of aquaculture facilities was made, based on a detailed study by sectors of the Canary Islands coast. The Vice Ministry of Fisheries and Water of the Canary Islands Government has been promoting since 2001 a series of studies of coastal sections for the selection of areas suitable for aquaculture. These studies carry out a characterization of the coastal stretches studied from a technical, environmental and socioeconomic point of view, subsequently delimiting areas suitable for aquaculture through the application of a series of criteria. These studies finally estimate the carrying capacity (production) that can be achieved in the proposed suitable areas, without causing significant environmental impacts on the marine environment. Although not all the coastal sections studied have estimated the carrying capacity, in general they have been very useful for the development of aquaculture in the Canary Islands.

Finally, the Vice Ministry of Fisheries and Water of the Government of the Canary Islands has prepared the Regional Plan for the Management of Aquaculture of the Canary Islands (PROAC). It is a planning instrument with a high regulatory content, so that the legislative development necessary for the effective management of aquaculture in the Canary Islands is concentrated in a single document.

The general objective of PROAC is the management of aquaculture, based on the provisions of Law 17/2003, on Fisheries in the Canary Islands, through the development of an instrument for the management of aquaculture for the Canary Islands, making its exercise compatible with the protection of marine natural resources, its ecosystems and other uses present on the coast, promoting an integrated management of uses and activities with an impact on the marine environment.

In accordance with the purpose of PROAC, the following specific objectives have been established:

- 1) Ensure the conservation and protection of natural resources, as well as compatibility with fishing and shellfish, tourism and water sports.

- 2) Achieve a balance between social and economic development and environmental protection, promoting a rational and efficient use of the marine environment and the territory, and the conservation of biodiversity.
- 3) Promote a sustainable growth of the activity, avoiding the conflict of uses in the marine and terrestrial environment.
- 4) Contribute to the maintenance of natural and cultural heritage.
- 5) Compatibility of coastal uses with the activity.
- 6) Maritime-terrestrial public domain division by zones, classifying them as prohibited, suitable and of interest for aquaculture.
- 7) Location of existing aquaculture farms.
- 8) Determination of prohibited species and those of interest to aquaculture, in a manner general or for certain areas.
- 9) Establishment of the types of aquaculture, their technical characteristics and the farm conditions, being able to establish specifications for specific areas or species.

The most important point of the PROAC is the zoning of the public maritime land domain in areas with or without aptitude for the development of aquaculture, so that by applying certain technical and environmental criteria a classification of the coastline is obtained in prohibited areas, areas suitable and areas of interest for aquaculture. All these exercises of planning and selection of sites have led to the development of aquaculture in the Canary Islands, and has been carried out in a coherent and orderly manner, not having seen serious environmental impacts on the environment marine and its ecosystems in marine aquaculture projects developed in the Canary Islands.

2.2.8 Fishery

In 1964 the European Fisheries Agreement, ratified by Spain, recognized the possibility of extending maritime jurisdiction in fisheries to a maximum of 12 nautical miles. Thus, Law 20/1967 and Royal Decree 2510/1977 address this extension based on the definition of normal baselines (low tide) or of, if any, straight baselines (depending on the coastal layout). In addition, they defined inland waters as those that remain between these straight baselines and the coast. On the other hand, Law 15/1978 defined for Spain the Exclusive Economic Zone that covers up to 200 nautical miles, measured from those baselines, also considering the Exclusive Economic Zones of neighboring countries.

In 1982, the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (which Spain ratified in 1997) was approved and after that a series of areas were defined: Inland Waters, Territorial Sea, Contiguous Zone, Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and High Seas, which provide complexity in the legal order due to the plurality of the Law of the Sea in relation to sovereignty, uses, rights and obligations. Finally, following the Spanish Constitution (1978), the Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands (1982) and Royal Decree 1938/1985, the competencies on fishery has been divided between the Inland Waters of the Autonomous Communities and the Territorial Sea and EEZ, under competence of the Central State.

The Statute of Autonomy of the Canary Islands (Constitutional law 10/1982 4/1996) states that the autonomous region of the Canaries owns sovereign rights in inland waters for fishing, shellfish and aquaculture. The statute also assigns the legislative handling and the execution of issues related to the fishing sector to the Autonomous region of the Canary Islands. In 1986 the state published the Royal Decree 2200/1986 of regulation of tools and forms of fishing in the waters of the Canary Islands. The Royal Decree 2200/1986 applies to the Spanish territorial waters around the Canary Islands as well as to the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).

The Fisheries Law of the Canary Islands, Law 17/2003 of April 10, dedicates its chapter III to the “Measurements of protection and regeneration of the fishery resources”, establishing a set of areas protected from fishing. The law declared three different protection schemes for marine reserves for fishing interests, marine restoration zones, and marine repopulation zones.

The minimum catch sizes of fish in waters around the Canary Islands are regulated in the Decree n ° 155 of 1986. This decree aims to avoid capture of too young and immature individuals and to protect breeding and nursery ground for a sustainable stock management. Sports fishing licenses are regulated by Decree n ° 121/1998.

With regard to the Canary Islands, the actors of the Fishery sector, are could the following:

- Administrations: 2 with competences in marine fishing and in the management of the sector: General Secretariat of Fisheries (Government of Spain) and the General Directorate of Fisheries (Government of the Canary Islands).
- Professional Fishermen: Federation of Regional Fishermen's Cofradías, Provincial Fishermen's Cofradías Federations (Las Palmas and Tenerife) that include 25 Brotherhoods, 2 Cooperatives, 1 Company and 3 Producer Organizations.
- Recreational Fishermen: 3 Recreational Fishing Associations (ACAPER, ASENPER and ACPESUR) that belong to the fishing with rod or line, both from land and from boat and to underwater fishing, and the Federation of Underwater Activities. In any case, recreational fishing has a low level of organization and associationism, for example, for the island of Tenerife it was estimated at around 5% (Pascual et al., 2012).
- (iv) Research: 3 entities, Spanish Institute of Oceanography, 2 Universities (ULPGC and ULL) and their respective Departments.
- (v) Non-profit associations; 2 are the NGOs most related to fisheries issues in the Canary Islands (WWF and Ben Magec). 7 Coastal Action Groups formed to lead and energize European actions or projects related to the fishing sector and its environment, formed by public and private agents, with the fishing sector having 50% representation in the governing bodies.

Regarding the mechanisms for resolving formal conflicts, the “Fisheries Advisory Council” stands out (Decree 182/2004, Decree 40/2012 and its modifications) which “is a representative collegiate body of all the agents of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands affected by the fishing policy”, made up of 8 representatives of the agency responsible for fisheries, 8 representatives of the organizations or associations of shipowners and fishers linked to the production, processing and marketing of fishery products, and aquaculture, 3 representatives of the

entities and associations related to the study, research, protection and defense of fishery and aquaculture resources, 2 representatives of fishermen's associations, 2 representatives of the most representative trade union organizations in the sector and 2 professionals of recognized prestige in the sector. In addition, "it corresponds to the Fisheries Advisory Council the functions of consultation, study and advice to the Ministry in matters within its competence". It must meet once every 6 months on an ordinary basis and, exceptionally, as many times as it is convened by its President.

2.3 LANDSCAPE LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The Coastal Law is the norm that defines and regulates the maritime-terrestrial public domain. The basic regulation of application is the Law of Coasts of 22/1988, the Law 2/2013, of protection and sustainable use of the coast and of modification of Law 22/1988 and Royal Decree 876/2014 which approves the General Coastal Regulation.

Since the date of entry into force of Law 22/1988, numerous modifications have been introduced in order to provide greater protection of the Spanish coast and greater legal certainty of the subjects affected by the limitations imposed by this regulation.

Law 2/2013 on the protection and sustainable use of the coast and modification of Law 22/1988, recently amended the aforementioned Law on Coasts, establishing a new legislative framework, which aims to increase in legal certainty for actions that affect the coast and the promotion of effective protection thereof that is compatible with the promotion of economic activity and job creation. This without forgetting the regulation of administrative procedures related to the determination of the maritime land public domain and its use regime, as well as those related to the limitations of ownership of land adjacent to the sea shore to ensure integrity and use public of the public terrestrial and maritime domain and the development of the transitional regime.

The land affected by the Coastal Law has a different nature and three stripes can be distinguished in it:

1. **The maritime-land public domain:**

It is a public domain land composed of goods that by constitutional definition enjoy an inalienable, imprescriptible and unattachable character.

Article 132.2 of the Spanish Constitution sets forth state-owned assets such as those established by law and, in any case, the maritime-terrestrial zone, beaches, territorial sea, and natural resources of the economic zone and the Continental platform. The Coastal Law extends the constitutional definition by classifying them in accordance with the provisions of articles 3 and 4.

2. **The protection easement:**

The Coastal Law establishes an administrative easement, for the defense and integrity of the maritime-terrestrial public domain called protection easement that falls, in general, on an area of 100 meters measured inland from the inner boundary of the sea shore. In this area there is private property but the facilities and works allowed are limited. The protection zone has a width of 100 m from the inner boundary of the sea shore, except in those coastal sections that, upon the entry into force of the Coastal Law (July 28, 1988), were already classified as urban or had a partial plan

already approved before January 1, 1988, in which the width is 20 m. The setting of the width of the easement is determined in the resolution of the demarcation.

The extension of this area may be extended by the State Administration, in agreement with the Autonomous Community and the corresponding City Council, up to a maximum of another 100 m. when necessary to ensure the effectiveness of the easement, taking into account the peculiarities of the stretch of coast in question.

3. **The area of influence**, whose width is 500 meters from the shore of the sea.

The buildings proposed by the urban planning instrument prevent the formation of architectural screens or accumulation of volumes, of such so that the density of building to be developed is consistent with that of the rest of the municipality.

Law 4/2017, of July 13, on the Soil and Protected Natural Areas of the Canary Islands, was promulgated in order to simplify, rationalize and update the applicable rules for the protection, management and use of territory of the Canary archipelago.

The system until then in force, based on DLeg 1/2000, of May 8, which had approved the Consolidated Text of the Laws of Ordination of the Territory of the Canary Islands and Natural Spaces of Canary Islands, is an ordination that, over the course of time and the development that over the course of those more than fifteen years had been carried out, had become excessively complicated to the point that it had been revealed, in certain measure as “a limitation that goes far beyond what is necessary to achieve the ends that justify them; that, sometimes, they become obstacles, not always explainable; that hinder, or even prevent, a rational and sustainable development of the territory”.

Principles of the Law and legal regime of the land

Law 4/2017 is based on the constitutional principle of sustainable development as a guiding criterion of the understanding of the rules that it establishes, of the regulatory norms that develop it and, above all, as a principle that should guide the work of management and intervention on the island floor. For this, the Law classifies the land as rustic, urbanizable and urban.

In spite of the intention of normative fullness pursued by Law 4/2017, it has been evident that the Law “does not exhaust the organization of this matter”, in aspects such as institutional and citizen participation, inter-administrative cooperation, the documentary content of the plans or the way of compliance with certain procedures (especially those related to the environmental assessment procedure); and, similarly, by the express call of the legislator, the environmental evaluation of the management instruments needs to be complemented in the aspects related to the criteria and the methodology of the evaluation, in order to avoid the diversity of interpretations in their application.

In this way, the Planning Regulation fulfills the function of collaboration, which is its own, developing:

The principles and classes of management, citizen participation and the right to information, the regulation of cooperation and inter-administrative collaboration, and the determination of common procedures for the development of management instruments subject to ordinary strategic environmental assessment Title I, arts. 1 to 27).

The norms and the particular rules of the instruments of management of the natural resources and of the territory (Title II, articles 28 to 35).

The plans and norms of protected natural areas and natural network 2000 (Title III, arts. 36 to 39). The territorial planning instruments, both of the territorial planning plans and of the projects of insular or autonomous interest (Title IV, arts. 40 to 53).

The urban planning instruments, regulating both the object and the procedure of the technical norms of urban planning, of the general planning plans, as well as of the rest of urban development instruments, such as detailed studies, protection catalogs and Municipal Urbanization, Municipal Building and Provisional Ordinances, both insular and municipal (Title V, arts. 54 to 93).

Ending the regulation of institutions common to all instruments, such as issues related to legitimation, communications, suspension of the processing of management and licensing instruments, effectiveness and validity, alteration of environmental management and evaluation instruments (Title VI, arts. 94 to 116).

An Annex that establishes the criteria and methodology to carry out the environmental assessment of the management instruments, Annex with which it is intended to comply with the provisions of art. 86.9 of Law 4/2017, which states that “the Government will regulate the regulations, criteria and methodology to be used by the environmental body in the exercise of its function, ensuring the unity and coherence of the environmental assessment, in accordance with public criteria and known in advance, the most objective and regulated that the state of scientific and technical knowledge and of the existing evaluation methods allow. ”

The environmental and territorial planning is formed by the following instruments:

- a) General and Sector Management Guidelines (DO).
- b) Island Management Plans (PIO).
- c) Natural Resources Management Plans (PORN).
- d) Plans and Norms of Protected Natural Areas and the Natura 2000 Network.
- e) Partial Territorial Plans (PTP).
- f) Special Territorial Plans (PTE).
- g) Strategic territorial actions.

The urban planning is articulated through the following instruments:

- A) Technical urban planning standards (NTPU).
- B) General Management Plans (PGO).
- C) Urban development instruments:
 - a) Partial Plans (PP)
 - b) Special Plans (PE)
- D) Urban planning instruments for the sector.
- E) Complementary instruments:
 - a) Detail Studies (ED)
 - b) Catalogs (CTGO)
 - c) Municipal building ordinances (OME)

- d) Municipal urbanization ordinances (OMU)
- e) Insular provisional ordinances (IPO)
- f) Municipal provisional ordinances (OPM)

The strategic and / or sectorial planning, in its territorial and urban dimension, will be developed through the following instruments:

- a) Projects of insular or autonomous interest (PII - PIA)
- b) Plans for modernization, improvement and increase of competitiveness (PMM)
- c) Action programs on the urban environment (PAMU)

Organization of management instruments that closes with the provision that “the relationship between all management instruments is governed by the principles of hierarchy, competence and specialization, in accordance with the provisions of articles 9 and 83 of the Law on Soil and Protected Natural Areas of the Canary Islands”.

Regarding the elements to consider on the management instruments and their processing procedure, it should be noted that:

- 1) The new Regulation synthesizes in fourteen precepts the common procedures for the development of management instruments submitted to ordinary strategic environmental assessment;
- 2) The new Planning Regulation with 23 precepts regulates common issues (such as legitimacy, communications, suspension of the processing of management and licensing instruments, effectiveness and validity, alteration of the instruments of environmental management and evaluation).
- 3) Development instruments are treated from a more general perspective, providing:
 - a) To establish the precise detailed planning for the execution of the planning, in whole or in part, of the consolidated urban land and of the rustic land of rural settlement.
 - b) Conserve and improve the natural environment and the natural and urban landscape.
 - c) Protect, conserve and rehabilitate the Canarian historical heritage.
 - d) Establish detailed management of urban areas undergoing urban renovation or renovation operations, without prejudice to actions on the urban environment.
 - e) Define the actions in the tourist centers or zones to be rehabilitated.
 - f) Order the general systems, when determined by the general plan.
 - g) Any other analog that is foreseen in other provisions.
- 4) The detailed studies are considered as complementary instruments.
- 5) The regulation of management guidelines is incorporated into the Planning Regulation, which until now was in two specific Regulations (Decree 127/2001, of June 5, which

regulates the Management Guidelines, establishing the formal guidelines for the preparation of the Natural Resources Management Plans. Management guidelines that, in accordance with the provisions of arts. 28 to 31 of the Planning Regulation:

- They constitute the instrument of strategic territorial planning of the Government of the Canary Islands, constituting the frame of reference for the remaining instruments of environmental, territorial and urban planning of the Autonomous Community.
- They may be general or sectoral

Regulations of law application are in progress of publication.

CHAPTER 3: ENVIRONMENTAL BASELINE

The island of Gran Canaria is a Volcanoe structure, of approximately circular shape, surrounded for the most part of its perimeter by very deep waters down to 3500 m.

Its southeast side faces an area within a suitable depth range of approximately 50 km². The zone is free from any protection regime and from any other constraints, and is included within the blocks where offshore wind farming is allowed, under Spanish Crown law 1028/2008. Two areas Natura 2000 areas are present at different distances. The whole area is notably free of any significant marine traffic. The shipping lane directed to Las Palmas runs offshore. There is a port serving the Arinaga industrial complex.

The area selected for a possible Blue Growth Farm Platform installation is located eastward of the port, over a seabottom with a slight slope, and a depth is in the range of 70-95 m.

The seabed is presumably rocky, given the island's geological nature. It is not described in detail in the EMODnet seabed cartography. The selected site is shown in the following map, with depth contours and the seabed features.

Table 4: Arinaga site characteristics

Site name: Arinaga	Position: λ 27,79986° ϕ -15,359552°
Port distance	3,5 nm
Land distance	3,5 nm
Depth	95 m
Seabottom	Rock
Protected areas distance	2,1 nm
Minimum temperature	18
Maximum temperature	23,5
Tide amplitude	3,2 m
Annual wave power	12,1 kW/m
Annual wind power	0,892 kW/m ²
Maximum Hs 2016-2018	4,5 m

The species selected for fish farming within the Blue Growth Platform facilities located within the Atlantic Ocean, the Canary Islands, is the seabream *Sparus aurata* (Linnaeus, 1758). This species is one of the most farmed within the Mediterranean and adjacent waters, with an annual gross production in the Mediterranean of 160.563 tonnes (FEAP, 2017) in 2016.

Seabream is farmed both in coastal and offshore waters from a weight of 5 to 10 g, to attain a final weight of 350-400 g, and a length of 35 cm at the end of a 16-18 month growth cycle.

Whilst seabream areal extends from the UK to the whole Mediterranean Sea, and down to Cape Verde (FAO, 2018; Fishbase.org, 2018), its temperature range lies between 13 and 26 °C, with suboptimal temperature from 10°C up to 28 °C tolerable for short periods.

3.1 PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT

The Canary archipelago constitutes an intraplate volcanic complex, located on the northwestern margin of the African plate. This archipelago extends over more than 500 km and consists of seven major islands: Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma and El Hierro.

The islands emerge from an ocean floor whose depth increases to the west, from about 3,000 m to the E of Lanzarote and Fuerteventura, to 4,000 m in the area of La Palma and El Hierro. The highest height in the archipelago corresponds to the Pico del Teide, of 3,718 m, located on the island of Tenerife.

On the other hand, the Canary Islands have special characteristics in terms of their genesis and underwater morphology. Each island has had a different and independent history, starting its activity at different times and with a particular duration and evolution for each of them, so a general model valid for the entire archipelago cannot be established.

From the geomorphological point of view, volcanic islands undergo vertical growth processes that are regularly affected by phenomena of landslides and avalanches of rocks and sediments that balance the gravitational stability of volcanic buildings. The morphology of the submerged area of the Canary archipelago is, therefore, the result of a rapid development of volcanic buildings and subsequent collapse of its flanks due to gravitational instability processes, favored in turn by seismic phenomena.

On the boundary between the coast and the continental shelf, marked by a strong slope break, lobed deposits corresponding to accumulations of solid masses stand out, reaching large dimensions as in the Great King Valley on the island from La Gomera or at the mouth of the Barranco de Las Angustias on the island of La Palma.

Regarding the continental shelf, two main sets can be distinguished. The first includes the islands of Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura, Lanzarote and La Gomera and presents a relatively large platform, while the second group, consisting of Tenerife, La Palma and El Hierro, the platform is practically non-existent, falling sharply to bottoms of more than 1,000 m (Maestro et al., 2005).

The slope is marked by pending marks and it can be observed frequent massive processes of landslides and avalanche phenomena (Acosta et al., 2005). The landslides have slopes that vary between 10° in header areas and 5° at depths of 3,000 m (Masson et al., 2002). Lobulated fans with large blocks are formed in the most remote areas.

Large masses of submerged landslides have been recognized, detached from recognizable scars generally on the flanks emerging from the islands.

Numerous canyons affect gravitational deposits, being able to exceed 60 km in length between the coast and the deep areas of the sedimentary basins.

Figure 9: Bathymetric map of Gran Canaria (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

3.1.1 Currents

Water bodies

In the environment of the Canary archipelago, several bodies of water can be differentiated according to their physical-chemical properties and their location in the water column. Based on

these two characteristics, the following bodies of water are distinguished: Surface Water, Central

North Atlantic Water, Intermediate Antarctic Water, Mediterranean Water, Deep North Atlantic Water and Bottom Antarctic Water.

Surface Water is characterized by high homogeneity of its properties due to the intense vertical mixing process due to the exchange of heat between the surface of the ocean and the atmosphere. Its thickness varies throughout the year from about 50 m at the end of summer, to about 170 m, at the end of winter.

The Central North Atlantic Water is water from the main Thermocline of the North Atlantic and extends between 100 m and 700 m. Its temperature varies between 10.5-18 °C, while its salinity ranges between 35.5-36.7 psu.

Depending on the area, the Middle Antarctic Water and the Mediterranean Water are located and below both is the Deep Water of the North Atlantic.

The Middle Antarctic Water is described in the three oceans of the southern hemisphere, and is characterized by having a main component to the north. It is between 700 m and 1,100 m deep and despite having little importance in terms of volume, it is important because of the amount of nutrients it contains. Its temperature ranges between 8-10 °C, and its salinity between 35.25-35.55 psu.

Mediterranean Water is characterized by high salinity due to the characteristics of the Mediterranean basin. It can be found in a way generalized throughout the Canary archipelago, but its presence increases to the northwest. The water of the Mediterranean Sea flows through the Strait of Gibraltar at a depth between 500 m and 1,100 m and gradually blends with the waters of the Atlantic, which explains why this ocean has an average salinity greater than the Indian or Pacific oceans. In its advance across the Atlantic from the Mediterranean, this body of water forms large lentil-shaped structures known as meddies, which can move away more than 2,000 km while retaining their properties and reach radii of up to 50 km.

The Canary archipelago is the limit of influence of the Mediterranean Water, which is located between 1,000 m and 1,400 m. Its temperature ranges between 7-9.5 °C and its salinity between 35.5-35.75 psu.

The Deep Water of the North Atlantic is, in the Canary archipelago, between 1,400 m deep to the seabed. Its temperature is between 2 °C and 7 °C and its salinity ranges between 34.8 and 35.5 psu. It has very homogeneous and stable properties, being the most important volume in the area. It is considered an essential element in the maintenance of the planetary ocean circulation, because its extension covers from its place of formation in the North Atlantic to all the great world oceans since it is involved in the thermohaline transport process that sustains the balances of the world oceans and their circulation.

General Circulation Dynamic

The large anticyclonic system of currents in the North Atlantic moves warm water to the European continent, but when it turns partially towards the South, facing the Bay of Biscay, this current begins to cool gradually. The waters transported by the current are cooled, with respect to the adjacent ocean waters, in their advance towards the Equator. This means that the Canary Current, when reaching the height of the Archipelago, can be considered as a cold current, always in relation to the temperature of ocean waters, the warmer the closer they are to Equator.

The Canary Current, although in general it presents variations throughout the year, has an SSO direction, parallel to the African coast. However, in the Canary Islands there are eddies, partly favored by the obstacle presented by the Islands to the general current. In shallow waters the current depends on the shape of the coast, but at some distance from the coast, at least on the islands of Tenerife, Lanzarote and Fuerteventura, on different occasions it has been observed as parallel to the coast.

Outside the influence of the Canary Islands, the average speed of the surface current is generally weak, especially in summer, not reaching 25 cm/s. However, among the Islands, especially when the tidal current has the same direction, the speed may be greater than 60 cm/s, as has been observed off the west coast of Tenerife.

Coastal and mesoscale processes

The Canary Current constitutes the eastern boundary of the North Atlantic subtropical gyre and flows parallel to the Northwest African continental margin until $\sim 15\text{--}21^\circ\text{N}$, where it detaches from the coast and merges into the westward North Equatorial Current. The Canary Current region displays a great geographical variability, resulting in highly diverse upwelling environments (Aristegui et al., 2009). For instance, the nutrient content of upwelled waters differs depending on the source of the water mass: North Atlantic Central Waters and South Atlantic Central Waters dominate north and south of Cape Blanc (21°N), respectively, with South Atlantic Central Waters providing higher concentrations of nutrients than the North Waters. Mesoscale activity plays also an important role in upwelling dynamics, as changes in shelf width and the presence of capes enhance the formation of recurrent filaments that export organic matter from the upwelling into the oligotrophic waters of the North Atlantic subtropical gyre. Besides, the perturbation of the main flow by the Canary Archipelago induces the generation of mesoscale eddies downstream the islands (at about $27\text{--}28^\circ\text{N}$), many of them drifting westwards to the open ocean along the path of an “eddy corridor” (Sangrà et al., 2009).

Despite this high diversity of environments, three main sub-regions are identified according to their upwelling intensity throughout the year: a seasonal upwelling zone along the Senegalese-Mauritanian coast, which expands from 13 to 20°N , a permanent upwelling zone, from 20 to 26°N , and a weak permanent upwelling zone, from 26 to 33°N . However, these latitudinal bands represent approximate boundaries, since they might vary from year to year due to the meridional shift of the trade wind system.

Figure 10: Schematic showing of vertical and horizontal fluxes associated with island generated cyclonic (C) and anti-cyclonic (A) eddies downstream of Gran Canaria Island.

(1) Surface flow and wind direction; (2) advection of chlorophyll-rich coastal water during cyclonic eddy formation; (3) entrainment of chlorophyll-rich water upwelled from the African coast by anti-cyclonic eddy; (4) lateral exchange of chlorophyll; DCM = Deep Chlorophyll Maximum. (Adapted from Arístegui *et al.*, 1997)

Tides

In the Canary Islands, as in almost all the Atlantic coasts, the tides are semi-diurnal, that is, that every day there are two high tides and two low tides, being approximately equal the amplitudes or vertical distances between high tides and consecutive low tides. The amplitude of the tide varies throughout the year reaching maximum values during the spring and autumn equinoxes, and in the Canarian coasts are of the order of 3 m. In the same way, the tidal range is minimal during solstices in early summer and winter, reaching values of up to 0.7 m approximately.

3.1.2 Waves

The waves of the Canary Islands are of two types, which give rise to two states of the sea: sea of wind and sea of bottom. In the sea of wind, the waves are under the action of the wind that

generates it; while during the sea of swells, the waves produced in the generating areas, when transmitted, reach a certain place in the absence of wind.

In summer, the area of the Canary Islands is under the action of the trade winds by Northeast wind waves, so that mainly the windward coasts of these winds are subject to an almost persistent swell, which usually does not reach 3 m height.

In shallow waters (less than half a wavelength) the friction of the bottom affects the movement of the wave, slowing down the deeper part of the wave that approach coast at an angle. Therefore, the fronts of the waves are curved when they reach shallow waters, that is, they are refracted and tend to be parallel to the coasts of the different islands of the Archipelago. In autumn, although the dominant swell is also from the Northeast, the weakening of the Azores anticyclone causes its intensity to decrease in the Canary Islands, producing periods of low waves, frequently interrupted by storms that, when crossing the North Atlantic Ocean, also hit the Canary Islands. From great distances the swell produced, sometimes at height greater than 10 m, spreads towards the South, being able to reach the Canary Islands after traveling up to 3,500 km in 2-3 days. In general, coming from the first and from the fourth quadrants, these swells reach the Canarian coasts, where they are refracted, shortened, and where their ridges sharpen, increasing the height of the wave up to hat 3.5 m. The storms passing at lower latitude, cause strong winds from the North side that produce waves of the order of 3 m in the northern coasts of the Islands. When the storms are very close to the Canary Islands, they can cause strong winds and swell from the SW, causing unusual storms in the southwestern Canary coasts.

As spring progresses, the anticyclonic situation in the Canary Islands area is reinforced, the influence of storms decreases and the waves tend to be exclusively generated by trade winds.

The waves in the Canary are the result of the combination of the local waves, controlled by the trade winds, and the swells generated by the storms located in the North Atlantic. In stormy episodes waves of up to 9 m high have been recorded. The action of the trade winds, together with the barrier effect that the Archipelago itself has on the flow of the Canary Islands Current, creates conditions so that the leeward areas of the islands, especially those of greater relief, is favoured by calm zones. These areas are less beaten by the wind and in them the waters mix less with those of the general current, giving rise to areas of warmer and more stable waters.

The Canary Archipelago presents an appealing wave energy resource, with an average annual wave power of 25 kW/m, while the Gran Canaria show an average annual wave power of 15 kW/m. It can be observed that when the bathymetry is more complex, affecting the propagations of the waves, the wave power is higher. The spatial distribution of the seasonal average wave energy power around the Gran Canaria Island shows that the winter months (December, January and February) are the most energetic ones, being the North coast more powerful than the East coast. The energy flux varies from 9 kW/m in the summer up to 20 - 25 kW/m in the winter.

3.1.3 Winds

The dominant climate in the Canary Islands is tropical dry, but due to its position in the middle of the Atlantic and its relief, there are numerous very significant topoclimates. The Canary Islands are riding between the western circulation zone that generates the polar front and the high subtropical pressures that are generated in the Azores. Although the trade winds regime is dominant, the seasonal variation of the Azores anticyclone allows the arrival of polar air masses, and the proximity to the African continent, at the height of the Sahara, allows the arrival of masses of dry continental tropical air and warm.

The wind regime in the Canary Basin is mainly determined by the location of the Azores high-pressure system, which causes that the mean wind direction range from the northeast all year long with changes being related to mesoscale weather systems. The most characteristic feature of the summer pattern is the ubiquitous Azores high-pressure elliptical centre that, together with the North Africa low baric center, produces the northeasterly trade wind regime. In the Canary Archipelago the trade winds reach their maximum monthly mean values of 8.7 m/s in August. During autumn or spring, the Azores anticyclone is not as deep as in summer, typically presenting a quite elongated shape.

The winter regime is determined by the southern movement of the Azores high pressure, which causes the passage of low-pressure centres through the Canary Basin. During winter the mean winds are still from the northeast, and the minimum monthly mean values corresponding to January (2.7 m/s). These winds reinforce the Canary Current, which attains its maximum intensity by late autumn. During winter the mean wind conditions respond to the high pressure centre located in its southernmost position, still causing northeasterlies but much weaker than during summer winds. At this time, it is frequent to find southwesterlies, associated to the passage of low-pressure centres, which cause important forcing fluctuations in relatively short time scales, a few days as compared with a characteristic time scale of 10 days during summer.

3.1.4 Sea water temperature

The temperature of the surface waters of the Canary Islands area presents notable differences in space and time, especially in the islands close to the African coast. The western islands have a higher average temperature than the eastern ones, due to the presence of deep colder waters.

The waters surface temperature ranges between a minimum of 16-18° C in the winter months and 23-25 °C of the summer, although seasonal phenomena of slightly more extreme temperatures may occur if certain sea currents are isolated. The temperature of the Atlantic Ocean around the Islands is not high since the cold current of the Canary Islands cools the body of water as it passes through the Archipelago.

In general, in horizontal distributions at the surface and at different levels, down to approximately 800 m deep, the isotherms tend to be parallel to the African coast, with increasing values as the distance from the coast increases.

Therefore, the surface temperatures of the waters of the western islands are, throughout the year, higher than those of the eastern ones, at a value that can sometimes reach 3 °C, mainly in summer. Between the waters of the eastern islands and those of the continental shelf of Cape Juby there is a temperature difference that also increases in summer, and that can reach 5 °C.

In the open sea, the temperature of the surface waters of the Canary archipelago can reach a maximum value of 25 °C in September and October, and a minimum value of 17 °C in the winter months. In shallow waters, especially in calm water bays, the exchange of heat with the atmosphere and with the land in the intertidal zone, especially on low-slope beaches, makes the difference in extreme temperatures usually higher to that indicated, and depend on the characteristics of the coastal zone. In the Canary Islands, as in the middle and low latitudes, the sea temperature has a vertical distribution, in which it is possible to distinguish three intervals:

- 1) An upper part, which can reach 150 m deep and has a great thermal variation throughout the year, because it is subject to the exchange of energy with the atmosphere.
- 2) A transition interval, consisting of intermediate waters between 150 m and approximately 2,000 m, in which the temperature decreases from 19-15 °C to 4 °C.
- 3) A lower part formed by cold waters, of polar origin, between 2,000 m and the bottom, where the temperature slowly decreases with depth, and can reach values of the order of 2.5 °C.

During the winter, the upper part of the sea in the Canary Islands is made up of homogeneous water, mixed by convection and by turbulence caused by the wind. However, at the end of spring and early summer, heat absorption produces a great increase in temperature at the top of the sea, which is called seasonal thermocline. Throughout the summer the seasonal thermocline intensifies, acquiring its maximum gradient at the end of that period and at the beginning of autumn, then weakening, disappearing almost completely when the season ends. However, immediately below the intermediate waters, there is an appreciable decrease in temperature with depth throughout the year, although much less pronounced than the seasonal thermocline, called permanent thermocline.

3.1.5 Salinity

The salinity of surface waters has annual values ranging between 36.7-36.9 psu, with eastern salinity values greater. A maximum difference of two degrees between the extremes of the Archipelago is found when moving off the African coast.

The salinity of the waters of the Canary Islands decreases with depth, as that of ocean waters at medium and low latitudes. This is mainly due to the fact that, due to the vertical decrease in temperature, the water density increases with depth, so that if there is an increase in surface salinity, water hardly descends a few meters. Immediately below the surface water, almost isohalin, there is a notable decrease in salinity, called halocline. At an average depth of 800 m a minimum is observed, with a value of 35.2-35.5 psu and then slightly increase between 1,100 m and 1,300 m, where it reaches a maximum of 35,7-35,3 psu, caused by water from the Mediterranean Sea that spreads at that depth. From this maximum, salinity slowly decreases, especially at depths greater than 2,000 m, in waters of polar origin, to remain practically constant from 4,000 m to the bottom,

with a value of 34.9 psu. The Canary waters have a minimum of surface salinity of approx. 36.2 psu during the summer and a maximum of 37.2 psu in winter.

In the horizontal distribution of salinity, the isohalines tend to be parallel to the African coast, presenting increasing values as their distance increases. Therefore, the surface waters of the western islands are up to approximately 1 unit more saline than those of the eastern ones, especially in winter, when the surface subtropical waters of high salinity are probably closer to the islands.

3.1.6 Dissolved oxygen

The amount of dissolved oxygen in the surface waters of the Canary Islands has supersaturation values in relation to temperature and salinity. This is realized down to about 100 m deep. At greater depths values below saturation are found, and typical minimum values of around 3.5 ml O₂·l⁻¹ are found at a depth of 700-1,000 m. From this point to the bottom of the ocean, the amount of oxygen increases again until it reaches values similar to those on the surface. This minimum of oxygen around 1,000 m is related to oxidation processes of suspended organic matter.

3.1.7 Nutrients

Nutrients are almost undetectable all year long within the mixed water layer, except during winter when deep convective mixing incorporates nutrients from the upper-thermocline. At this time, nitrate concentration may increase to 1–2 µmol/l in the top 150 m (Perez et al., 2001; Perez-Rodriguez et al., 2001). Phosphate concentration follows this same pattern while the silicate distribution in surface water shows intermittent high values (about 2 µmol/l) due to Sahara Dust events arriving to the region. Below the mixed layer we find the nutricline, where nutrient concentrations roughly increase with potential density except in those regions where the isopycnals approach the surface and nutrients are utilised.). As the upper-thermocline waters recirculate, dissolved nutrients increase through the dissolution of falling particles and regeneration of organic matter (Kawase and Sarmiento, 1985). Nitrate is very well linearly correlated with phosphate throughout the whole water column. Nitrate is nonlinearly correlated with silicate within due to redissolution of opal skeletons and decreased regeneration of nutrients with depth, particularly near the upwelling waters at the eastern boundary (Perez et al., 2001).

The Canary Islands are lacking a continental platform and sink rapidly to the ocean floor to reach depths of the order of 3,000 m a few miles from the coast. The oceanic waters surrounding the Canary Islands are oligotrophic waters. Nutrients are almost undetectable all year long within the mixed water layer, except during winter when deep convective mixing incorporates nutrients from the upper-thermocline. At this time, nitrate concentration may increase to 1–2 µmol/l in the top 150 m (Perez et al., 2001). Ammonium shows values in the Canary Islands below 1.0 µg N - NH₄/l and an irregular distribution with depth.

3.1.8 Rain

Figure 11: Rainfall and number of rainy days in Gran canaria (Source: worldweatheronline.com)

Canarian weather is definitely dry, and featured by a short number of rainy days concentrated from December to February. In Spring/Summer months from April to September, number of rainy days is 12 in total.

3.2 NATURAL ENVIRONMENT

3.2.1 Protected areas

The Canary Islands host a number of habitats classified as special, understanding as such those that have been subject to recognition and consideration by Community legislation and / or international conventions due to their special interest in science or biological diversity.

As for the habitats protected by community Directives, the Canary Islands require criteria adapted to the characteristics of the typically Macaronesian bottoms, in which shallow rocky habitats of volcanic origin predominate. This type of bottom, the most common in the coastal waters of the Canary Islands, is also the most influenced by anthropogenic action due to its proximity to the coast. In recent decades, these funds have been subject to destabilization due to the increase in the density of the lime hurchins (blanquizales), favored by the drastic decrease in predators. This fact is due, among other reasons, to the fishing pressure of the Canary fleet, a declining economic activity, but of great importance for the Canary primary sector.

Since the mid-1990s, different areas called Marine Reserves of Fishing Interest have been

established in the Archipelago and their resources, including several species of fish of commercial interest in the Annex III of the Protocol of Action on Marine Protected Areas and Biological Diversity of the Barcelona Convention, under the heading "Species whose exploitation must be regulated", has been safeguarded to increase the durability of fishing activity. The first was established in the island of La Graciosa and islets north of Lanzarote, in 1995. It covers funds up to 1,000 m deep and has an extension of 700 km², of which just over 11 km² are of integral reserve, specifically the waters that surround the Roque del Este, from its coast to a mile from it. Around this integral nucleus there is a restricted use zone of two miles of radius around La Roque with the sole purpose of prohibiting the practice of recreational fishing from a boat.

The Marine Reserve of Punta de La Restinga-Mar de Las Calmas, located at the southern end of the island of El Hierro, was declared in 1996. This reserve covers bottoms down to 400 m deep, and has an extension of 7.5 km² of which almost 2 km² are of integral reserve. It is flanked by two restricted use zones. The most recent Marine Reserve of Fishing Interest, established in 2001, is located in the southwest area of La Palma, and covers 37 km² of bottoms down to 1,000 m deep, of which 9 km² are of integral reserve.

There have been several initiatives from different areas (fishing sector, administrations, etc.) for the establishment of other areas with this protection regime in the rest of the islands (La Gomera, Tenerife, Gran Canaria, Fuerteventura), or even the increase in the geographical scope of protection of existing ones (such as the islands of El Hierro or La Palma). Other initiatives, of Cabildos or Town Halls, have gone through pointing to another type of protection regime less focused on fishing, although always from the local perspective. This is the case of the fishing micro-reserve promoted by the Granadilla City Council in Tenerife, the marine parks proposed by the Cabildo de Gran Canaria as part of its island strategy (El Confital Bay, El Cabrón, Maspalomas and Punta Sardina, according to Jordan et al. 2006), the project for the protection of diving areas in Tenerife (Güímar, Montaña Amarilla, El Palmar - Rasca) and Gran Canaria (Sardina, Cabrón, Baja Pasito and Arguineguín) within the framework of the GESMAR (Sustainable Management of Marine Resources), of the Madeira - Azores - Canary Islands Transnational Cooperation Program (PTC-MAC 2007-2013), or initiatives to prioritize areas to protect from WWF (WWF, 2006).

Another type of protection regime for the protection of these shallow rock bottoms is the World Biosphere Reserve. These are areas with terrestrial and / or coastal / marine ecosystems internationally recognized within the framework of the UNESCO Program on Man and the Biosphere (MAB). They contribute significantly to the fulfillment of the objectives of Program 21 and the agreements adopted at the Rio Conference and the Convention on Biological Biodiversity. The effectiveness of the Biosphere Reserves requires that the scientific community, the groups involved in conservation and development, the administrative authorities and the local communities, participate and work together to achieve their functions. In turn, the Biosphere Reserves constitute an agreement between all the agents that interact in their delimitation. In Spain, the areas declared by UNESCO have all or part of the territory protected by their own legislation. However, the Biosphere Reserves, even being recognized by the State, lack their own legal coverage in the state legal system and, although most have management bodies and have part of

their areas under other legal protection, they lack sufficient competences to achieve its objectives with the dynamism that the marine environment imposes, lacking - with the exception of some Autonomous Community - of legal instruments that allow an integrated management of its terrestrial and marine space. Some of these Biosphere Reserves do not include marine areas, but or behind it, such is the case of Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura.

In 1999, 174 Places of Community Importance (SCI) were proposed in the Canary Islands, which were declared in 2002 (Decision 2002/11 / EC). This figure, together with the update of 3 SCIs as compensation measures for the construction of the Port of Granadilla, and the 43 Special Protection Areas for Birds (ZPS), make a total of 208 “protected” spaces forming the Natura Network 2000 in the Canary Islands.

According to the Annexes of Habitats and Species to be protected from the European directive, the Canary Islands SCIs were established for various reasons:

Presence of Habitat 1110 “Sandbanks permanently covered by shallow seawater”: Sebadales del Sur de Tenerife, Sebadal de San Andrés, Sebadales de Antequera and Franja Marina Teno - Rasca in Tenerife, Playa de El Cabrón, Bahía de Gando, Sebadales from Playa del Inglés, Marine Strip of Mogán, Sebadales de Güigüi and Bahía del Confital in Gran Canaria, Sebadales de Guasimeta, Leeward beaches of Jandía and Sebadales de Corralejo in Fuerteventura and Sebadales de La Graciosa in Lanzarote. It should be mentioned that there are other criteria, which are not limited to the conservation of biodiversity, which give rise to the fact that the most important sebadales present in the Canary Islands have been left out of the protection of the SCI (such as the Granadilla sebadal) and that, After the new catalog of protected species of the Canary Islands (Law 4/2010, BOC No. 112 of June 9), neither the *Cymodocea nodosa* as a species, is protected, although it is classified as “Species of Interest for the Canary Ecosystems”.

Presence of Habitat 8330 “Submerged or semi-submerged Marine Caves”: Coast of San Juan de La Rambla and Marine Cave of San Juan in Tenerife, Coast of the Organs in La Gomera, Sea of Las Calmas in El Hierro, Coast of Garafía and Marine Strip from Fuencaliente in La Palma, Sardina del Norte Coast in Gran Canaria, Cave of Lobos in Fuerteventura and Cagafrecho and Los Jameos in Lanzarote.

For the adaptation to the Natura 2000 Network to the marine field within the planned deadlines, the Ministry of Environment, and Rural and Marine Affairs has run a LIFE + 2009-2013 project (Inventory and Designation of the Natura 2000 Network in Marine Areas) for the characterization as possible marine protected areas of a series of offshore areas within the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Spanish State. In the Canary Islands, the two zones chosen, already proposed at the time by the 2006 WWF report, are the Banco de La Concepción, northeast of Alegranza, and the Banks of Amanay and the Banquet, southwest of Fuerteventura known this area in the INDEMARES project as "South of Fuerteventura". The Banco de La Concepción rises from 2,541 m to its top at 170 m deep. Amanay and El Banquete are underwater mountains that rise from 2,000 m deep to 50-100 m at their tops.

The influence of the African upwelling and local upwellings on the western coast make this region the most productive in the Canary Islands. Although underwater mountains are considered as an essential habitat due to their sensitivity in the OSPAR list (“Seamounts”), the Habitats Directive does not yet consider them as such, although Habitat 1170 “Reefs” is considered. These types of underwater structures support other types of special habitats, also contemplated by the OSPAR list, such as deep sponge aggregations (“Deep - sea sponge aggregations”), or cold-water coral reefs (“*Lophelia pertusa* reefs”). In both there are several shark and whale shark protected by OSPAR areas, as well as several fish species of commercial interest included in Annex III of the Protocol of Action on Marine Protected Areas and Biological Diversity of the Barcelona Convention, under the heading of “Species whose exploitation must be regulated”.

Figure 12: Biosphere Reserve (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Figure 13: Map of protected areas, not including Natura 2000 (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 14: Sites of community interest, 2016 (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Figure 15: Map of habitat of community interest (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Figure 16: Detailed map of habitat of community interest, Arinaga area (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Figure 17: Bird areas, zone of special protection under Bird Directive (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Figure 18: Special conservation zones (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 19: IBA important bird areas (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 20: Bird priority areas (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

3.2.2 Birds

Seabirds are considered very good indicators for marine environment due to their long lives, being highly mobile with a wide foraging and habitat range, conspicuous manner at sea and at their breeding colonies (Piatt *et al.*, 2007). Changes in lower trophic levels or in the physiochemical state of the environment are likely to be manifested in their populations, and these taxa are also affected by anthropogenic pressures (both at their breeding colonies), invasive species (Hervías *et al.*, 2013), human disturbance (Vi-blanc *et al.*, 2012), human infrastructure developments (Hill, 1995) and habitat loss (Bost and Le Maho, 1993)) and within their foraging and non-breeding habitat at sea bycatch (Baker *et al.*, 2007), chemical and litter pollution (Montevecchi *et al.*, 2012), climate change and severe weather phenomena (Sydeman *et al.*, 2012).

The Macaronesia is an internationally important area for seabirds; however, most of the information needed for an accurate assessment is still missing. While the main islands were important breeding places in the past, most seabird populations are now restricted to small islets due to anthropogenic pressures (Monteiro *et al.*, 1996a). Some authors have pointed out the serious decline that some species, such as the Macaronesian shearwater (*Puffinus lherminieri*), are experiencing on the Canary Islands (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2012). Whereas, some colonies are still predicted to become extinct before any action plan is implemented (Bécares *et al.*, 2015).

The Commission Decision 2017/848/EU (2017) determines the species groups of Descriptor 1 of the MSFD. Five different groups based on how seabirds feed (see ICES, 2013) at sea are defined as listed below. However, only two of these groups are well represented in the Macaronesia. It is important to note that these definitions based on the feeding behaviour are not exclusive (i.e. some species might feed on different taxa even within the same functional group, and the different populations might present different diving depths and foraging behaviours (Burger, 2001). Nevertheless, the following seabird indicator species were selected as indicator species for the Macaronesian subregion based on the classification proposed:

Wading birds: Species of this group were not considered as good indicators species due to the difficult standardization. Only one species is known to breed in the Azores archipelago, the Kentish plover *Charadrius alexandrinus*. This species breeds in beaches and forages on mud flats, tidal areas and salt pans, so it was not considered to be indicative of the marine environment state.

Pelagic-feeding birds: Pelagic feeders dive below the surface to feed on fish and invertebrates (e.g. squid, zooplankton) at a broad range of depths or close to the seabed. ICES (2013) defined this group as ‘birds that feed across a broad depth range in the water column’. Five indicator species were selected as good indicators for the Macaronesia, based on the criteria listed in the Guidance for Assessment under Article 8 of the MSFD (WG GES, 2017).

- Bulwer’s petrel (*Bulweria bulwerii*)
- Desertas petrel (*Pterodroma deserta*)
- Cory’s shearwater (*Calonectris borealis*)
- Macaronesian shearwater (*Puffinus lherminieri baroli*)

- Zino's petrel (*Pterodroma madeira*)

Surface-feeding birds: Forage on small fish, zooplankton and other invertebrates at or within the surface layer (the upper 1–2 m). ICES (2013) determined this functional group as 'birds that are mostly restricted to the surface layer of the water column'. Five indicator species were selected as good indicators for the Macaronesia, based on the criteria listed in the Guidance for Assessment under Article 8 of the MSFD (WG GES, 2017).

- Band-rumped storm-petrel (*Hydrobates castro*)
- Common tern (*Sterna hirundo*)
- Monteiro's storm-petrel (*Hydrobates monteiroi*)
- Roseate tern (*Sterna dougalii*)
- White-faced storm-petrel (*Pelagodroma marina*)

Benthic-feeding birds: There are no known breeding species of this group for the subregion, thus no indicator species were chosen for this group. There are still large knowledge gaps regarding the Macaronesian seabird species, especially robust data that is systematically collected and validated for all species and representative number of colonies (population distribution, population abundance and population condition, for example). In the frame of MISTIC SEAS II, the seabird group followed a stoplight methodology in order to find common grounds between archipelagos and determine the indicators reachability, taking this lack of knowledge into account as well as the feasibility of the monitoring schemes proposed. After this process, twenty-one MUs were selected, comprising eight species of Procellariiformes and two species of Charadriiformes. While some species can be assessed in all three archipelagos, some will only be assessed in one or two, depending on the breeding colony's location and/or data/logistic available. Almalki et al. (2017) identified that Macaronesia archipelagos have unique populations based on genetics and morphometric differences suggesting that each archipelago is better assessed as an independent MUs. In total, 19 MUs of 8 indicator species were selected for the Azores, 7 for Madeira belonging to 7 indicator species and another 9 MUs of 6 indicator species for the Canary Islands. The species and the parameters measured were chosen based on standardized methods for monitoring as proposed by the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC), the OSPAR Sea Convention and other bodies relevant to seabird monitoring within the MSFD.

Table 5: Pelagic and surface feeding birds

Feature	Common name	Scientific name
Pelagic feeding birds	Bulwer's petrel	<i>Bulweria bulwerii</i>
	Desertas petrel	<i>Pterodroma deserta</i>
	Cory's shearwater	<i>Calonectris borealis</i>
	Macaronesian shearwater	<i>Puffinus lherminieri</i>
	Zinos's petrel	<i>Pterodroma madeira</i>
Surface	Brand-rumped strom petrel	<i>Hydrobates castro</i>

feeding birds	Common tern	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>
	Monteiro's storm petrel	<i>Hydrobates monteiroi</i>
	Roseate tern	<i>Sterna dougallii</i>
	White-faced storm petrel	<i>Pelagodroma marina</i>

Pelagic-feeding birds

Bulwer's petrel - *Bulweria bulwerii*

The Bulwer's petrel (*Bulweria bulwerii*) is a pantropical species that breeds in the three oceans. Its breeding distribution extends from the eastern Atlantic (Azores) to the southern Pacific (Marquesas islands) (Brooke, 2004). The species is highly pelagic. Its diet includes mainly fish and squid, although crustaceans and sea-striders have also been found in the diet. It feeds largely at night by surface-seizing (Neves et al., 2011a).

The Macaronesian populations of Bulwer's petrels largely overlap during the non-breeding season in tropical waters north of Saint Paul's Rocks, and only birds from the northern populations exploit the sub-tropical Atlantic Ocean further south than 20° (Ramos et al., 2015). The breeding season begins in late April-early May and lasts until September.

Bulwer's petrel is an abundant breeder in the archipelago of Madeira, particularly in the Desertas' islands (45.000 breeding pairs, Catry et al., 2014), nesting in smaller numbers in Selvagens (5000 breeding pairs (Zino and Biscoito, 1994), and few breeding pairs in Farol Islet (in the eastern tip of Madeira) and in the islets of Porto Santo. The scarce data on post-nuptial dispersion (obtained in Selvagem Grande) suggest that the birds migrate southwest to deep equatorial waters. Bulwer's petrel colonies in the Desertas, and also in the Selvagens, are considered the main breeding areas in the Atlantic Ocean (Catry et al., 2014). Bulwer's petrel will only be monitored in Selvagem Grande. This is a predator-free colony.

Although the species breeds in most islets and main islands, two colonies on the Canary Islands have been selected for the monitoring: La Graciosa (with introduced predator presence) and Montaña Clara (free of introduced predators). The breeding areas within these two locations are, nonetheless, fragmented, so a number of polygons were drawn in order to include a significant number of pairs.

Desertas petrel - *Pterodroma deserta*

The Desertas petrel (*Pterodroma deserta*) is a relatively recent split species (Jesus et al. 2009) and is considered one of the rarest procellariiform species in the world with 160-180 breeding pairs (BP). Population estimation shows a trend that is considered to be stable. Breeding occurs between early June and mid-November (Ramírez et al., 2013). It is considered as 'Vulnerable' according to IUCN criteria. Endemic breeding occurs only on a single plateau at Bugio Island (Madeira

archipelago, Portugal). Its distribution range covers both subtropical and tropical temperatures with intermediate wind speeds and oligotrophic waters and includes wintering areas identified at the Southwest, Central Tropical and Northwest Atlantic Ocean (Ramírez et al., 2013). It is also a species with high individual wintering site delity (Giménez et al., 2016), which according to the same author can bring conservation issues heavily dependent on an adult's exhibity and future generation's capacity to disperse and use new wintering areas.

Cory's shearwater - *Calonectris borealis*

There is not much data available for the Canary Islands although the species abundance seems to be stable (Rodrigues et al., 2012). The only population estimate for the whole archipelago dates from the late 1980's when around 30.000 pairs were estimated (Martín et al., 1987). However, recent and more local estimates seem to indicate that the Canary Islands population must be much bigger. For instance, over 10.000 pairs were estimated only on Alegranza Islet (Rodríguez et al., 2003).

Macaronesian shearwater - *Puffinus lherminieri*

The Macaronesian shearwater (*Puffinus lherminieri*) is pelagic and normally found in offshore waters. It breeds on oceanic islands and rocky offshore islets, occupying cliffs and earthy slopes, usually with little more than herbaceous vegetation, or amongst rocks. Recent revision of the taxonomy of the *P. assimilis* / *P. lherminieri* complex led BirdLife International (2014) suggests that *P. baroli* breeding on the Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Islands and *P. boydi* on the Cape Verde Islands should be regarded as subspecies of *P. lherminieri*. The Macaronesian shearwater is colonial, often nesting at low densities and in small numbers and sometimes in mixed colonies with other species, for example, Cory's shearwater, which can take over their burrows (Monteiro et al., 1996b). The Macaronesian shearwater is a non-migratory shearwater that feeds at the lowest trophic level among Macaronesian seabirds, shows diurnal and nocturnal activity and feeds deeper in the water column on small schooling squid and fish. Presenting different behaviour after the breeding period, the birds dispersed offshore in all directions and up to 2500 km from the breeding colony (off North America), fed at higher trophic levels and foraged mainly South of the colony and North in the Canary Islands (Bécares et al., 2016) while feeding at lower trophic levels during chick-rearing period (Neves et al., 2012). It breeds from December-January until late May, in rock crevices or self-excavated burrows.

Surface-feeding birds

Band-rumped storm petrel - *Hydrobates castro*

The band-rumped storm-petrel (*Hydrobates castro*) breeds on most oceanic islands in tropical and subtropical Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. This marine species is highly pelagic, occurs in warm waters and rarely approaches land except near colonies. It feeds mostly on planktonic crustaceans, sh and squid but will also feed on human refuse. It mainly feeds during the day by pattering, dipping and also by surface-seizing. Its breeding season varies locally in colonies on undisturbed

islets, in at areas near the sea or inland on cliffs (del Hoyo et *al.*, 1992).

In the Azores, five main islands have islets with confirmed breeding colonies – Santa Maria, São Jorge, Graciosa, Flores and Corvo, with 8 colonies in total (Monteiro et *al.*, 1999). This species breeds on surrounding islets and inaccessible cliffs on the islands, which makes the monitoring of its abundance difficult.

There is no accurate estimation on band-rumped storm-petrels (winter and summer population). It breeds on the Desertas Islands and on the Selvagens Islands. The last census indicates 10,000 birds around Madeira but most gathered on the Desertas and Selvagens Islands (Equipa Atlas, 2008a).

Common tern - *Sterna hirundo*

The common tern (*Sterna hirundo*) has been assessed only on Azorean islands. This feat though, is hindered by the inaccessibility of most colonies and/or over-predation of eggs and chicks (by European starlings, yellow-legged gulls and ruddy turnstones) in the more accessible ones (e.g. Praia and Vila islets) making data collection and research on breeding of terns extremely difficult.

The population of common terns in the Azores archipelago is substantial (~3000 pairs, Neves et al., 2011a) as well as breeds on all the Azorean islands mostly on the coast and small islets (inaccessible). Common terns breeding in the northwest spend the non-breeding period along the West African coast (Wernham et *al.*, 2002) and some terns from the Azores migrate to the coast of South America (Neves et *al.*, 2015). Breeding season starts in April until September. Terns forage very close to the colonies and do shallow dives through plunge diving.

White-faced storm petrel - *Pelagodroma marina*

The white-faced storm-petrel (*Pelagodroma marina*) breeds on several tropical, subtropical and temperate islands in both hemispheres, but some aspects of its breeding biology are still poorly known. The European subspecies *hypoleuca* is almost confined to a small archipelago, the Selvagens Islands, about 300 km south of Madeira Island. Due to this restricted distribution, this subspecies is relatively vulnerable to extinction. Breeding season occurs from mid-December to mid-August (Campos and Granadeiro, 1999) and the estimated Selvagem Grande population is 36,000 BP.

The number of white-faced storm petrels *Pelagodroma marina* may be higher than previously thought with a new estimate of at least 62,550 pairs on the two islets, Selvagem Pequena and Fora (Cтры et *al.*, 2010). This estimate still holds a considerable margin of uncertainty, and more studies are needed to determine the size of this population.

3.2.3 Fish

The fish are represented in the Canary Islands by 691 species (85 chondrichthys and 606 osteichthys) (Brito et al., 2002), being the third diversified group in the marine environment, after

mollusks (1,170 species) and arthropods (1,096 species). The diversity of fish in the Canary Islands is markedly greater than in Azores and Madeira, despite the fact that the deep areas (mesopelagic, bathypelagic, abyssal or batial) are much more investigated in Madeira. The current environmental circumstances of the Canary Islands, as also seems to have happened in past geological times, favouring the presence of a high number of species, but at the same time they are not very favourable to promote important evolutionary processes, so that endemism at the regional level it is low (Aguilera - Klink et al., 1994) and, in the case of vertebrates, practically negligible. Only three species of fish are indicated with certainty exclusively for the Canary Islands, but they are species of depth, little known, which probably have wider distributions. On the contrary, the number of endemisms on a larger scale is considerable, at the level of the Atlantic archipelagos that make up the so-called macaronesian region, since 18 species present in the Canary Islands seem to have this distribution model shared with one or more of the nearby archipelagos (Azores, Madeira and Cape Verde).

In a global analysis of the fish fauna, there is a clear domain of the forms of wide distribution (pantropical, cosmopolitan and tropical and subtropical amphitropical) (Brito et al., 1996), which is maintained in the analysis by large units or ichthyocenosis. This pattern is less marked in coastal pelagic ecosystems and upper batial funds, and is not true for coastal funds, which have a greater number of models and a predominance of more restricted forms of distribution (Brito et al., 2001). Thus, for the coastal species and those pelagic linked to the coast, there is a predominance of the species distributed by warm-temperate sectors of the eastern Atlantic and of those of wider distribution by said sector, a remarkable representation of those widely distributed by tropical sectors (amphitropical and pantropical), the scarce entity of the typically Guinean and the confirmation of the existence of an appreciable macaronesian contingent, representing almost 7% of the species. At the island level, the biogeographic patterns also show a particular distribution in relation to the environmental characteristics of the islands, so that warm species increase towards the western islands, the most oceanic and warm, and those of a temperate nature towards east, influenced by the cold waters of the African upwelling.

Pelagic fish

In the Canary Islands, due to the low existing productivity, there is a reduced biomass of nektonic species in relation to other regions, although there is a great diversity of species. The epipelagic nekton can be divided into littoral, composed of species that always remain in the same waters, although they do not have to be exclusively neritic, and in oceanic, formed by species that make migrations across the ocean (tuna and some sharks mainly), but not exclusive to the oceanic region and also found in coastal waters.

Many epipelagic species of small size and short life have a great capacity for reproduction and are grouped together forming schools:

- Scomber (*Scomber colias*): it is the most abundant pelagic-coastal species caught in the Canarian waters. Epipelagic and migratory, it is found in nearby coastal and oceanic waters, up to 250-300 m deep. Make seasonal migrations, approaching and moving away from the

coast, and occasionally penetrating shallow coastal waters. It feeds on planktonic organisms and small fish, and constitutes the food of several pelagic species such as medregales, tunas, etc.

- Sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*): migratory species that inhabits the waters of the insular platform, from the surface up to 250 m deep. It feeds on phyto and zooplankton (mainly planktonic crustaceans).
- *Sardinella aurita*: it is distributed on the insular platform up to 250 m deep. It is migratory and feeds on small planktonic invertebrates, fish larvae and phytoplankton.
- *Sardinella maderensis*: it is distributed on the insular platform up to 100 m deep. Make migrations of approach and remoteness of the coast of low intensity. It feeds on small planktonic invertebrates, fish larvae and phytoplankton.
- *Trachurus picturatus* and *T. trachurus*: inhabit the waters up to 300 m deep. It is usually littoral pelagic, but it can often be found near the bottom, on sandy substrates. They carry out seasonal migrations, approaching and moving away from the coast, where the juveniles are located. They feed on fish, crustaceans and cephalopods.
- *Atherina presbyter*: pelagic coast that forms compact schools near the surface and near the coast, generally in rocky inlets, cliffed areas and breakwaters to a depth of about 20 m. They feed on small crustaceans, juveniles of mollusks and fish larvae, and are the prey of medregales, barracudas, among others.
- Anchovies (*Engraulis encrasicolus*): Inhabits coastal waters, where it forms large schools. It is found in the waters of the insular platform and the upper edge of the slope. It tends to migrate towards shallow waters in summer, returning and descending in winter at depth. It feeds on planktonic organisms.
- *Boops boops*: it is found on all kinds of bottoms of the insular platform (rocky, mixed and sandy) up to 250 m deep. In coastal waters it is usually found mostly at the edges of the steep rocks.

The white pigeon (*Trachinotus ovatus*), the needle (*Belone belone*), the palometon (*Lichia amia*), the bluefish (*Pomatomus saltatrix*), the barracudas (*Sphyraena* spp.) and the amberjacks (*Seriola dumerili*, *S. fasciata*, *S. rivoliana*) are also typical in coastal waters. The barracudas and the medregales frequent the rocks and coastal lows, where they usually prey on the small benthic fish.

The Mugílids (*Liza auratus* etc.) live mainly in sandy and muddy bottoms. They form flocks and swim in the middle water and on the surface, although they are benthic feeders, ingesting a lot of mud (Brito et al., 1984).

Several species of deep-water fishes, especially those that perform nocturnal vertical migrations to surface waters, are fully integrated into island dynamics. This is the case, for example, of the scholar (*Ruvettus pretiosus*) or *Promethichthys prometheus*, which during day are on batial bottoms, below 400 m deep, and at night they ascend to surface.

In the waters of the Canary archipelago, about twenty species of pelagic sharks have been cited, the most common and characteristic of this fauna being the tintorera or blue shark (*Prionace glauca*), the hammerhead sharks (*Sphyrna spp.*) and the Mako (*Isurus oxyrinchus*). Other epipelagic sharks of the Carcharinidae and Lamnidae family are present in waters of the Canary archipelago, although their populations are very scarce and their presence in artisanal catches is anecdotal. Another representative of this epipelagic fauna is the blanket (*Mobula mobular* and *M. tarapacana*), which frequents the coastal and oceanic waters around the Islands and is usually seen swimming on the surface feeding on small fish and planktonic animals.

Tunas are epipelagic fish that live in all warm and temperate seas, and to a lesser extent, in the cold. Normally they are found forming large schools in a relatively superficial layer, they live on the high seas, approaching the coasts by seasons. They perform remarkable reproductive migrations (genetic migrations) and feeding (trophic migrations). It is in the course of the latter when they arrive in the Canary Islands, where they remain for some time, preying on the banks of small pelagics, fundamentally, mackerel, sardine, vogue, guelde and trumpeter, as well as various species of cephalopods.

The situation of the Canary Islands, as well as their oceanographic characteristics, determined by the cold current of the Canary Islands, the trade winds and the proximity to the African coasts, make their waters can be frequented by several species of tuna, both from the group of the temperate ones, as of the group of typically tropical species. The Archipelago represent, for most of these species, the boundary zone where their catches acquire some importance. The main species that visit the Canarian waters are tuna or bigeye (*Thunnus thynnus*), yellowfin (*Thunnus albacares*), albacore or skipjack (*Thunnus alalunga*), prickly pear (*Thunnus obesus*), and bonito or listing (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) (Brito et al., 1984). All these species have a marked seasonality, appearing on the Islands, each of them, at different times of the year. Other tunas that appear in the Islands at some times ace of the year, although less frequently, are the melva (*Auxis thazard*), the sierra or bonito (*Sarda sarda*), the breastplate (*Acanthocybium solandri*), and the tarmac (*Orcynopsis unicolor*). The swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*), the great marlin (*Makaira nigricans* and *Tetrapturus albidus*) and the sailfish (*Istiophorus albicans*) are also oceanic species sporadically caught in the Canarian waters.

On the other hand, the mesopelagic and batipelagic areas lack primary producers. Mesopelagic organisms, through vertical migration, can reach the epipelagic zone and take more direct advantage of phytoplankton productivity, while batypelagics depend mainly on microorganisms and detritus that fall from the upper zones. The density and diversity of organisms is higher in the mesopelagic area.

Ramos and Bordes, (2001) determined that the mesopelagic fauna maintains its presence in all

the Islands between 400 and 700 m deep during the day, and perform a vertical migration ascending at sunset and descending at dawn. These authors identified 115 species of mesopelagic fish belonging to the following orders: Anguilliformes, Osmeriformes, Stomiiformes, Aulopiformes, Myctophiformes, Lampriformes, Stephanoberyciformes, Zeiformes, Syngnathiformes and Perciformes.

Benthic and demersal fish

Among the fish that inhabit sublittoral sandy bottoms without vegetation, *Xyrichtys novacula*, *Bothus podas*, various representatives of the *Soleidae* family, *Uranoscopus scaber* stand out. Spider fish (*Trachinus draco* and *T. radiatus*) or the family Triglidae represented by the species *Trigloporus lastoviza* and *Chelidonichthys obscurus*. In certain sectors, with stability in the sediment and subject to the currents, appear the populations of the garden eels (*H. longissimus*) that constitute one of the typical communities of the soft bottoms. Among the fish of nocturnal habits, it is worth mentioning the conger *Ariosoma balearicum*, as well as several chondrichthys: the chuchos (*Dasyatis pastinaca*, *Taeniura grabata*), the torpedo (*Torpedo marmorata*), the manta (*Gymnura altavela*) and the angelfish (*Squatina squatina*). Other frequent chondrichthys in the shallow sandy bottoms are the dogfish (*Mustelus mustelus* and *M. asterias*). Most of the epifauna species mentioned are also associated with seagrass beds and other plant communities present on soft substrates. The sandy bottoms of transition constitute the own habitat of species like the mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*) or the breca (*Pagellus erythrinus*), among others.

In the seabeds it can be found species of fish of the family Syngnathidae: *Syngnathus typhle*, *S. acus* and *Nerophis ophidion*, or of the family Gobiidae as the green bloodsucker *Opeatogenys cadenati*.

Mena et al. (1993) recorded 51 species of fish present in several seabeds of Tenerife, while Espino et al. (2008) catalog 67 species for the seabeds of the eastern islands; In both studies, the Sparidae family is the best represented in terms of specific wealth. The mojarra (*Diplodus annularis*) and the chopra (*Spondyliosoma cantharus*) are the best represented.

The fish community of the sublittoral rock bottoms has a remarkable species richness and high structural complexity, indicating the presence on these bottoms of a total of 132 species for the whole of the islands. The most frequent species in the sampling on this type of bottoms are the black fula (*Abudefduf luridus*), the white fula (*Chromis limbata*), the pejeverde (*Thalassoma turkey*), the *Sparisoma cretense* and the blue drum (*Canthigaster rostrata*). The ichthyological composition of the blanquial is characterized mainly by the white fula (*Chromis limbata*), black brunette (*Muraena augusti*), murion (*Gymnothorax unicolor*), cabrilla (*Serranus atricauda*), abade (*Mycteroperca fusca*), pejeperro (*Bodianus scrofa*), genus *Diplodus*, *Dentex* and roosters (*Balistes capriscus*, *Stephanolepis hispidus*), among other fish.

Among the characteristic fish of the soft littoral bottoms there is the *Uranoscopus scaber*, the spider fish *Trachinus radiatus*, the *Trigloporus lastoviza* and *Chelidonichthys obscurus* and among the chondrichthys: the chuchos (*Dasyatis pastinaca*, *Taeniura grabata*), the tablecloth

(*Gymnura altavela*), the angel (*Squatina squatina*) and the dogfish (*Mustelus mustelus* and *M. asterias*).

The fish community of hard substrates in the circalitoral zone is represented by numerous species, many of them of notable commercial interest: in this area the main artisanal fishing activities of the Canary Islands are developed. Along with the species already indicated above for the infralitoral zone, other characteristics such as samas and snappers (*Dentex spp.*), the bocinegro (*Pagrus pagrus*), the drums (*Umbrina ronchus* and *U. canariensis*), the Conger (*Conger conger*) are characteristic, as the sprout (*Phycis phycis*) or the small sparid of the genus *Pagellus*.

In the deepest part of the soft batial and abyssal bottoms there are fish species with commercial interest, some with numerous populations constituting important fishing resources. Popcorn populations can be found (*Beryx decadactylus* and *B. splendens*), white hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), scorpenidae such as the black mouth (*Helicolenus dactylopterus*) or the bishop (*Pontinus kuhlii*), in addition to other species indicated for the circalitoral zone. Certain bentopelagic fish are also present in these depths, such as the school (*Ruvettus pretiosus*), the rabbit (*Promethichthys prometheus*) and the lamp (*Epigonus telescopus*). Among the most frequent shark and rays are the *Galeorhinus galeus*, *Odontaspis ferox*, *Centrophorus granulosus*, *Dalatias licha*.

3.2.4 Mammals

3.2.4.1 Bats

Currently, seven native species of bats, belonging to the genera *Pipistrelus*, *Plecotus*, *Barbastella* and *Tadarida*, are known in the Canary Islands, which makes this group the most important of the island mammals.

The different works carried out to date on Canarian bats reveal a great affinity between island and continental populations. These affinities are evident even when considering endemic taxa such as the 'canary ears' (*Plecotus teneriffae*).

Based on genetic and color differences, the Canary Islands' forest bat populations were described as endemic (*Barbastella basbastellus guanchae*), currently the scarcest and most distribution-restricted chiropter of those living in the Canary Islands.

Among the Canarian bats the only endemic species is the long-eared (*Plecotus teneriffae*), present in all types of habitats, but more common in forest areas of pine or mixed pine.

With their powers of flights, bats have been able to colonise the islands over the years, and currently there are eight breeding species. Most of the bats require sheltered areas out of the prevailing winds in which to forage at night for flying insects, and many species are therefore restricted mostly to areas with intact forest structure close to roost sites. Populations of many species would have declined, as the original forest cover was lost. Seven species of bat breed on the Canary Islands, while just three species occur in Madeira. However, bat distribution is uneven on the Canaries, showing higher diversity on the wetter and more heavily vegetated Western and Central Canaries, while only one species, the widespread Kuhl's Pipistrelle, breeds on Fuerteventura.

The Canary Big-eared Bat is endemic to the Western and Central Canaries, and the Barbastelle has an endemic subspecies on La Gomera and Tenerife. The Madeira Pipistrelle occurs on both island groups and is found elsewhere only on the Azores. One further species, the Egyptian Fruit Bat, was accidentally introduced to Tenerife, where it caused problems for native fauna and flora, so was the subject of an eradication programme and is believed to have been extirpated by 2016. Some of the commoner bats may be encountered feeding around outside light in built-up areas, but many of the bats are rarely seen and remain poorly known. Populations' sizes of many of the bats are thought to be small and a risk from loss of roosting and feeding habitat and, in particular, overuse of pesticides.

Table 6: Canary Islands and Gran Canaria bat species and their red list

Common Name	Scientific Name	Gran Canaria	RLS	RLE	RLG
European free-tailed bat	<i>Tadarida teniotis</i>	x	LC	LC	LC
Barbastelle	<i>Barbastella barbastellus</i>		VU	VU	NT
Savi's pipistrelle	<i>Hypsugo savii</i>	x	LC	LC	LC
Leisler's bat/ Lesser noctule	<i>Nyctalus leisleri</i>	x	LC	LC	LC
Kuhl's pipistrelle	<i>Pipistrellus kuhlii</i>	x	LC	LC	LC
Madeira pipistrelle	<i>Pipistrellus maderensis</i>	x	EN	VU	VU
Canary big-eared bat	<i>Plecotus teneriffae</i>		EN	VU	VU

3.2.4.2 Cetaceans

Atlantic spotted dolphin - *Stenella frontalis*

The Atlantic spotted dolphin (*Stenella frontalis*) is a small delphinid endemic to the tropical and warm-temperate Atlantic, ranging between 50°N to about 25°S. In the Northeast Atlantic, it is mainly found in pelagic waters, where it feeds on small epi- and mesopelagic sh and squid (Herzing and Perrin, 2018).

The Atlantic spotted dolphin was identified as a common MU for the three Macaronesian archipelagos, being one of the most abundant species in Macaronesia. Given their oceanic distribution and reliance on pelagic prey, it was considered a good indicator species to assess the GES of pelagic ecosystems. In addition, the distribution of the species seems to be strongly linked to water temperature and primary productivity (Tobeña *et al.*, 2016) (which possibly affects the distribution of their preferred prey) and abundance of the species may provide a good indicator of climate-induced changes in marine ecosystems in the region.

This species is seasonally abundant in the Azores. Although there have been no comparisons with dolphins from the Canary Islands, the wide-ranging movements of the species and their

seasonal presence in Azores and Madeira suggests that a single population occurs in Macaronesian waters. Atlantic spotted dolphins are also seasonally abundant in Madeira appearing mainly in summer and autumn but are also observed the rest of the year (Freitas *et al.*, 2014a). The seasonal presence of Atlantic spotted dolphins reduces the exposure to local human impacts in coastal waters, but its wide movements and considerable use of offshore waters makes them potentially vulnerable, directly or indirectly, to fisheries and other human activities in the open ocean. This species is also targeted by whale-watching boats being the second most observed species in Madeira with 23% of all sightings (Freitas *et al.*, 2014a). In the Canary Islands, this species is present throughout the year all over the archipelago with relative fewer sightings during the summer months when it is seasonally more abundant in Azores and Madeira.

Bottlenose dolphin - *Tursiops truncatus*

Bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) inhabit temperate, subtropical and tropical oceans worldwide. They are primarily found in coastal areas (lagoons, bays, estuarine and marine habitats) and over the continental shelf, but some populations live mainly in pelagic waters. Coastal bottlenose dolphins preferentially feed on benthic fish while offshore bottlenose dolphins rely more on epipelagic and mesopelagic prey (Wells and Scott, 2018).

The bottlenose dolphin is one of the most frequently sighted species in all the three European Macaronesian archipelagos. This species is representative of coastal island shelf habitats, offshore seamounts, and can be used to assess the environmental state of ecosystems therein.

This species is present year-round in the Azores mainly over shallow areas around the islands and offshore seamounts (Tobeña *et al.*, 2016). Photo identification and genetic data indicate that bottlenose dolphins in the Azores constitute a single but open population composed of several geographic communities that interact with neighbouring communities and with dolphins from outside the archipelago (Silva, 2008). Genetic studies show that there is no more than one population within the Azores archipelago, and that dolphins from the Azores are not genetically differentiated from dolphins occurring in Madeira or in the offshore waters of the Northeast Atlantic (Louis *et al.*, 2014). They are genetically distinct from coastal populations living in the UK, Ireland, France and Spain, and from Mediterranean dolphins of the Strait of Gibraltar and Alboran Sea (Louis *et al.*, 2014). Thus, bottlenose dolphins occurring in the Azores are part of the North Atlantic offshore population of bottlenose dolphins.

Some movements of individuals among western islands of the Canary Islands (El Hierro, La Palma, La Gomera and Tenerife) (Tobeña *et al.*, 2014) were recorded indicating that at least 20% of the dolphins in the western islands travel among different Special Areas of Conservation (SACs). While a high proportion of bottlenose dolphins are seen only once in these waters (transient animals), others have been re-sighted multiple times and could belong to island-associated communities.

Due to its coastal distribution and year-round presence, island-associated bottlenose dolphins may be highly susceptible to local, human impacts including those derived from regular exposure to

whale-watching boats, marine traffic, habitat loss and shery bycatch. In addition, island-associated bottlenose dolphins may constitute unique ecological or demographic units and should be monitored separately from offshore populations.

Common dolphin - *Delphinus delphis*

The common dolphin (*Delphinus delphis*) has a seasonal presence in Canary coastal waters mainly in winter and spring. Still, some groups are seen year-round. These animals belong to a larger oceanic population that includes common dolphins from Azores as shown by the absence of genetic differences between them (Querouil *et al.*, 2010).

The common dolphin is present year-round in the Azores and is the most frequently sighted species from late autumn to early spring. However, sightings of the species decline significantly in spring and summer (Silva *et al.*, 2014) when line-transect surveys to monitor marine mammal abundance are likely to take place due to better weather conditions and could be insufficient for robust abundance estimation. Thus, this species was not considered a suitable indicator for the Azores.

The common dolphin is proposed as indicator species due to its oceanic distribution, occupying a specific ecological niche associated with pelagic waters, feeding on prey also targeted by sheries (small pelagic fish) and interacting more often than other cetacean species with the tuna shing boats (Nicolau *et al.*, 2014). The examination of stranded animals over the years has shown evidence of mortality in this species related with human activities, namely, impact from litter, bycatch and intentional killing; although those impacts seem to be at a quite low level.

Bryde's whale - *Balaenoptera edeni*

This species occupies a specific ecological niche in oceanic pelagic waters at a low trophic level in the marine food chain.

It is the most common baleen whale in the Canary Islands waters, present throughout the year, with a greater number of sightings recorded between April and October. The archipelago represents breeding and feeding area for this species.

Fin whale - *Balaenoptera physalus*

The fin whale (*Balaenoptera physalus*) has been reported from all the oceans of the world. Its global distribution includes temperate and polar latitudes, with a hiatus in equatorial waters. The species is believed to undertake regular seasonal migrations between low-latitude breeding areas in winter and high-latitude feeding grounds in summer. Fin whales feed on a wide variety of organisms including euphausiids and schooling shes (Aguilar and Garca-Vernet, 2018).

The fin whale occupies a unique niche at an intermediate-low position in the food web. As such, this species is expected to respond rapidly and strongly to changes in physical, chemical and hydrographic properties of the pelagic ecosystem as well as to contamination.

In the macaronesian archipelagos, fin whales are observed mostly from spring to early summer along the banks off the central islands and in the open waters between groups of islands, but the species has been acoustically detected also during autumn and winter (Silva *et al.*, 2014). Satellite telemetry studies show that the macaronesian region s constitutes a mid-latitude foraging ground for this species (Silva *et al.*, 2013) and its occurrence in the area is associated with seasonal productivity (Tobeña *et al.*, 2016). Fin whales encountered in spring and summer migrate to Greenland-Iceland foraging grounds (Silva *et al.*, 2014) and belong to a single population of fin whales that is considered to exist in the North Atlantic based on genetic analysis (Bérubé *et al.*, 1998).

Cuvier's beaked whale - *Ziphius cavirostris*

Cuvier's beaked whales are present year-round in the Canary Islands with high degree of residency reported in some areas (e.g. the southern area of El Hierro Island, (Reyes *et al.*, 2015), and the eastern areas of Lanzarote and Fuerteventura Islands). Several hotspots exists in the Canary Islands, as the El Hierro Island and the eastern areas of Lanzarote and Fuerteventura islands.

The Cuvier's beaked whale is the most abundant beaked whale species implicated in mass stranding events that occurred in different parts of the world including the Canary Islands on several occasions (Santos *et al.*, 2007; Fernández *et al.*, 2009). Beaked whales are considered especially susceptible to noise sources and for this reason they are the best indicator among the cetacean species to detect pressure from anthropogenic noise, a pressure with potential population level effects in some cases.

Risso's dolphin - *Grampus griseus*

Risso's dolphins (*Grampus griseus*) are distributed worldwide in temperate and tropical oceans with an apparent preference for steep shelf-edge habitats between 400 and 1000 m deep. This species feeds mostly on mid- and deep-water cephalopods (Hartman, 2018).

Risso's dolphins are present year-round where they and tend to occupy waters deeper than 1000 m as well as island shelves (Silva *et al.*, 2014). This species feeds mostly on mid- and deep-water cephalopods and it is a good indicator of GES for deep pelagic systems.

Short-finned pilot whale - *Globicephala macrorhynchus*

The short-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*) is a deep diving species that explores the deep pelagic ecological niche with a preferential use of waters deeper than 1000 m.

The species is a regular visitor to the Azores but sightings vary greatly across months and years consistent with their transitory presence in the area (Silva *et al.*, 2014). This would make it dif cult to obtain robust absolute abundance estimates for short- nned pilot whales in the Azores and use the species as an indicator of GES of deep-diving toothed cetaceans.

The short- finned pilot whale also has a permanent presence in the Canary Islands coastal waters

with a preferential use of waters deeper than 700 m. Its distribution along the islands is uneven with a much higher presence in the southwest waters of Tenerife and La Gomera where resident populations use these waters for feeding, socialising, resting, breeding and calving (Servidio, 2014). Photo identification studies over previous decades have shown that short-nosed pilot whales using the archipelago belong to a larger oceanic population with most animals being identified as transient animals and a smaller proportion of re-sighted animals (visitors and animals associated to the islands; Servidio, 2014). These two ecotypes mix and interact with each other contributing to a complex social and population structure and prevent genetic isolation of the island-associated animals. The extent to which this species uses the offshore waters of the archipelago is unknown.

The island-associated animals are strongly vulnerable to local human impacts due to much higher use of the area and also due to being the target of a highly developed whale-watching industry (Servidio, 2014). This species, targeted by whale-watching boats, is the third most observed with 12% of all sightings (Freitas *et al.*, 2014a).

Sperm whale - *Physeter macrocephalus*

Sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) are widely distributed from the tropics to near the ice edges in both hemispheres but males and females occupy distinct parts of this range. Females stay in tropical and subtropical waters year-round where they live in long-term social groups with their immature offspring. Males disperse from their natal group as they approach puberty and gradually move to higher latitudes reaching as far as polar waters. In their late twenties, males start migrating periodically to the warm waters inhabited by females to mate (Whitehead, 2003). The diet of sperm whales is mainly comprised of deep-water cephalopods and fishes (Clarke *et al.*, 1993).

Social units of sperm whales are nomadic and their distribution is driven by the distribution of their deep-water prey (Whitehead, 2003). Hence, sperm whales were proposed as an indicator of mesopelagic and bathypelagic ecosystems in the Macaronesia. In addition, sperm whales are one of the main targets of the whale-watching industry (Oliveira, 2005), which makes it useful to monitor the impact from this pressure.

Steiner *et al.* (2015) found 13 matches of female and immature whales between the Azores and Canary Islands, one between Azores and Madeira, and one between the Canary Islands and Madeira. No matches were found from any of these sites to Cape Verde, the Caribbean, Gulf of Mexico or the Mediterranean. These results suggest that sperm whales seen in the Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands may belong to a single population that has a core habitat within Macaronesian waters. Mortality rates from ship strikes in the Canary Islands may be threatening this population (Fais *et al.*, 2016). Ship strikes are also a growing concern in the Azores where four sperm whales are known to have died from collisions with vessels (unpublished data). Although ship strikes do not seem to be a major issue in Madeira inshore waters, the same cannot be said about offshore waters because of lack of data (Cunha *et al.*, 2017). The population may also be adversely affected by underwater noise especially from seismic surveys widely used in geophysical research and mining exploration.

Seals

Monk seal - *Monachus monachus*

The Mediterranean monk seal (*Monachus monachus*) is a critically endangered species. With less than 600 individuals throughout its distribution range, it is considered one of the most endangered mammals in the world (Karamanlidis and Dendrinis, 2015). It is priority species of Community interest listed in Annexes II and IV of the Habitats Directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC, 1992).

The species has two clearly differentiated populations. The Mediterranean one is mostly distributed in Greek and Turkish territory. The Atlantic population is divided into two isolated sub-populations: one in Africa (Mauritania and Morocco) and the other in Europe (Madeira). From the 1950s, fishing activities caused a sharp decline in the Madeiran sub-population. By 1988 only 6-8 individuals were left.

Conservation efforts since the 1980s, however, have increased the European Atlantic population to an estimated at 30-40 individuals (5-7% of the global population). Nevertheless, the gradual growth in population and distribution of the species in the archipelago of Madeira is creating new tensions with different users of the marine environment, especially fishermen, tour operators and local inhabitants.

Monk seal is present only in Madeira.

3.2.5 Reptiles

Loggerhead turtle - *Caretta caretta*

The loggerhead turtles (*Caretta caretta*) are highly migratory animals that use a wide range of broadly separated areas and habitats during their lifetime (Bolten and Witherington, 2003). Upon leaving the nesting beach, hatchlings begin an oceanic phase in major current systems (gyres) that act as open-ocean developmental grounds (Bolten and Witherington, 2003; Putman and Mans eds, 2015). After 6.5 - 11.5 years in this oceanic zone, loggerheads recruit and migrate to neritic areas rich in benthic prey or epipelagic prey notwithstanding that individual may be moving between oceanic and neritic environments. Age at maturity varies considerably, and it is estimated at 10-42 years (Arens and Snover, 2013). Once loggerhead turtles reach sexual maturity they undertake breeding migrations between foraging grounds and nesting areas at remigration intervals of one to several years with a mean of 2.5 - 3 years for females (Schroeder *et al.*, 2003). Males would have a shorter remigration interval (Hays *et al.*, 2010). Both males and females migrate and, in doing so, may traverse oceanic zones (Plotkin, 2003). Loggerhead turtles are the most common species in all three archipelagos, and their status can be linked to the state of the local pelagic environment and associated pressures (e.g. oceanic fisheries).

Loggerhead turtles in this region are found throughout the year and consist mainly of juveniles with curved carapace lengths (CCL) ranging from approximately 8.5 to 82 cm (e.g. Bolten, 2003).

The main rookeries that contribute to the local aggregation are South Florida, the largest nesting population in the Atlantic and second largest worldwide, Northeast Florida-North Carolina, Mexico and Cape Verde (Bolten *et al.*, 1998).

No contemporary abundance estimates for the loggerhead population are available in the Canary Islands. The juveniles that arrive to the Canary waters have very large movement dispersal in search of feeding grounds ranging from the coast of Portugal to Mauritania and north of Cape Verde (Varo-Cruz *et al.*, 2016). A sex ratio of 7 females: 1 male was obtained using data from the necropsies of individual loggerheads in the Canary Islands (Orós *et al.*, 2016), but it is not currently known whether this ratio is representative of turtles present in the waters of the archipelago or if otherwise there is a mortality biased by sex. Spanish surface longline fishing fleet work around Canary waters but, at least currently, the activity does not seem to be too intensive and it is limited to a few months per year. Most of the Canary shing fleet is made up of artisanal shing vessels (87.5%). This eet is mixed and uses various types of shing gears and targets different species.

Green Turtle- *Chelonia mydas*

The green turtle (*Chelonia mydas*) has a global distribution, occurring throughout tropical and, to a lesser extent, subtropical waters. This species is also highly migratory and occupies different habits during its life cycle.

After hatching, green turtles disperse from their natal beaches and typically spend 3–5 years in open-ocean pelagic habitats, feeding mainly on planktonic animals (Musick and Limpus, 1997). When their curved carapace length (CCL) is 20–40 cm, turtles settle into neritic/benthic habitats to which they show delity for at least several months (Meylan *et al.*, 2011). Settlement is typically associated with a shift from a carnivorous diet to an omnivorous or herbivorous diet consisting of macroalgae and seagrasses. Nevertheless, some individuals could stay in the pelagic environment during their whole life (Hatase *et al.*, 2002). Individuals forage in distinct areas as juveniles and adults and migrate to other areas once they are close to reaching sexual maturity. During the adult stage, green turtles undertake periodic migrations between foraging grounds and nesting areas generally every 2-3 years. The age of sexual maturation is estimated around 19-50 years (Avens and Snover, 2013).

Canary waters constitute a feeding and developmental area for juveniles that occupy neritic coastal habitat. Green turtles in the Canary Islands are juveniles in their neritic phase (CCL = 53.7 ± 12.6 , mean \pm SD; range = 28.3-79.9 cm, n = 38), and born in different populations from the eastern and western Atlantic, mainly Guinea Bissau, Surinam and Costa Rica. However, it is necessary to sample during a period of 4-6 years to determine the natural genetic variability (although this depends on the sampled animals) The distribution doesn't seem to be uniform along the coasts of the archipelago and isconcentrated in certain localities. In each locality, a reduced number of individuals have been registered using reduced areas (<45 km²) for several years (Monzón-Argüello *et al.*, 2015). *Phanerogam seagrass* beds are used as feeding areas, including *Cymodocea nodosa*, in its diet. Some individuals show a link with the ports where they feed opportunistically (Monzón-Argüello *et al.*, 2015, 2018a, 2018b). Studies of this species started recently in this area

(2014) and available information is therefore limited. Up-to-date information is still scarce although important knowledge on various aspects of their biology and ecology is available.

3.2.6 Primary production

The marine fauna and flora of the Canary Islands are rich and diverse, both in terms of resident and migratory species, which arrive from more northern latitudes and also from more tropical sectors (Haroun *et al.*, 2003). This high biological diversity is due to the subtropical nature of the Archipelago, close to Africa, and in the course of the cold current of the Canary Islands, which puts it in contact with temperate zones of the north and warm ones of the west, as well as for the complex pattern of regional variability. On the other hand, as with other oceanic islands, the presence of great depths at a very short distance from the coast, allows the integration of oceanic species in an island dynamic and seems to favour some particular phenomena, such as the settlement of stable colonies of cetaceans.

Phytoplankton

Primary production is determined mainly by the concentration of nutrients available and the amount of light: in subtropical areas, such as the Canary Islands, light does not become a limiting factor, productivity will depend on the amount of nutrients available to phytoplankton (Brito *et al.*, 1984).

In the open ocean waters of the Canary region, the annual plankton production cycle is affected by the quasi-permanent seasonal thermocline. This sharp density transition restricts the vertical flux of inorganic nutrients from upper thermocline waters to the euphotic zone, limiting phytoplankton growth during most of the year. The seasonal thermocline only disappears during winter as the result of surface cooling and the mixed layer reaches its maximum penetration depth (150–200 m). The seasonal thermocline begins to reform in April–May, leading to the more common situation of a surface euphotic zone depleted of nutrients. Therefore, only during the short mixing period that follows deep convection that phytoplankton can grow fast. In this circumstance, the phytoplankton builds up a bloom, at the only condition that cellular growth rate is higher than the grazing rate of zooplankton. The dynamics of this late-winter bloom is more similar to the autumn bloom (nutrient-limited) than to the spring bloom (light-limited) in temperate seas.

From late spring to early winter, most chlorophyll is found in a deep maximum within the seasonal thermocline, and large phytoplankton cells are almost absent from surface waters. Indeed, small picophytoplankton, characteristic of oligo-trophic regions, is the most abundant autotrophic group, contributing to total chlorophyll and production more than 75% in autumn and up to 50% in spring (Aristegui *et al.*, 2001). These cells, together with the heterotrophic bacteria and their consumers, the heterotrophic flagellates, are the main components of the autotrophic and heterotrophic biomasses, respectively, of the planktonic food webs. They are also mainly responsible for the remineralization of organic matter in surface waters (Aristegui and Montero,

2005). Nevertheless, the structure of this microbial community displays seasonal and spatial changes, to a large extent related with mesoscale variability induced by the flow passing through the islands and the nearby coastal upwelling.

Only during late winter peaks in chlorophyll and primary production may be observed in surface waters. These maxima (0.5–1.0 mg/m³) are significantly higher than the annual means (0.2 mg/m³ Braun and Real, 1984). Chlorophyll values between 0-200 m were between 30 and 155 mg m⁻². To the east of the island of Fuerteventura to the north of Gran Canaria and La Palma, the annual productivity decreased in gradient towards the west (237 g C m⁻² year⁻¹, 164 g C m⁻² year⁻¹ and 145 g C m⁻² year⁻¹). The high productivity of Fuerteventura was related to the seasonal coastal upwelling, and although it was observed on the other two islands, there was no corresponding increase in productivity, which indicated that the waters were poor in nutrients, more characteristic of the oligotrophic ocean, with minimal influence of coastal in waters near the surface.

In oceanic waters the year-round variation in chlorophyll concentrations, integrated over the whole water column, ranges between 15 and 60 mg Chl m. This range of variation is relatively small as compared with the much larger variability in primary production values, at least one order of magnitude greater (Basterretxea, 2000).

Table 7: Chlorophyll values and primary production for oceanic waters of the Canary Islands Current, around the Canary Islands and on the outcrop of the African coast

(Source: Hernández - León et al., 2007)

	Chlorophyll (mg m ⁻³)	Primary Production (mg C m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Open ocean	< 0,05	100-200
Canary Islands	0,10 - 0,14	325-385
Outcrop	1-14	180-5.300

Zooplankton

Zooplankton biomass values are rather low during most of the annual cycle. North of Tenerife Island, the average biomass value between 0 and 200 m depth was found at 390 mg dry weight/l, while south of Gran Canaria Island the average value for the annual cycle was 1370 mg dw/m³ for the same depth strata. This sharp difference is related to an island mass effect on the biomass values of plankton. A mesozooplankton bloom appears to coincide with increased mixing during late winter (Hernandez-Leon, 1998), although an increase of biomass may be observed in July–August coinciding with the maximum intensity of the trade winds on the southern shelf of Gran Canaria Island. Mesozooplankton grazing in the Canary Island waters is relatively small, in agreement with observations for other oceanic areas. Based on indices of metabolism and assuming herbivorous feeding, it was estimated that this potential grazing accounted for 10% to 46% of the primary production, while most of the grazing control in these waters should be due to Protista

Finally, the control of zooplankton and protista on primary production can change depending on the bottom-up and top-down control in the rather complex food web of warm water ecosystems.

Ictioplankton

94% of the larvae present in canarian waters have a neritic origin. The sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), show a significant correlation between lower filament temperatures and their abundance. In contrast, larvae of oceanic species are virtually excluded from the filament. Anchovy larvae are also good indicators of offshore displacement of the upwelling waters, and that the alternation between anchovy and sardine as dominant species in the area's fish larvae community during the summer depends mainly of the temperature of the water in the region of the African upwelling, dominating the anchovy in the highest temperatures.

3.2.7 Benthos

Figure 21: Broad benthic classification (Source: EMODnet, www.emodnet.eu)

Species

According to Brito. (1984), from the point of view of marine fauna, the Canary Islands are well framed in the Atlantic-Mediterranean region (from the English Channel to Cape Blanco), keeping greater affinity with a sector that covers from coasts of southern Portugal to the southern tip of it, including the Western Mediterranean, although they present a fauna with peculiar characteristics due to a greater presence of tropical, subtropical, pantropical and amphiatlantic species, and a certain degree of endemism.

The number of marine species identified in the Canary Islands until 2003 amounts to 5,232 and

63 subspecies. Of these, the endemisms amounted to 164 species and 5 subspecies (Moro *et al.*, 2003). The number of endemic marine taxa is low compared to the terrestrial environment, which is explained by the greater uniformity of its physical characteristics, both spatially and temporally, more evident in the deepest areas. The volcanic origin of the Canary Islands and their position in Macaronesia is the most important factor in terms of the distribution and uniqueness of the marine species that inhabit them. This origin gives the islands high slopes on the seabed, limiting the area of the bathymetric ranges and making light the crucial factor that determines the distribution of ecosystems. In this way we find that between 5 and 50 m there are 2,379 species, 45% of the total. This concentration of species in such a small belt highlights the importance of good coastal management in order to protect coastal natural resources.

With regard to marine flora, the Canary Islands are located in the southern position of the warm temperate region of the eastern Atlantic (Hoek, 1984), which extends from the south of the British Isles to the coasts of Senegal, also including the Mediterranean Sea. This region shows the greatest floristic wealth on the east coast of the Atlantic (Hoek, 1975). Benthic algae in the Canary Islands (Rhodophyta, Phaeophyta, Chlorophyta and Cyanophyta) are represented by 702 species (Moro *et al.*, 2003), with a clear domain of red algae (56%), followed by brown algae (19%), and green algae (17%) and finally cyanophytes (9%). According to Samson *et al.* (2001), and on a floristic catalog of 621 species, the predominance of red algae with respect to the rest of the divisions is due to the proximity of the Canary Islands to the tropics. These same authors point out that approximately 31% of the species of algae have a restricted distribution area within the limits of the warm temperate region of the eastern Atlantic and, therefore, are endemic to this phytogeographic region. On the contrary, the exclusive endemisms of the Canary Islands are very scarce, only 16 species (Afonso-Carrillo and Samson, 1999).

The rest of the components of the marine flora are distributed between characteristic species of the tropical and subtropical coasts (30%), species widely distributed throughout most of the coasts of the whole world, and that can be treated as cosmopolitan and subcosmopolitan (19%), characteristic species of the cold temperate coasts that in many cases have their southern distribution limits (16%) in the Canary Islands and, finally, a small number of species of disjoint distributions (4%). The Canary Islands show, as a feature within the warm temperate region of the eastern Atlantic, a high number of species of distribution amphiatlantic and with these islands as the only known locations on this side of the Atlantic. While in the case of red algae the endemic and tropical-subtropical elements are clearly dominant, in brown and green algae, the proportion is similar for all large phytogeographic groups.

On the east coast of Gran Canaria, facing the BGF possible installation, there are currently two SIC areas (“ES7010053 Playa del Cabrón” and “ES7010048 Bahía de Gando”) that are part of the Natura 2000 Network, designated by the presence of important sandbars (Habitat “1110 Sand banks covered permanently by shallow seawater) and, in the case of Gando Bay, because they are also habitat for the loggerhead turtle (Species 1224 “*Caretta caretta*”). Due to the small size of these protected areas, the strong fishing activity that exists in the area and the great diversity and richness of marine communities that house their bottoms, the protected area is currently insufficient to

ensure their conservation.

In the Gando-Arinaga area, the creation of a marine reserve in offshore waters has been proposed and, in addition to biological data on its waters, evaluations have been carried out on the impact that different human activities may have on this area.

In visual sampling, 36 fish species have been counted, increasing their richness with depth and being especially abundant *Abudefduf luridus*, *Thalassoma turkey*, *Chromis limbata*, *Sparisoma cretense*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Pomadasys incisus* and *Boops boops*. It is also an area where there has been extensive fishing activity that is endangering the biological diversity of the area and has led to the overexploitation of various species.

El Cabrón beach is home to a great ecological and genetic wealth. Studies on their communities between the infralittoral zone and -30 meters deep describe bottoms in which 7 clearly key environments stand out:

1- The upper infralittoral belt, with small tidal ponds and some algal communities composed of *Calothrix crustacea*, *Enteromorpha compressa*, *Fucus spiralis*, *Cystoseira humilis*, *C. compressa*, *Padina pavonica*, *Hypnea spinella*, *Rytiphlaea tinctoria*, *Corallina elongata*, *Ceramium spp.*, *Gelidium pusillum*, *Spyridteria lamentosa* and *Haloporia lamentosa scoparia*.

The most characteristic fauna is mollusks (*Littorina striata*, *Osilinus atratus*, *Patella spp.*, *Chiton canariensis*, *Siphonaria grisea*, *Haliotis coccinea canariensis*, *Aplysia dactylomela*, *Gibbula candei*, *Amyclina pfeifferi*, *Columbella rustica*, *Marginella sp.*, *Mitra gitstonia*, *Mitra hamatama*, *Mitra gitoma striata*, *Mitra lamellosum*), crustaceans (*Grapsus grapsus*, *Ligia italica*, *Chthamalus stellatus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *P. serratus*, *Dromia personata*, *Clibanarius aequabilis*, *Pagurus anachoretus*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*, *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Xantho incissa*, *X. poressa*), *Anemonia sulcata* and *Actinia equina*, echinoderms (*Coscinasterias tenuispina*, *Asterina gibbosa*, *Paracentrotus lividus*, *Ophioderma longicauda*) and fish (*Gobius paganellus*, *Mauligobius maderensis* and *Parablennius parvicornis*).

2 - The photophylic seaweed band. With *Asparagopsis taxiformis*, *Cottoniella lamentosa*, *Cystoseira abies-marina*, *C. compressa*, *Dictyota spp.*, *Halopithys incurva*, *Halopteris scoparia*, *Lophocladia trichoclados*, *Sargassum desfontainesii*, *S. vulgare*, *Stypopodium zonale* and *Rytiphlaea tinctoria*. Withing this belt, cnidarians can also be observed (*Corynactis viridis*, *Balanophyllia regia*); mollusks (*Kaloplocamus ramosus*, *Strigatella zebrina*, *Stramonita haemastoma* and *Octopus vulgaris*); crustaceans (*Lysmata seticauda*, *Dromia personata*, *Macropodia rostrata*, *Maja cristata*, *M. squinado*, *Pisa nodipes*, *Plagusia depressa* and *Stenorhynchus lanceolatus*); echinoderms (*Arbacia lixula*, *Paracentrotus lividus*, *Holothuria arguinensis*, *H. dakarensis*, *H. sanctori* and *Echinaster sepositus*); and fish (*Abudefduf luridus*, *Centrolabrus trutta*, *Chromis limbata*, *Diplodus cervinus*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *Oblada melanura*, *Sparisoma cretense*, *Spondyliosoma cantharus* and *Thalassoma turkey*). In some areas, where rocky bottoms covered by seagrass beds with sandy bottoms alternate, other fish species are found such as *Canthigaster capistrata*, *Chromis limbata*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Sphyraena viridensis* and schools

formed by a large number of snoring *Pomadasys incisus*, commonly known in the islands with the name of "hoarseness".

3 - The blanquizal. Dominated by the sea hurchin *Diadema antillarum*, with densities of 7-10 specimens per m². Crustaceans (*Stenorhynchus lanceolatus* and *Tuleariocaris neglecta*) are observed; fish (*Chromis limbata*, *Abudefduf luridus*, *Coris julis*, *Thalassoma turkey*, *Ophioblennius atlanticus*, *Labrisomus nuchipinnis*, *Tripterygion delaisi*, *Diplodus sargus*, *D. cervinus*, *D. vulgaris*, *Serranus atricauda*, *S. cabrilla*, *Mycteroperca rubatus*, *Epinephelus pausus*, *Dentex dentex*, *Balistes capriscus* and *Aulostomus strigosus*); seaweed (*Dictyota spp.* and *Cottoniella lamentosa*); annelids (*Hermodice carunculata*, *Sabella spallanzanii* and *Protula tubularia*); mollusks (*Hypselodoris picta*, *Peltodoris atromaculata* and *Cerithium vulgatum*) and echinoderms (*Ophidiaster ophidianus*, *Echinaster sepositus*, *Marthasterias glacialis*, *Coscinasterias tenuispina*, *Arbacia lixula*, *Holothuria sanctori* and *H. dakarensis*).

4 - The boulder bottom. It houses some important communities of algae (*Sporochnus pedunculatus*, *Lophocladia trichocladus*, *Asparagopsis taxiformis* etc.), in which the populations of the polychaete *Eurythoe complanata* can develop under the stones, and sporadically, *Phyllodoce madeirensis*, the mollusks *Lima lima*, *Mantellum hians* and *Haliotis coccinea canariensis*, the echinoderms *Antedon bifida* and *Ophiolepis paucispina*, the decapod crustaceans *Gnathophyllum elegans*, *Alpheus macrocheles*, *Pagurus anachoretus* and *Galathea sp.* and the chafarrocas fish (*Lepadogaster sp.*). In the deep infralitoral (-30 m.), dominated by a strong hydrodynamic, appear colonies of gorgonian anthozoans (*Leptogorgia ruberrima*) and zoantal (*Gerardia savaglia*). On these colonies can be found the gastropod mollusk *Neosimnia spelta*. On these bottoms the sargos (*Diplodus sargus*, *D. cervinus* and *D. vulgaris*) and the mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*) exploit the benthic fauna.

5 - Caves and other dark environments. Some are large (20 meters long). Species found are *Bonellia viridis*, *Caryophyllia sp.* *Scleractinias*, *Polydora sp.* *Polychaetes*, *Morchellium argus* and crustaceans *Enoplometopus callistus*, *Lysmata grabhami*, *Cinetorhynchus rigens*, *Scyllarides latus*, *Stenopus spinosus* and the elasmobranch *Taeniura grabata*. In the cavities and cracks it is common to find the anemone *Telmatactis sp.* next to the crustacean *Thor amboinensis*.

The populations of croaker, such as *Umbrina canariensis* and *U. cirrosa*, stand out for being few species in the islands. Other species representing the ichthyofauna are *Apogon imberbis*, *Aulostomus strigosus*, *Phycis phycis*, *Heteropriacanthus cruentatus* and *Thorogobius ephippiatus*.

6 - Sandy bottoms. They are mainly terrigenous in nature. It is where the typical community of garden eels (*Heteroconger longissimus*) is located, between the rocky slope and the beginning of the turf of Phanerógams. Nor is it difficult to observe the false conger (*Ariosoma balearicum*).

Buried in this substrate can be seen the mollusks *Linga columbella*, *Venus verrucosa*, *Maetra corallina*, *Tonna galea* and *Phalium granulatum*; the echinoderms *Narcissia canariensis*, *Astropecten aranciatus* and *Brissus unicolor*; the crustacean *Calappa granulata*; and the cnidarians *Pachycerianthus sp.*; not forgetting the abundant presence of fish, especially elasmobranchs (*Squatina squatina*, *Taeniura grabata*, *Dasyatis parsnip*, *Myliobatis aquila*, *Torpedo marmorata*).

7 - Seagrass beds. *Cymodocea nodosa* meadows usually occur on sandy substrates between -12 and -25 meters deep. At greater depth, *Cymodocea nodosa* is gradually replaced by the chlorophycea *Caulerpa prolifera*. Both *Cymodocea* and *Caulerpa* are seasonally colonized by epiphytes as *Fosliella spp.*, *Polysiphonia exella*, *Cottoniella lamentosa* and *Dasya spp.*

Finally, it should also be noted the occasional presence in these shallow environments of species of interest due to their rarity in the Canarian backgrounds, such as the teleost *Lutjanus goreensis* and the ophiuroid *Ophiopsila aranea*.

Figure 22: Map of *Cymodocea nodosa* beds (Source: EMODnet, www.emodnet.eu)

In the upper batial zone, over the -200 meters, clusters or fields of *Stichopathes sp.*, which develop on a rocky substrate, next to *Alcyonium sp.*, numerous sponges and *Astrospartus mediterraneus* were found. In greater depth, soft bottoms predominate in this area, with more sandy areas that, due to the current, form underwater dunes and ripples, and odflush formed by compact sediment.

Scatteredly, species of cnidarians appear as sea whips (*Funiculina quadrangularis*), gorgonians (cf. *Siphonogorgia scleropharingea*, *Viminella agellum*), black corals (*Stichopathes sp.*), Dead hands coral (*Alcyonium sp.*, Cf. *Bellonella sp.*), stony corals (*Caryophyllia cyathus*, *Flabellum chunii*), flytrap anemones (*Actinoscyphiidae*) and hydrozoos (*Sertularella sp.*).

Among the fish, the ojiverdes (*Chlorophthalmus agassizi*) stand out because of their abundance, which perched on the ground facing the current forming large clusters. Other species present are *Arnoglossus cf. imperialis*, *Capros aper*, *Conger conger*, *Cyttopsis rosea*, *Helicolenus*

dactylopterus and *Macroramphosus scolopax*, as well as the elasmobranchs *Dasyatis pastinaca*, *Raja maderensis* and *Squalus megalops*. There are also demospongiacs and hexactinélidas, bryozoans (*Hornera sp.*), Mollusks (*Eledone cirrhosa*, *E. moschata*), as well as lepadomorphs that develop on the shell of the deep-rooted ñocla (*Cancer bellianus*). Finally, mention should be made of the presence of taliaceae (*Pyrosoma atlanticum*) and ctenophores (*Cestum veneris*).

Between -450 and 500 meters, the formation of a reef formed by the calcareous structures of colonies of *Lophelia pertusa* stands out, as well as the presence of species of Alcionáceos (*Bebryce mollis*) and antipatarios (*Parantipathes hirondelle*) different from those recorded at a lower depth. The same occurs in the case of the appearance of hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), an undocumented fish species in shallower areas. Finally, mention the existence of sponges (*Asconema setubalense*) and echinoids (*Echinus melo*).

Anthropic wastes and debris are abundant, including mats, tubes, plastics, cans, metals, ends and fabrics.

Figure 23: Benthic broad habitat types (Source: EMODnet, www.emodnet.eu)

Benthic communities

The benthic communities of the Macaronesian biogeographic region can hardly be classified by the EUNIS classification codes; currently they are included under the Spanish classification of benthic habitat (Templado et al., 2012)

Soft substrates

- **Coastal communities**

The mobile bottoms with low organic matter content, with their instability prevents the settlement of sessile species. The community is represented almost exclusively by the infauna, consisting of microorganisms such as protozoa and small worms from different groups that live in the interstices that leave the grains of sand.

On the sandy beaches there is the same community of amphipod crustaceans as in the supralittoral sandy areas, and that they live buried or under the accumulations of seaweed and seagrasses deposited by the sea. They are detritivorous species of the genera *Talitrus*, *Orchestia* and *Floresorchestia* (Brito et al., 1984). In the lower horizon, species of macrofauna can appear such as mollusks that live buried in the sediment (the bivalves *Ctena decussata* and *Glycymeris pilosa*), and the crabs *Albunea carabus* and *Portumnus latipes*. Muddy and muddy substrates are scarce, due to the slopes of the bottom and the marine dynamics of the islands. A small population of the marine Phanerogam *Zostera noltii*, which seems to reach here the southern limit in its geographical distribution, has been located in Arrecife (Lanzarote), in muddy bottoms of 0-3 m (being able to withstand periods of emersion). *Z. noltii* is distributed throughout the Mediterranean, European Atlantic coasts, British Isles and Mauritania. In coastal depressions with a high salinity in the substrate, and subject to long periods of drought in the short tide times, communities of coastal halophilic vegetation or “Saladares” are installed. They are characterized by the presence of *Arthrocnemum macrostachyum*, occasionally accompanied by *Zygophyllum fontanesii*. These salt flats are typical of the flat coast of the eastern islands.

Almost at the boundary of high tide, the Salt Marshlands are located, which are constituted by more complex communities floristically and structurally. *Sarcocornia perennis*, characteristic of the southwestern European Atlantic coastlines, is a bush of the family of *Chaenopodiaceae*, with woody and crawling stems from which erect, fleshy and yellowish-reddish branches emerge about 20 cm high. Another subassociation is characterized by the ever-living *Limonium ovalifolium*. This community resists short periods in which it remains completely covered by high tide, a limiting factor for other halophilic species.

▪ **Infralittoral communities**

The specific composition of this ecosystem varies greatly depending on the predominant environmental factors. As a result of these environmental factors, the biocenoses present are different in the northern or southern areas of the islands. In addition, biocenosis, both vagile and sessile, is very diverse and varied, with very marked differences between the eastern and western islands.

Although in the Canarian waters there are species of algae that exceed 100 m deep, the optimal area for the development of these plant communities does not usually exceed 50 m. This production of plant biomass and its extension on the substrate is affected by the devouring activity of the *Lima hurchin* (*Diadema aff. Antillarum*) very common in the rocky bottoms of this bathymetric level. The populations of this herbivore are so abundant, that in those places where they are found, the rocky substrate completely lacks plant cover. These funds without algal coverage are called blanquizal, named for the whitish color that shows the rocky bottom due to the presence of

calcareous algae, motherpowers and sponges that cover it and that resist the continuous browsing of these hurchins.

The beginning of the infralitoral zone is marked, in general, by a dense algal settlement characterized by the pheophyte *Cystoseira abies-marine* (usually the most abundant) and other genera such as *Gelidium*, *Corallina*, *Zonaria*, *Padina* or *Sargassum*. In this dense algal settlement known as "belt of photophilic algae", lives a rich sessile fauna, as the sponge *Ircinia spp.* and *Aplysina aerophoba*. The photophilic anemones *Anemonia sulcata* and *Aiptasia mutabilis* are also frequent. Some slow-moving organisms, such as stars *Marthasterias glacialis* and *Coscinasterias tenuispina*, powerful predators, are present. Herbivorous invertebrates as *Patella spp.*, *Luria lurida* and *Erosaria spurca*, *Paracentrotus lividus*; *Arbacia lixula* or *Diadema aff. Antillarum*, and crustaceans consume intensely the different species of algae present in these shallow bottoms.

This algal band reaches a variable depth, although it normally does not exceed 15 m deep, below which, these algae develop only forming spots in very specific places. The relative composition of species in this algal band is variable, changing according to the ecological conditions acting and mentioned above. Depending on the degree of prevailing hydrodynamics, two types of communities can be distinguished, one in funds or open areas with strong hydrodynamics and another in funds or protected areas with low hydrodynamics. In funds with great hydrodynamics, the *Cystoseira abies-marine* species marks the tidal limits up to 2 or 4 m below the low tide line, where they are replaced by other brown algae communities, with the following species as dominant: *C. discor*, *Lobophora variegata*, *Zonaria tournefortii*, *Styopodium zonale*, *Taonia atomaria*, *Padina pavonica*, *Dictyota dichotoma*, *Sargassum vulgare* and *S. desfontainesii*.

As the depth increases, the effects of the waves are less intense, so they are established alongside other brown seaweed communities species such as *Helminthocladia calvadosii*, *Liagora distenta*, *Asparagopsis taxiformis* and *Asparagopsis armata*. Other species of brown and red algae appear in the semi-exposed waves areas. The most common brown algae are *Dictyota dichotoma* and *Sargassum desfontainesii* and *Lobophora variegata*, the latter usually associated with vertical walls. Among the species of red algae are *Helminthocladia calvadosii* and others belonging to the genera *Liagora* and *Bryopsis*. In sheltered funds or quiet areas with blocks or stones, red algae communities settle in the form of dense masses, the most abundant species being: *Liagora canariensis*, *Asparagopsis taxiformis*, *Asparagopsis armata*, *Dudresnaya verticillata*, *Helminthocladia calvadosii*. In the western islands, funds with low hydrodynamics are populated with calcareous algae of encrustant type and populations of *Caulerpa webbiana* and *Codium decorticatum*. In addition, in these more protected places with sciaphilic environments, the species *Lobophora variegata*, *Zonaria tourneforti* and *Styopodium zonale* are abundant.

In the Canary Islands, the largest number of algae species (420 species) has been found in the upper infralitoral (0-10 m deep). Of these, 129 species are so far exclusive of these depths. This number drops sharply, up to 120 species, in the next 20 m deep. Below 30 m, knowledge of marine flora is still partial, and data are only available in isolated locations on the islands. However, 19 species of algae have been cited exclusively under the 30 m level, some of them as *Cryptonemia seminervis* and *Syringoderma floridana* below 60 m and others such as *Leptofauchea brasiliensis*

below 90 m (Haroun *et al.*, 1993; Samson *et al.*, 2001).

Generally, below the band of photophilic algae there are rocky or stony whitish bottoms, devoid of or almost devoid of algae and with a dense settlement of the *Diadema aff. antillarum* urchin. The lower limit of the band of photophilic algae does not seem to be marked by the lack of light intensity, but by the intense browsing. In some areas, especially in the first meters, other species of hedgehogs stand out for their abundance such as *Paracentrotus lividus* and *Arbacia lixula*.

Figure 24: The “Blanquizal” (*source: Monterroso et al., 2010*)

In these funds devoid of algal coverage and with a dense settlement of the hedgehog *D. aff. antillarum*, some sessile invertebrates are characteristic such as sponges *Hemimycale columella*, *Batzella inops*, *Phorbas fictitius*, *Chondrosia reniformis*, *Petrosia (Petrosia) ficiformis* and *Sarcotragus fasciculatus*. The bryozoans *Schizomavella auriculata*, *Reptaedonella violacea*, *Celleporina lucida*, *Doliocoitis atlantica* constitute an important faunistic component. In places with high hydrodynamics, the gorgonians *Aglaophenia* and *Leptogorgia viminalis* are typical. Present are the nudibranch *Hypselodoris picta*, the prosobranchs *Charonia lampas* and *Ch.*

Variiegata (busios), predators of *D. aff. antillarum*, some stars like *Ophidiaster ophidianus* and *Hacelia attenuata* or the free-living polychaete *Hermodice carunculata*.

On the underside of the most stable rocks and in certain areas with formations such as walls, cornices or cavities, environments or microenvironments are characterized mainly by a severe decrease in the light gradient. They live an abundant sessile fauna more or less sciáfila, as well as numerous vague species, especially molluscs and crustaceans. The algal population is poor, represented by sciáfilic species that disappear when the light reaches certain limits. On the other hand, stable rocks have a rich sciafilic fauna on their underside, constituted mainly by spongiaries, bryozoans, polychaetes, crinoids, ofiuras, nudibranchs, crustaceans and ascidians. Some species of sponges, especially the corneans, and calcareous algae, contribute to stabilize these rocks, cementing them to the substrate. Also on the underside of the stony stones located a few meters deep, there is a fauna similar to that mentioned for the stony ones located in the mesolithral zone, highlighting the sponges of the genus *Clathrina*, the decapod crustaceans *Percnon gibbesi* and *Porcellana platycheles*, the ophiura *Ophioderma longicauda*, the nudibranchs such as *Chromodoris purpurea*, the herbivorous prosobranch *Haliotis tuberculata coccinea*, the cyprea *Luria lurida* and *Erosaria spurca*, the chiton *Chiton (Rhyssoplax) canariensis*, the fish *Lepadogaster candolii*. The *Antedon bifida* crinoid, the *Celleporina lucida* bryozoan, the anemones of the genus *Telmatactis*, the polychaetes such as *Eurythoe complanata* and the *Echiurus sp.* (Brito et al., 1984) are found on these bottoms.

On the walls or cornices that start from the surface, the initial photophilic algae band is rapidly impoverished, giving way to a population, in general, not very dense, of sciaphilic elements. In small places the small coralimorphic actinia *Corynactis viridis* is common, forming pseudocolonies of great extension, as well as hydroids among which *Aglaophenia* quill stands out. In some places of the islands, mantles of encrusting anemones (*Palythoa caribbaeorum* and *Protopalythoa canariensis*) are also developed on rocky or stony substrates, covering surfaces of hundreds of square meters (Espino et al., 2006). At greater depths, 6-10 m, semi-swamp species appear, such as the hermatypic coral of macaronesian distribution *Madracis asperula*, which grows forming plates with short and irregular branches. In the deeper walls, below 20 m, the settlement is typically similar to the circalitoral, highlighting the colonies of the zoantidium with a corneal skeleton *Gerardia macaronesica* and the antipataro *Antipathes wollastoni* (Black Coral).

Anfractuositities and cavities serve as habitat for numerous species characteristic of the infralitoral zone. The spongiaries stand out for their diversity and abundance, especially *Chondrosia reniformis*, *Ircinia spp.*, *Spongionella pulchella* and *Petrosia (Petrosia) ficiformes*; the latter serves as food and substrate for the mollusk nudibranch *Peltodoris atromaculata*. Among the anthozoans, an anemone of the genus *Telmatactis* is characteristic, of remarkable size and variable and very colorful colors. This species has a rich commensal fauna associated with crustaceans, such as *Lysmata grabhami*, a fish cleaning shrimp. Some ahermatypic corals such as *Phyllangia americana mouchezii* and *Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) inornata* are typical of these environments, together with *M. asperula*, which usually grows more branched here. The ascidians *Ciona intestinalis* and *Halocynthia papillosa* are common in these funds, although they are also present in the adjacent

circalitoral funds, as is the case with the Canary lobster (*Scyllarides latus*), the spider crab (*Stenorhynchus lanceolatus*) or the octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*).

Sandbanks permanently covered by shallow seawater

These are sandbars and sandy bottoms submerged permanently, covered or not by meadows of seagrasses and algae, present down to a depth of approximately 40 m (depth that constitutes the lower limit, approximate, of distribution of the marine phanerogam *Halophila decipiens*). The communities present in this bathymetric range are described, although some of them extend their lower distribution limit to almost 70 m.

Sandy bottoms without vegetation

The infauna in these substrates is very poor, conditioned by their mechanical stability; at greater depth correspond a greater stability in the sediment, appearing a characteristic infauna whose abundance depends on the available organic matter that, in general, is scarce. Bivalve molluscs are well represented in the infauna of these funds, with species such as: *Macra stultorum*, *Cardium spp.*, *Venus verrucosa* and *Callista chione*; while the echinoderms include irregular urchins: *Echinocardium cordatum*, *Brissus unicolor* and *Plagiobrissus costai*. Crustaceans are represented by amphipods and copepods, and *Ditrupa arietina* and *Diopatra neapolitana* are common in the group of polychaete annelids. Another polychaete, *Bispira viola*, a suspensivorous feeding tube species, can form dense colonies on this type of substrate. Some species of corals adapted to live in the sediment, the Pennatulaceans, with four species present in the Canary Islands are developed on this type of bottom and the sandy-muddy ones: *Veretillum cynomorium*, *Virgularia mirabilis*, *Pteroeides spinosum* and *Cavernularia pusilla* (Brito and Ocaña, 2004). The starfish *Narcissia canariensis*, the gastropod mollusks *Conus pulcher* and *Semicassis granulata*, the holothurians *Holothuria spp.* and the crab *Cryptosoma cristatum*, capable of burying almost completely, exposing only its pedunculated eyes. Among the invertebrates of nocturnal habits, the starfish *Astropecten aranciacus*, the gastropod *Tonna galea* or the holoturia *Euapta lappa* stand out.

The greatest specific richness and complexity occur in the transition zones with the rocky bottoms and with the phanerogam meadows, where the detritivorous crustaceans (*Paramysis*, *Siriella spp.*, etc.) form large clouds and activate the transfer of organic matter. These organisms are consumed by a wide variety of bottom and pelagic coastal fish.

Community of Heteroconger longissimus

Heteroconger longissimus is a congrid of diurnal habitus, which lives half buried in tubes dug in the sand. With a maximum length of 51 cm, it feeds on plankton and detritus, for which it keeps part of its body out of the sand, facing the dominant currents that give it its food. This eating behavior forces him to be placed in illuminated environments and of constant marine currents.

In the Canary Islands its presence has been registered in all the islands. It is distributed at depths between 10 and 70 m, although its optimum seems to be 45 m (Barquín-Díez et al., 2005). In general, the great densities of this species are located on soft bottoms devoid of vegetation, however

they can be observed by sharing substrate with seagrasses such as *Cymodocea nodosa* or *Halophila decipiens*, with the green algae *Caulerpa prolifera*, or with the pipe polychaete *Bispira viola*, among others, although in these cases they are usually small groups of individuals or even isolated individuals.

Figure 25: The sandy eel *Heteroconger longissimus*

Community of the polychaete *Bispira viola*

Bispira viola is a tubular polychaete of the Sabellidae family that can be found on the soft substrates of the islands, forming colonies that can reach a high density of individuals. It has an amphiantic distribution and is also present in the Mediterranean and the Pacific. In the Canary Islands its presence has been confirmed in the islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma, Gran Canaria and Lanzarote (Martín *et al.*, 2004). They are preferably located in sheltered areas of the dominant currents of the most of the islands (Martín *et al.*, 2004) and according to Barquín - Díez *et al.* (2005), show preference for the fine sands, with which they build their tubes. The breadth and density of these populations make the *Bispira viola* polychaete one of the most important macroinvertebrates of the shallow canary sub-tidal sandy substrate. In Tenerife, the total extension of this species in the studied area was 171 Ha, which represents 2.6% of the available sandy substrate, in a bathymetric range between 20 and 67 m, although it is very possible that it is higher depth.

The cobble infralitoral communities

Being submerged areas, the greater stability of the substrate allows the settlement of algae and the callaos have a stable vegetation cover, dominated by several species of red algae such as *Corallina elongata*, *Halopithys incurva*, *Asparagopsis spp.* and others from the *Liagoraceae* family, as well as the brown algae *Halopteris scoparia*, *Sporochnus pedunculatus* and *Sargassum spp.*, which provide shelter for a more varied fauna (Haroun et al., 2003). In the fauna of this type of bottom, the mollusks that adhere to the stones, such as the black lapa (*Patella candei crenata*), the *Haliotis tuberculata coccinea* or the canary chiton *Chiton (Rhyssoplax) canariensis*, which feed on algae. Other mollusks, such as *Aplysia dactylomela* and *Umbraculum umbraculum*, the *Chromodoris purpurea* nudibranch, or the *Luria lurida* also live in the sublitoral stony. The stable stones have a rich scyaphilic fauna on their underside, represented by sponges such as *Clathrina coriacea*, worms such as *Eurythoe complanata*, species of echinoderms such as comatulas (*Antedon bifida*), ofiuras (*Ophioderma longicauda*) or the captain star (*Asterina gibbosa*) that lives adhered to the underside of the stones. The *Xantho poressa* and *Porcellana platycheles* crabs (in very shallow stony) and other species of crustaceans such as the *Gnathophyllum elegans* shrimp or the galateas (*Galathea sp.*) Also take refuge under the stable stones of this type of bottom. In shallow areas, the fish called bloodsucker (*Lepadogaster lepadogaster*), which adheres to the substrate by means of the suction cup in which its pelvic fins have been transformed, also seeks refuge under the cobble.

Community of the marine phanerogam Cymodocea nodosa. Sebadales

Cymodocea nodosa is a marine plant that has a very characteristic morphology, with long leaves in the form of ribbons, which appear in groups along a rhizomatous stem (usually buried in the sand), from which they arise some short roots. In the Canary Islands, the prairies of this phanerogam are called sebadales, and constitute the dominant plant community of the shallow soft bottoms. Most sebadales are located on the east and south coasts of the islands, always in sheltered areas, protected from trade winds, at depths ranging between 2 and 35 m. They are more abundant in the eastern and central islands, being the oldest and eroded, with a submerged island platform of greater dimensions and greater amount of sediments (Brito, 1984; Haroun et al., 2003).

According to Espino et al. (2008), between 5 and 10 m deep, the sebadales show a distribution in patches; below that range the grasslands acquire a continuous aspect, with coverage close to 100%. In general, the most structured meadows, with greater density and coverage, are located in bays or coves more sheltered, protected from waves and currents. In more exposed areas, the prairies are more irregular and lax. As the depth increases, the meadow becomes more lax and *C. nodosa* is gradually replaced by the green algae *Caulerpa prolifera* and *C. racemosa*, with a transition zone, at varying depths, between these species. The bathymetric distribution of the *Caulerpa* species exceeds that of the phanerogam, since it can reach more than 50 m deep.

The sebadales present their own fauna, adapted both in their morphology and in their coloration, predominantly elongated or tapered shapes, as well as greenish or brown tones (imitating live or dead sebas, respectively), as a way to camouflage. Among the crustaceans, the decapods of the *Hippolytidae* family stand out, while among the mollusks it is worth mentioning *Oxynoe olivacea*, a small greenish-colored opisthobranch. It constitutes an ecosystem of enormous ecological importance for various reasons, among which its high productivity stands out, with annual average

values of primary productivity of 665 g ps m⁻² (Espino et al., 2008), which is also an important source of matter organic detrital for the next funds, product of the annual detachment of foliar biomass (Aguilera - Klink et al., 1994).

Community of the marine fanerogam Halophila decipiens

Halophila decipiens is a marine phanerogam of the *Hydrocharitaceae* family, characterized by its small size (up to 3 cm high) and its opposite bright green leaves, which reach between 1 and 2.5 cm in length and 3 to 6 mm Wide. Worldwide it has a pantropical distribution, and its presence is recorded in all the islands of the archipelago, with the exception of Lanzarote and Fuerteventura, at depths between 12 and 40 m (Haroun et al., 2003) on substrates with a slope less than 14 °. After *Cymodocea nodosa*, it is the second most abundant marine phanerogam in the Canary Islands.

Their populations are distributed on sandy and sandy-muddy bottoms by way of small spots or patches. These spots can be monospecific or share substrate with green algae such as *Caulerpa prolifera*, *C. racemosa* var. *cylindracea* (considered as invasive algae) or brown seaweed *Dictyota dichotoma*. It can also share a substrate with the sebadales, sometimes intercalating with each other, although it is usual for *H. decipiens* to be below the lower limit of these.

Community of Caulerpa prolifera

Caulerpa prolifera is green algae of the *Caulerpacae* family. Globally it is distributed by the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea; in the Canary Islands it is present in the soft bottoms of all the islands and islets. It grows in sandy, muddy or mixed bottoms, at depths of approximately 10 m and up to a maximum variable to 50-60 m. It can coexist with representatives of other typical sandy bottom communities such as the *Cymodocea nodosa* seagrasses, *Halophila decipiens*, the *Heteroconger longissimus* and the polychaete *Bispira viola*.

Like the other plant formations that develop on sandy substrates, the prairies of *C. prolifera* contribute to retain and stabilize the sediment and organic matter, reducing the turbidity of the water. However, very dense communities produce an excess of organic matter in the substrate that could result in the appearance of anoxic conditions.

▪ Circalitoral Communities

The Canarian waters, below 40 m deep, are characterized by low light intensity, with populations mainly of sciaphylic species. Macroscopic algae do not normally exceed 100 m deep and are usually corallinaceous (calcareous red algae) that can grow free, embedded or forming concretions. In this area there is a great diversity of coral communities. As the most genuine representative is the one known as "biocenosis of *Dendrophyllia ramea*".

Between 80 and 150 m deep, the island platforms extend; the lower limit of the circalitoral zone is located within this bathymetric belt, where banks of the orange madreporary, *D. ramea*, are located, which supports a rich and complex community of benthic invertebrates. The skeletal body structure of this species creates a large stable substrate surface, which is only altered by intense

invasions of terrine sediment. In addition, the moderate hydrodynamics and the large number of microenvironments provided by the skeleton favor the high diversity observed in these funds (Aristegui et al., 1987). The base substrate of this biocenosis is the coral itself, along with the skeletal axes of other dead corals such as *Ellisella paraplexauroides* and *Antipathes wollastoni*. Aggregates of the bivalve *Neopycnodonte cochlear* originate a secondary substrate with many microenvironments, which serve as space shelters for uncompetitive species.

The dead branches of the *D. ramea* coral are colonized by numerous sessile invertebrates such as sponges, gorgonians, hydroids, bryozoans, bivalves or brachiopods, as well as encrusting calcareous algae and other corals. The most notable species of sessile invertebrates are the foraminifer *Homotrema rubra*, sponges *Axinella damicornis*, *A. polypoides* and *Hexadella racovitzai*, the gorgonians *Ellisella paraplexauroides*, *Leptogorgia ruberrima* and *Paramuricea grayi*, the antipatarians *Stichopathes gracilis*, the corals, *Madracis pharensis* and *Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) inornata*, the hydroids *Aglaophenia quill*, the bivalves *Neopycnodonte cochlear* and *Chama gryphoides*, the bryozoans *Escharina porosa* and *Reteporella couchii*, the pennatuláceos *Veretillum cynomorium*, *Paralcyonium spinosum*, *Pennatula acleataunca pus*, *Cavernulaliaia triadioca*, *Cavernula triapodata*. Sedentary invertebrates include the ophiuroid *Astrospartus mediterraneus*.

Maërl community

Generically “maërl” is a term applied to several species of non-articulated coral red algae (family Corallinaceae) that live free. They can form extensive mantles, mostly on coarse gravel or sand bottoms or mixed with muddy substrates, both on open coasts and channels intertidal or in protected areas of fjords with gentle currents. Since the maërl requires light to perform photosynthesis, the depth at which they live is a function of the turbidity of the water, from shallow coasts to more than 40 m deep. The bottoms of maërl are composed of live algae, dead algae, or a mixture of both in different proportions. It constitutes one of the most productive and most diverse ecosystems in temperate regions. In the Canary Islands, maërl funds present as dominant species *Lithothamnion corallioides* and *Phymatolithon calcareum*. These free calcareous talos can accumulate, constituting this type of funds, widely distributed throughout the seas and which in the Canary Islands also receive the denomination of “confection” or “anise” funds. According to Falcón and Carrillo (2005) they are located in the deepest area of the infralitoral, and although shallower spots can be found, their greatest development occurs from 40-50 m (40-60 m according to Brito and Ocaña, 2004), being able to occupy wide extensions to greater depths.

Due to the rhodolite's anfractuous shape, the maërl bottoms can house an important variety of organisms, either offering shelter to small invertebrates or as a support or substrate, both from algae and sessile invertebrates. Barquin et al. (2005), they find that the zoantide *Palythoa grandis* sits on the rhodoliths of the maërl bottoms, while Brito and Ocaña (2004) describe large settlements of the antipatario *Stichopathes setacea* installed on them, as well as the solitary mothers *Caryophyllia smithii* and *Paracyathus pulchellus* or small branches of *Madracis asperula* and *Cladocora debilis*, which they consider as frequent. For algae, Falcón and Carrillo. (2005), find that the rhodoliths constitute the support of red and brown algae, some of extraordinary arbuscular bearing, of genera such as *Sporochnus*, *Nereia*, *Cottoniella*, *Lophocladia*, *Sargassum*, *Halopteris* and *Hypnea*, among

others.

In the circalitoral, sandy-muddy, muddy and detritic substrates abound, the latter composed of dead calcareous algae, coral remains and shells, often intercross with terrigenous sediments.

Batial and Abyssal Communities

From 150-200 m deep, the batial zone begins which corresponds to the island's slope. The coral community mentioned above is being modified and impoverished. The characteristic coral of the previous zone, *Dendrophyllia ramea*, is replaced by another species of the same genus, *D. cornigera*, which has a smaller bearing and an intense yellow color, forming what is known as "biocenosis of *Dendrophyllia cornigera*".

Among the corals characteristic of these funds are: *C. cyathus*, *Eguchipsammia gaditana*, *Anomocora fecunda*, *Siphonogorgia sp.*, *Acanthogorgia hirsuta*, *Placogorgia sp.*, *Callogorgia verticillata* and *Leiopathes glaberrima*. The gorgonia *Isidella elongata* also appears in these bottoms.

In those batial areas where the rocky substrate appears discovered, it is colonized by characteristic solitary corals such as *Sphenotrochus andrewianus* and *Anocomora prolifera*, and species of the genus *Deltocyathus*. Also present are gorgonians *Isidella elongata*, *Viminella flagellum* and vitreous sponges (hexactinélides) (Brito and Ocaña, 2004).

This species composition extends to the lower limit of the batial zone, between 400-500 m deep, being in turn gradually replaced by a "white corals biocenosis". In these deep batial bottoms over 500 m soft substrates predominate as a result of the finer sedimentation processes. On the other hand, in these soft bottoms of the middle part of the insular slope of the islands, with sandy-muddy substrates above all, in addition to the aforementioned species, other detritivorous species such as regular hurchin *Coelopleurus sp.*, *Centrostephanus sp.* or *Cidaris sp.*, are very abundant in numerous areas.

Up to 800 m deep, the aforementioned "White-corals Biocenosis" is distributed, consisting of dead and associated colonies of *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*. These bioconstructor white corals have a high diversity of associated organisms such as gorgonians of the genera *Placogorgia* and *Acanthogorgia*, the antipatario *Leiopathes glaberrima* or the *Phakellia ventilabrum* sponge. In addition, it is believed that these funds present an important presence of the species of deep distribution of the genus *Corallium* (Brito and Ocaña, 2004).

In these bottoms of the slope of the islands, diverse species of crustaceans are present and some of them with abundant populations, highlighting the shrimp (*Plesionika edwardsii* and *Heterocarpus ensifer*), the carabinero (*Aristaeopsis edwardsiana*), the royal crab (*Chaceon affinis*), the Deep spider crab (*Maja goltziana*) and long-legged crab *Paromola cuvieri*.

3.3 HUMAN ASSETS

3.3.1 Fishery

Professional fishing in the Canary Islands is artisanal, multi-purpose and multi-specific, since most of the boats are small (less than or equal to 15 meters in total length) and use various fishing gear for various fishing species; However, there are also larger vessels, whose target species are, among others, large tunas. Marine recreational fishing is carried out for entertainment, sport or hobby and not for profit; It can be carried out from land, from boat or underwater. To carry out these activities, fishermen must hold the corresponding recreational sea fishing license.

Shellfish is a complementary activity of fishing. The professional is the extraction with habitual character and profit, of echinoderms, molluscs and crustaceans from the marine environment with specific and selective gears for their exercise and can be done from boats or on foot, from the shore. To get these activities to be sustainable, protection and regeneration measures of marine resources are of main importance: there are currently three Marine Reserves of Fishing Interest in the Archipelago: Lanzarote, El Hierro and La Palma. Other measures to protect the seagrass beds exist, specifically for the sebadales (*Cymodocea turf*) and the areas with artificial reefs.

Figure 26: Map of Marine Reserves in Canary Islands

The FEMP funds 2014-2020 and POSEI (Program of Specific Options for Remoteness and Insularity, destined for the outermost areas of the Union European) are intended to help fishermen in the transition to sustainable fishing, help coastal communities to diversify their economies and finance projects to create jobs and improve the quality of life on the European coasts.

In the Canary Islands, fishing can be developed by professional and recreational fishers, although professionals can sell their catch and not recreational. As for the professionals, there are 25 Cofradías de Pescadores - non-profit associations - that have generic areas assigned, although this assignment does not imply any right over the resources, but the possibility of being considered actors to the time to make inquiries about processes or projects that can be carried out in those places. There are also Fishermen's Cooperatives - for profit - but they do not have this zone allocation. As for the special restrictions on fishing activity, the three marine reserves of fishing

interest have different use regimes and non-fishing areas. In addition, there are 6 locations that contain artificial reefs (in some cases with restrictions on fishing) and 18 aquaculture concessions in operation where fishing is not allowed. There are other types of locations, such as port enclosures, bathing areas, etc., where fishing activity is also restricted. It emphasizes that the Special Conservation Zones (ZEC) do not include any measure in terms of quantities, species, or effort.

The regulations develop the uses on the types or gear allowed (around 20 types) at a high level of detail in terms of islands, areas, depths, times, months (including weekends and holidays), in addition to differences in the characteristics of the mesh light of some gears aimed at a species at one time (in some cases). It is also important to consider the development of specific fisheries management plans that are carried out (eg in El Hierro and Fuerteventura), which entail particular modifications in each case. On the other hand, recreational fishing does not have any spatial restrictions, with the exceptions described above and the exception of the underwater fishing modality that does have its own areas. As for shellfish, there are areas with spatial and temporal closures that consider several species and even, in some cases, the conditions change when specific plans are developed.

Professional Fishing

The fleet is the set of vessels that are used to capture the different target species. According to the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment (MAPAMA), and on the basis of the Operational Fishing Fleet Census as of December 31, 2016, 748 vessels (95.16% of the fleet based in the Canary Islands) operate in the Caladero Canario. 94% fish with “minor gear” (hook, gill, fence, traps, etc.) and 6% with “longline” (tuna fishing vessels, bottom longline and surface longline). In any case, if the base port is considered by Autonomous Community (for the Canary Islands) of the Census, we have 786 ships. This figure represents a reduction of 30.44% in the last 10 years.

Figure 27: Number of fishing licences per year (Data source from Canary Government)

The average length of the Canarian ships is 9.92 m (10.87 m is the national average) and the largest fraction of the fleet (77%) is less than 10 m in length, for a 66% in the whole of Spain. Finally, on average, the age of Canarian vessels is 38 years, the highest nationally (31 years). In addition, 48% are 40 years or older by 29% for all of Spain.

Figure 28: Percentage of overall fishing boat length (Data source: from Canary Government)

On the other hand, according to data from the Government of the Canary Islands, compiled through the First Sale (PV) system (this came into operation in 2006) of fresh fish, between 2006 and 2016 the trend of catches by weight is increasing. It is important to note that the PV system was not fully implemented in all ports until approximately 2008. The dispersion of the analyzed average data gives an idea of the high variability of the catches, so it is necessary to take these results with great caution for the purpose. Predictive as for the data of the value in euros, they do not indicate the real value of the catches since the PV system does not imply in any case any economic transaction, since it is primarily a traceability tool for the catches rather than the economic value of the same. That is, the value in euros indicated in the PV is a mere approximation.

Figure 29: Value of landed fish by year (Data source: from Canary Government)

On an island scale, the contribution to the capture by weight on average between 2009 and 2016 (excluding the first three years of data, since the PV system was in its infancy) by the Canary fleet is due, more at a minor, on the island of Tenerife (54.12%), Gran Canaria (20.13%), Lanzarote (15.19%), Fuerteventura (5.65%), La Palma (3.29%), El Hierro (1.25%) and La Gomera (0.37%). The greatest contribution to the weight and value of the catches is due to pelagic fish (oceanic and coastal), although the profitability is greater in demersal. On the other hand, the demersal group does not show clear upward trends in catches. On an island scale, by biological group, the greatest contribution of pelagic fish in Tenerife and Lanzarote stands out, while in the rest of the islands the contribution of demersal fish is significant.

Figure 30: Weight of landed fish by biological group, data from Canary Government

As for the catch values at the island level, they must be taken with some caution because the ships, although they are attached to an island on a documentary level, can develop their fishing activity in the surroundings of other islands or in more oceanic waters or even on the African coast. On the other hand, the PV system, as indicated above, owes its initial design to a traceability purpose rather than fisheries management. However, its potential as a tool for analysis and decision making is enormous as it includes daily catch data, in weight per species, for each ship that makes its landing in the Canary Islands. In addition, since 2015 vessels are obliged to indicate by which fishing system they have made the catch in each case, which indicates a certain progress in granting this information gathering system the importance that it could have for fisheries management in the Canary Islands. (Boza, 2015; Pérez-González *et al.*, 2017). Of course, this system has a lot of room for improvement in the quality of the information, and that should be addressed as soon as possible to increase the validity of the data obtained (Boza, 2015).

On the other hand, statistics on catches landed in the Canary Islands and their have to be considered with great caution, since the state in which the fishery resources of the Canary Islands are found is characterized above all Because of its high uncertainty. Thus, according to González (2008) the pelagic coastal resources (mackerel, sardine, etc.) its abundance and state of exploitation is unknown, while the oceanic pelagics (bigeye, yellowfin, beetle, etc.) are evaluated internationally and the Relevant species for the Canarian economy are at a maximum level of exploitation of their populations. As for the demersal and coastal shellfish resources, they indicate that they are in a state of overexploitation, so it is necessary to adopt measures for their recovery. And in regards to deepwater resources they need to be evaluated, although in some cases, already studied, they may present alternatives or complements to the currently exploited resources.

Recreational fishing

According to the website of the Government of the Canary Islands “marine recreational fishing is that which is carried out for entertainment, sport or hobby, not for profit, and its captures cannot be the object of sale or transaction (...) its exercise requires being in possession of the corresponding license, which is an administrative document of a personal and non-transferable nature, which enables its holder to exercise this activity”.

There are 3 types of licenses with different modalities:

- 1st Class: it is the one that authorizes the practice of recreational fishing from a boat, using the surface trolling. In addition, for the exercise of collective recreational fishing carried out from vessels dedicated to this activity on a business basis (boats of sixth list), the first class collective license will be necessary and is inherent to the vessel.
- 2nd Class: enables the practice of underwater recreational fishing and shellfish.
- 3rd Class: authorizes the practice of marine recreational surface fishing, carried out from land or from a boat without using the surface trolling. It also enables shellfish collection.

The available data on licenses of the Government of the Canary Islands indicate licenses issued per person. But a person can have one, two or all three modalities of licenses. In general, there is a more or less constant trend in the issuance of licenses in recent years.

In any case, the number of licenses issued, together with the validity of 3 years, shows the enormous fishing power of this sector with 101,434 licenses in force (in 2016, considering the sum of those issued in 2014, 2015 and 2016). On an island scale, the capital islands (Tenerife and Gran Canaria) cover 70.66% of the licenses in force in 2016, which is clearly related to the population. Thus, 7.30% (SD. 4.03%) of the population in the Canary Islands has at least one license for one type of recreational fishing (10.1% of those people are licensed for two or three modalities). It also highlights the prevalence of type 3a licenses, as it is the most easily developed by the population. Finally, the group of “non-residents”, although it is the least numerous, is the one with the highest growth in the last 9 years with an annual average of 13.66% (SD. 27.45%), considering the annual variations in current licenses (total average - 0.86%; SD. 6.0).

On the other hand, and in relation to the impact of recreational fishing on the fishery resources of the Archipelago and the economy, Jiménez-Alvarado (2015) estimated that in 2010 recreational fishermen obtained 47.3% of the total catch landed in the Islands, while the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPyA), in 2005, estimated a total expenditure of 117 million euros per year for this fishing modality in the Canary Islands, which provides an idea of economic relevance of this activity.

The fishing effort could be understood as the material and economic resources, which in turn imply an expenditure of energy and time, to obtain the catch (Guerra-Sierra and Sánchez-Lizaso, 1998). On the other hand, the fishing regulations (European and National) regulate the Satellite Fishing Tracking System through the use of the Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS), or “blue boxes”. Spanish fishing vessels with a length ≥ 12 m will have a satellite-tracking device installed on board. Although they may exempt from carrying this equipment the ships of their flag,

whose length is <15 m if: (i) they fish exclusively in the territorial waters of the flag member state, or (ii) they never spend more than 24 hours at sea.

In the Canary Islands, estimating the effort requires applying measures that fill the information gaps according to the different fleets that fish in this fishing ground. However, knowing aspects related to fishing effort, such as the time allocated (according to gear) and its spatial location requires measures to be implemented in some of these fleets. In this sense, the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) has provided a lot of initial information (MAPAMA, 2017) that traces the direction where research is going to be directed in this field.

Thus, in the following paragraphs the most interesting of this initiative is extracted for the purposes of the objectives of the OEM. The IEO intends to obtain the spatial distribution and time series of the fishing effort by fishing system (métier), exerted by both professional and recreational activities and both on boats and on foot. As for the professional fishing activity with VMS, it will also be carried out together with other monitoring programs in order to obtain all the variables associated with the catch and effort. In addition, the Maritime Navigation Monitoring Program (AIS) that will provide a significant improvement in signal frequency will complement it. For the professional fishing activity without VMS, they are assessing the implementation of a validated Fishing Unit Location System (SLUP).

Figure 31: Geographic distribution of of fishing effort by gear: bottom lines (MAPAMA, 2017)

Figure 32: Geographic distribution of of fishing effort by gear: hand lines (MAPAMA, 2017)

Figure 33: Geographic distribution of of fishing effort by gear: purse seine nets (MAPAMA, 2017)

Any particular interaction is expected between BGF and the local fishing fleet.

3.3.2 Aquaculture

In terms of production, the Canary Islands in 2013 were the third Spanish producer of gilthead seabream after Valencia (41%) and Murcia (22%), contributing 18% of the production of this species. In relation to sea bass, the Canary Islands stood in 2013 as the second national producer of this species, accounting for 29%, after Murcia (34%). Aquaculture production in the Canary Islands almost reaches 6,000 tons in this year: more than 3,600 tons of sea bass, about 2,300 of gilthead seabream and 33 of sole. The value of first sale was around 27.8 million euros.

Table 8: Aquaculture production in the Canary Islands

Canary	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Seabream	3.983	3.605	2.664	2.524	2.526	2.311
Seabass	2.930	4.795	3.219	4.125	3.592	3.645
Sole	0	0	0	29	26	33
Total	6.913	8.400	5.883	6.678	6.144	5.989

Table 9: Aquaculture production in the Islands

Island	Seabream		Seabass		Sole		Total	
	2012	2013	2012	2013	2012	2013	2012	2013
Gran Canaria	1.431	263	11.964	12.676	271	323	13.666	13.262
Tenerife	1.734	1.770	3.839	1.819	-	-	5.573	3.589
La Palma	620	0	3.929	4.923	-	-	4.549	4.923
Lanzarote	5.063	6.048	0	0	-	-	5.063	6.048
Total Canary	8.848	8.081	19.733	19.004	271	323	28.851	27.822

Figure 34: Share of aquaculture production; top: sea bass; down: sea bream (Source: PEACAN 2010-2014)

The last crisis of the sector has caused that in 2013 only 18 of the 32 aquaculture facilities with a current administrative concession were in operation; seven of them on the island of Tenerife, six in Gran Canaria, one in La Palma and one in Lanzarote.

It also highlights the existence of a series of concessions pending, pending completion of the granting procedure; 2 on the island of Gran Canaria (4,000 T) and 3 on Tenerife (2,400 T). The increase in the productive capacity in the islands can reach 6,400 T, if they end up installing all the concessions that are currently in process.

Table 10: Company in operation on 2014

Titular/ Solicitante	Término municipal	Capacidad produc. anual autoriz / solicit.(dorada y lubina)	Situación en 2014
Lanzarote			
Yaizatún, S.A.	Yaiza	1.856 (*)	Operativa
Insular de Cefalópodos, S.L.	Yaiza	48 tons. de pulpo	-
Gran Canaria			
Alevines y Doradas, S.A.(ADSA-Castillo)	S. Bart. de Tirajana	615	Operativa
Alevines y Doradas, S.A. (ADSA-Melenara)	Telde	650	Operativa
Canarias de Explotaciones Marinas, S.L. (CANEXMAR, S.L.)	Telde	340	Operativa
Productos de Crianza, S.L. (PROCRIA, S.L.)	S. Bart.de Tirajana	1.800	Operativa
Granja Marina Playa de Vargas, S.L.	S. Bart. de Tirajana	2.000	Operativa
Granja Marina Playa de Vargas 2001, S.L.	Agüimes	500	-
Inter Aqua S.L.	S. Bart. de Tirajana	2.800	Operativa
Tenerife			
Cultivos Marinos Teide, S.L.	Arona	160	Operativa
Efficient System Service, S.L.	Arona	125	-
Socat Canarias, S.L.	Arona	125	Operativa
Industrias Acuícolas de Canarias, S.L. (Inac)	Arona	125	Operativa
Cabo Pez, S.L.	Arona	125	Operativa
Punta Rasca, Cultivos Marinos de Canarias, S.L.	Arona	125	-
Cultivos Marinos Atlántico, S.L.	Candelaria	125	-
Punta Rasca Cultivos Marinos de Canarias, S.A.	Adeje	350	Operativa
Efficient System Service, S.L.	Adeje	350	Operativa
Marcultivos, S.L.	Adeje	125	-
Pérez Cortés, S.L.	Adeje	125	-
Cabo Pez, S.L.	Adeje	175	Operativa
Exmarcan, S.L.	Adeje	125	-
Tingoe Canarias, S.L.	Adeje	125	-
Océano San Juan, S.L.U.	Adeje	125	-
La Palma			
Acuipalma, S.L.	Tijarafe	1.000	Operativa

Below is a table with the employment data generated by the aquaculture sector in the Canary Islands in 2012:

Table 11: Employment data by the aquaculture sector

Region	Total	
	N° UTA	N° Persons
Canary Islands	158	199

Finally, aquaculture has produced a high positive impact in the field of research, not only for the employment generated in the numerous projects that have been undertaken in this area in the islands, but also for the valuable scientific production and technological obtained.

As mentioned in the analysis of the evolution of the sector, one of the consequences of the crisis was the business organization, so a large part of the companies organized to market their products in common. With this objective, two commercial groups were initially created: DYLCAN, in 2002, and ACUIMARCA in 2004. In 2007, PEMARCA was created, a group in which several of the companies that until then marketed through the other two were integrated. Only the companies Yaizatún (Lanzarote) and Acuipalma, which left PEMARCA in October 2011, are responsible for marketing their production, while the companies Efficient System Service, S.L. and Punta Rasca C.M. S.L. sold through the company Mesocosmos Canarias.

Table 12: Commercial groupment of aquaculture companies

DYCLAN	PEMARCA
- ADSA - PROCRÍA	- Canexmar, S.L. - Cabo Pez, S.L. - C.M. Teide - Industrias Acuícolas Canarias, S.L. - SOCAT Canarias, S.L. - G.M. Playa de Vargas

DYLCAN: It has a packaging ship in the south of Gran Canaria, which involved an investment of just over five million euros. It has 22 workers and in 2012 it only had two-associated production companies; ADSA and PROCRÍA.

ACUIMARCA: It has two warehouses in the Granadilla estate, dedicated to the packaging, transformation and commercialization of sea bream and sea bass, with an investment of about six million euros. It reached a workforce of 16 employees, but ceased its activity in 2011 because all its associated companies ceased production.

PEMARCA: It began operating in 2008, with two small packaging ships (Tenerife and Gran Canaria) and an average workforce of 6 workers.

In spite of the attempts to increase the added value of the product by means of the “embandejado”, eviscerado, fileado, etc., in the Canary Islands the gilthead seabass and the seabass

are still commercialized without any previous transformation, which is explained in large part by the maximum prices imposed by retail distributors.

POSEICAN: Regulation 1911/91 (OJ No L 171) included the Canarian Archipelago in Common Policies, including the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), matching its conditions to those of the rest of Spain, with the following exceptions:

- 1) In the application of the Common Agricultural Policy and the CFP, the specific characteristics of the Canarian productions would be taken into account.
- 2) A Specific Supply Regime was created for agricultural products.
- 3) The islands were outside the VAT application.
- 4) A transitional period was established in which an Arbitration on Production would be applied and importation of merchandise with exemptions for certain local productions.
- 5) Gradual application of the common customs tariff.

One of the measures proposed to take into account the peculiarities of certain local productions was the approval of a Program of Specific Options for the Remoteness and Insularity of the Canary Islands, POSEICAN, which was approved by Commission Decision 91/314 / EEC, which introduced a set of measures aimed at alleviating the effects of the extra costs derived from the commercialization, due to the remoteness and insularity of territories such as the Canary Islands, allowing the products of these regions to access the continental markets on equal terms, in relation to those from the rest of the European Union.

In the case of the fisheries and aquaculture sector, it is compensating the cost overruns driven by the status of the outermost region in the marketing of fishery and aquaculture products, through the granting of Community aid to the sector.

The first program (1992-1993) covered the production of tuna and small pelagics and in 1996 cephalopods were incorporated. In 1998 the aquaculture products (sea bream and sea bass) were included in the list of species benefiting from these grants.

In its beginnings, POSEICAN directly supported the producing companies, but in 2004 only the production exported outside the Canary Islands was subsidized, becoming the commercializing companies the direct beneficiaries of the compensations. This fact caused an imbalance in the economic forecasts of the producing companies, leaving without support the extra cost derived from the production in the Canary Islands (imports of feed, fry, materials, etc.).

The approved sites

Following the approval of the Plan of Region Ordination of Aquaculture (PROAC), a number of sites were classified on the Island of Gran Canaria.

The following code has been adopted:

- ZPA, in red in maps: Sites forbidden to aquaculture installation;
- ZIA, in green in maps: Sites allowed for aquaculture installation.
- ZAA, in yellow in maps: Sites adapt for aquaculture.

The following excluding factors has been considered:

- Proximity to seagrass meadows (buffer 100m)
- Rocky bottoms
- Protected areas
- Presence of protected species
- Proximity to turistic areas or beaches
- Areas shallower than 50 m where no informations on seabottom communities available.

Areas have been selected within the isobaths from -20 to -60 m, while no mention has been made of offshore areas. Each area is granted for a maximum level of production, also taking in account the existing farms.

For each selected area, some actions of correction of aquaculture exploitation effect on the environment and on other sea uses are established.

BGF platform selected site remains further offshore any coastal aquaculture site, and no interctions are expected.

Figure 35: Aquaculture zoning (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 36: Aquaculture zoning, detail. Red areas: aquaculture development forbidden. Green areas: areas of interest for aquaculture; orange: existing farms (Source: Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 37: Bathymetry of Arinaga offshore area, detail (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

3.3.3 Oil and Gas

Nine offshore blocks have been recently opened to hydrocarbon exploration. They are located along the east coast of Tenerife and Fuerteventura, within the Spanish EEZ. Licences are in hands of RWE Dea, Repsol and Woodside. Minimal distance of the nearest block from BGF site exceeds 200 km; therefore, no direct or indirect influence is expected.

Figure 38: Exploration blocks, locations

Figure 39: Exploration blocks, details of activities

3.3.4 Wind farms

Figure 40: Map of wind average speed, Gran Canaria (Source: Sistema de Información Territorial de Canarias)

Figure 41: Position of onshore wind farm, Gran Canaria (Source: *Sistema de Informacion Territorial de Canarias*)

Canary Islands are rated for an average wind speed of 6-8 m/s, for a total range of 3000-4500 eq.hrs. Off shore wind power density is estimated as greater than 700 W/m² off shore Arinaga, (see D2.2)

A huge number of onshore wind turbine exist on Gran Canaria, and a huge number increase is expected in the next few years.

EQUINOR has recently been granted for a 200MW floating wind farm, to be installed within 2024 in the offshore of Gran Canaria.

No exclusive areas for offshore wind farm has been established so far, with except of the PLOCAN test area.

No interactions are expected at this stage.

Figure 42: The PLOCAN test area

3.3.5 Cultural heritage

The area facing the BGF platform hosts, along the coast, the remains of a pre-hispanic village (Juncalillo del Sur).

In the vicinity, the remains of a fortified villa, dating the 17^o-18 century (Castillo del Romeral – Playa de La Caleta) a defence structure born for safeguarding the near salt extractory industry. The remains are located between -3 and -10 m.

The buffer area does not intersect the BGF area.

3.3.6 Landscape

Maps on landscape features of the East area of Gran Canaria are not yet available; this baseline information will be postponed.

3.3.7 Maritime traffic

On December 2006, the measures associated with the declaration of the Canary Islands as a Specially Sensitive Maritime Zone (ZMES) by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) entered into force.

The purpose of declaring the Canary Islands, as ZMES is to protect them since their environment may be damaged as a result of maritime activities. This statement has three associated measures for traffic regulation and Maritime and marine ecosystem protection:

1. Two navigation routes or Traffic Separation Devices (DST) between Gran Canaria and Tenerife, and between Gran Canaria and Fuerteventura.
2. Mandatory notification for ships of dangerous goods.
3. The establishment of five areas or areas to avoid for vessels transiting the ZMES (allowed under certain conditions for inter-island traffic and artisanal fishing).

As regards the exclusion zones to maritime traffic, to avoid risks of pollution and damage to the environment in especially sensitive marine areas, all tankers and gross tonnage vessels exceeding 500 GT that carry hydrocarbon or dangerous cargoes should avoid five areas, of which three are World Biosphere Reserves and the other two are established as especially sensitive by the breeding of cetaceans: at the height of the island of Tenerife, the area delimited by the meridian of longitude 17 ° 22 'W and the southern coast of the island and the parallels of latitude 28 ° 0' N and 28 ° 21 'N, and at the height of the island of Gran Canaria, the area delimited by the meridian of longitude 16 ° 0 'W and the coast and latitude parallels 27 ° 44' N and 28 ° 0 'N.

No interaction between maritime traffic and the BGF platform is expected.

CHAPTER 4: PROJECT DESIGN FRAMEWORK

See D4.1.1 – France for more details on platform's arrangements.

CHAPTER 5: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

5.1 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

5.1.1. Impact on birds

Seabirds

At the aim of gather information on the presence and permanence of the seabird potentially affected by the BGF installation, the surrounding sites have been investigated.

Due to the high vagrantive nature of some species (*Calonectris*, *Puffinus*, *Morus*), the sites considered have been extended to the whole Canary archipelagus.

The following Natura 2000 Sites has been particularly investigated:

- **ES0000039 - Jandía**
- **ES0000040 - Islotes del norte de Lanzarote y Famara**
- **ES0000099 - Los Ajaches**
- **ES0000100 - La Geria**
- **ES0000103 - El Hierro**
- **ES0000104 - Gorreta y Salmor**
- **ES0000106 - Teno**
- **ES0000109 - Anaga**
- **ES0000112 - Juncalillo del Sur**
- **ES0000114 - Cumbres y acantilados del norte de La Palma**
- **ES0000338 - Acantilado de Las Traviesas**
- **ES0000344 - Roque de la Playa**
- **ES0000345 - Rasca y Guaza**
- **ES0000346 - Tamadaba**
- **ES0000350 - Llanos de La Corona y Tegala Grande**
- **ES0000351 - Llanos de La Mareta y cantil del Rubicón**
- **ES0000523 - Espacio marino de la zona occidental de El Hierro**
- **ES0000524 - Espacio marino de los Roques de Salmor**
- **ES0000525 - Espacio marino del norte de La Palma**
- **ES0000526 - Espacio marino de La Gomera-Teno**
- **ES0000527 - Espacio marino de los acantilados de Santo Domingo y Roque de Garachico**
- **ES0000528 - Espacio marino del Roque de la Playa**
- **ES0000529 - Espacio marino de Anaga**
- **ES0000530 - Espacio marino de Mogán-La Aldea**
- **ES0000532 - Espacio marino de los Islotes de La**
- **ES0000535 - ZEPA Banco de la Concepción**
- **ES7010016 - Área marina de La Isleta**
- **ES7010017 - Franja marina de Mogán**
- **ES7010028 - Tufia**
- **ES7010048 - Bahía de Gando**
- **ES7010053 - Playa del Cabrón**
- **ES7011005 - Sebadales de Güigüí**
- **PTZPE0062 - Ilhas Selvagens**

From the above Natura 2000 sites, the number of breeding seabirds or resident seabird has been derived. The Standard Data Form for all the NATURA 2000 sites (both under Bird and Habitat

Directives) have been investigated. Following the same method used for the Marseille site, the number of birds has been related to their own feeding range during breeding, to determine an areal density at sea. At this aim, only the Natura 2000 sites from where the BGF platform can be reached during feeding, has been included.

Figure 43: Habitats Directive sites in the Canary Islands (Source: EEA)

A number of seabird species has been selected for the collision risk assessment, including those which feeding range overlap with the BGF area. Species at very low density (as *Morus bassanus*) or occasional in the area has been excluded.

Table 13: Species include in the collision assessment. CAT: categories of Standard Natura 2000 Form: R: reproducing; P: present; W: wintering. Feeding Range in km. In color, categories of IUCN Red Lists of Spain, EU and Global (LC: Least Concern; VU: Vulnerable; EN: Endangered)

COMMON NAME	SCIENTIFIC NAME	CAT	MAX RANGE	RLS	RLEU	RLGlo
Bulwer's petrel	<i>Bulweria bulwerii</i>	R	>600	LC	LC*	LC
Scopoli's shearwater	<i>Calonectris diomedea</i>	R	330	LC	LC*	LC
European storm-petrel	<i>Hydrobates pelagicus</i>	R	65	LC	LC*	LC
Yellow-legged gull	<i>Larus michahellis</i>	PR	SCV	LC	LC	LC
Band-rumped storm-petrel	<i>Hydrobates castro</i>	R	?	LC	LC*	LC
Leach's Storm-petrel	<i>Oceanodroma Leucorhous</i>	W	poss/Scarce	VU	VU*	VU
White-faced storm-petrel	<i>Pelagodroma marina</i>	R	?	LC	EN*	LC

Little shearwater	<i>Puffinus assimilis</i>	PR	>300	LC	LC*	LC
Common tern	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	PR	30	LC	LC*	LC

Scenario 1 – Wind turbine only

The present collision assessment is concerning the solely presence of the wind turbine, not considering any positive attractivity by a fish farm or a roosting area. Parameters used in setting the CRM (Band, 2012) are displayed in the below table.

Table 14: Seabirds parameters used in setting the CRM (Band, 2012)

Species	Scientific name	Body Length (cm)	Wingspan length (cm)	Flight Distribution 0 - 40 m	Flight speed (m/s)	Density (ind/k ²)	Nocturnal activity %	Flight type
Bulwer's petrel	<i>Bulweria bulwerii</i>	26-29	63-73	<i>Puffinus spp.</i>	10	0.055	50	Gliding
Scopoli's shearwater	<i>Calonectris diomedea</i>	44-52	117-135	<i>Puffinus spp.</i>	14,8	0.673	25	Gliding
Band-rumped storm-petrel	<i>Hydrobates castro</i>	19-21	43-46	<i>Puffinus spp.</i>	10	0.055	50	Gliding
Yellow-legged gull	<i>Larus michahellis</i>	58-68	140-155	<i>L. marinus</i>	12	0.006	50	Flapping
White-faced storm-petrel	<i>Pelagodroma marina</i>	22-28	45-48	<i>Puffinus spp.</i>	10	0.055	50	Gliding
Little shearwater	<i>Puffinus assimilis</i>	25-30	58-67	<i>Puffinus spp.</i>	10	0.0108	25	Gliding

Bulveria bulwerii

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational of wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density birds/km ²	0	0	0	0,055	0,055	0,055	0,055	0,055	0,055	0	0	0	
Proportion at rotor height	1,0%												
Total daylight hours per month	328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323	
Total night hours per month	416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421	
Flux factor	0	0	0	153	161	158	162	160	151	0	0	0	
Avg collision risk for single rotor transit	2,0%												
Collision assuming no avoidance	0,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Collision assuming avoidance rate	95,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
birds per month or year	99,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Calonectris diomedea

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational of wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density	birds/km2	0	0	0	0,673	0,673	0,673	0,673	0,673	0	0	0	
Proportion at rotor height	1,0%												
Total daylight hours per month		328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323
Total night hours per month		416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421
Flux factor		0	0	0	2351	2511	2471	2536	2467	2299	0	0	0
Average collision risk for single rotor transit	2,2%												
Collisions assuming no avoidance	0,0%	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	8
Collisions assuming avoidance rate	95,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
bird/month	99,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Hydrobates castro

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density	birds/km2	0	0	0,06	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,06	0	0	
Proportion at rotor height	1,0%												
Total daylight hours per month		328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323
Total night hours per month		416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421
Flux factor		0	0	129	1898	2027	1994	2047	1991	1856	126	0	0
Avg collision risk for single rotor transit	1,6%												
Collisions assuming no avoidance	0,00%	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	6
Collisions assuming avoidance rate	95,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
birds per month	99,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,50%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Pelagodroma marina

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density	birds/km2	0	0	0	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0	0	0	
Proportion at rotor height	1,0%												
Total daylight hours per month		328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323
Total night hours per month		416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421
Flux factor		0	0	0	2238	2356	2302	2370	2333	2210	0	0	0
Average collision risk for single rotor transit	1,5%												
Collisions assuming no avoidance	0,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collisions assuming avoidance rate	95,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Puffinus assimilis

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density	birds/km2	0	0	0	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0	0	0
Proportion at rotor height	1,0%												
Total daylight hours per month		328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323
Total night hours per month		416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421
Flux factor		0	0	0	25	27	27	27	27	25	0	0	0
Avg collision risk for single rotor transit	2,0%												
Collisions assuming no avoidance	0,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Collisions assuming avoidance rate	95,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
birds per month	99,0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Scenario 2 – Wind turbine + Fish farm

The following collision simulation represent a case where a wind turbine is adjacent o a fish farm that extert a positive attraction to seabirds. The species likely to be affected is *Larus michaellis*, which density is very low in Canary, being present with 2000 individuals in La Gomera. Resulting density has been increased on a five-fold basis to account for fish farm/platform positive attraction, following Buschmann at *al.* (2006).

Sterna hirundo is present in canary with a very low number of individuals; therefore, its density at sea and the resulting collision risk are negligible.

Larus michaellis

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	year avg
Proportion of time operational wind turbine	92%	82%	79%	88%	96%	95%	98%	99%	92%	71%	76%	73%	86,8%
Daytime areal bird density birds/km2	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Proportion at rotor height	15.6%												
Total daylight hours per month	328	313	371	384	419	416	425	407	370	357	324	323	
Total night hours per month	416	359	373	336	325	304	319	337	350	387	396	421	
Flux factor	97	89	101	100	106	103	106	104	99	100	95	97	
Average collision risk for single rotor transit	4.7%												
Collisions assuming no avoidance	0,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Collisions assuming avoidance rate	95,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	98,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
birds per month	99,00%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99,50%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Consideration

The wind turbine of BGF platform has resulted to give an irrelevant impact on seabird population, and this is due to three main factors:

1. Seabird flight height distribution is mainly skewed to the sea surface;
2. Pelagic seabird density at sea is low. Nevertheless, it worth to notice that their distribution is linked to marine frontal zones, variable in time;
3. Blade clearance from sealevel is enough to ensure a safe zone for most seabird species;

On the other hand, some species (gulls, partially terns) have a vertical distribution intercepting blade swept areas, and gulls density at sea, mainly related to their ability to exploit fishery offals, in presence of an attractive source as BGF fish farm, can hardly be regarded as in natural conditions.

The significativity of the present figure will be considered further in a following chapter on impacts, but it's now possible to see that numbers of collisions are irrelevant. *Larus michaellis* is a species classified as Least Concern under IUNC categories, and which populations at both global and EU level are large and with an expanding trend. The conservationist concern can be considered as very low, and the number of fatalities, near to zero, can not raise any possible concern.

Migratory birds

The Canary Islands are not located along a major migratory route; however, birds reach the Archipelago during their southward migration when they are blown off their route by trade winds (Viana et al., 2016).

At present stage, the narrow swept area by BGF rotor make any quantitative collision assessment not significant when compared with the width of any potential migration corridors. Moreover, bird density at sea is unknow and any calculation by the CRM model unfeasible, while it remains questionable that the BGF site, 6.5 km offshore, can actually experience a regular migration passage.

The assessment is therefore only at a qualitative level.

Some bird groups, known as migrating near coastline, have been excluded at the present stage, in absence of any information on migration routes.

The birds included in present table are only those listed as “B” (breeding) or “W” (wintering) in Natura 2000 site assessment.

Within the sites, 21 bird species potentially migrating close the BGF platform has been identified.

None of them has been so far recorded in papers as at different risk level when interacting with windfarms. However, the lack of information is evident and cannot be overcome presently.

Table 15: Canary birds with migration potential

Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	RLS	Collision risk
Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Ardeidae	LC	ND
Ruddy turnstone	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Sanderling	<i>Calidris alba</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Dunlin	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Red Knot	<i>Calidris canutus</i>	Scolopacidae	NT	ND
Curlew Sandpiper	<i>Calidris Ferruginea</i>	Scolopacidae	NT	ND
Little Stint	<i>Calidris minuta</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Common Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	Charadriidae	LC	ND
Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Ardeidae	LC	ND
Common Snipe	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Bar-tailed Godwit	<i>Limosa lapponica</i>	Scolopacidae	NT	ND
Black-tailed Godwit	<i>Limosa limosa</i>	Scolopacidae	NT	ND
white Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Motacillidae	LC	ND
Whimbrel	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Ruff	<i>Calidris pugnax</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Eurasian Spoonbill	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	Threskiornithidae	LC	ND
Grey Plover	<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	Charadriidae	LC	ND
Common Greenshank	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Scolopacidae	LC	ND
Northern Lapwing	<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	Charadriidae	NT	ND

While number of individuals belonging to these species is relevant, density at sea remain unknown and a quantitative collision risk assessment still unfeasible at the present stage.

5.1.2 Impact on mammals

Impact on cetaceans

The BGF platform is expected to emit low-frequency noise at low intensity, mainly due to wind turbine machinery (see Impact on mammals, Marseille site).

Consideration exposed for that site remains valid for Canary also, although the presence of cetaceans in this latter area is quite different.

Table 16: Cetacean abundance in Canary Islands (Source: MYSTIC SEAS II estimate, 2017)

Common name	Scientific name	Num. individual
Atlantic spotted dolphin	<i>Stenella frontalis</i>	39306
Bottlenose dolphin	<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	2808
Common dolphin	<i>Delphinus delphi</i>	NA
Cuvier's beaked whale	<i>Ziphius cavirostris</i>	56
Risso's dolphin	<i>Grampus griseus</i>	NA
Pilot whale	<i>Globicephala macrorhynchus</i>	1980
Sperm whale	<i>Physeter catodon</i>	224
Bride's whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	NA
Fin whale	<i>Balaenoptera edeni</i>	NA

The species present in the area and more sensitive to the sonification of the marine environment are the Sperm whale and the Cuvier's beaked whale, this latter often involved in mass strandings after naval sonar exercitation.

The audiogram of *Ziphius* shows a hearing sensibility in the range between 1 and 100 kHz, although at sound pressures above 50 dB.

At the present stage, the BGF platform is expected to emit low frequency tones mainly between 1 and 700 Hz, with a peak intensity of 120 dB at 150 Hz, that can hardly be perceived by *Ziphius cavirostris*. Other frequencies emitted by the wind turbine, up to 10 kHz, can be perceived by *Ziphius* but above 90 dB, say at very close distance from the wind turbine mast basis and the platform.

Sperm whale is still suffering a heavy mortality rate in Canary Islands due to the high risk of ship strike in Canary water (Carrillo & Ritter, 2010; Fais, 2016). These waters are reputed at very high collision risk for Sperm whales, mainly due to the very intense ferry transit between island, and to the use of high-speed passenger vessels. Moreover, 19% of all cetaceans strandings are caused by human activities.

Figure 44: Cetaceans core habitat and ships’ lanes (Source: Carrillo & Ritter, 2010)

The BGF platform is located outside the cetacean core habitats, both for Sperm whales than for other cetaceans (Carrillo & Ritter, 2010), thus minimizing the risk of habitat displacement; however, the noise emission by BGF wind turbine is similar to that of a ship (see Marseille study), at least as frequency range, although sound emission level is lower.

Figure 45: Audiogram of Ziphius cavirostris (Source: Escobar, 2016)

Sperm whale hearing ability is included in the range from 0.1 kHz to 60 kHz, with a better sensitivity at 5, 10, 20, 40 kHz. This sensitivity partially matches the likely wind turbine sound emission pattern, and even its lower frequencies are audible by Sperm whale. The low frequencies have a peak at 120 dB at 150 Hz, while other audible frequencies are emitted at a sound level of 80-90 dB: a transmission loss of 35 dB can be expected at 100 m from source, and 55 dB of loss at 1000 m, following Thiele model (see Sound paragraph, Marseille study).

Figure 46: Sound frequencies emitted by a 2MW wind turbine

The vocalizations of Sperm whale are emitted in a range from 0.1 to 15 kHz (Pace, 2016). They are used for echolocation and for social communication. Lowest frequencies (500 Hz) are audible at distance in the magnitude order of dozens of Km, while echolocation at 15 kHz is perceived up to 16 km.

The wind turbine's peak emission at 150 Hz of 120 dB, following Thiele's law, will suffer a transmission loss of 60 dB at 10 km, maintaining thus a noise level of 60 dB. Is therefore possible that, in calm weather, the wind turbine sound is felt by Sperm whale at great distances.

In conclusion, an overlap between low frequencies emitted noise by the wind turbine with the hearing capability of Sperm whale at low frequencies is possible, and can not be excluded that a masking effect of Sperm whales' vocalizations may be experienced in the BGF area.

However, data on BGF sound emission are not yet understood, and any masking effect can only be a hypothesis at the present stage.

Impact on bats

Bat species in Gran Canaria belong to sedentary and non migratory species; they are described as restricted to more pristine area, where forest cover is rather dense. No bats are listed among resident species into the standard data form of the Natura 2000 areas facing the BGF installation.

The island hosts an endemic species, *Plecotus teneriffae*, (EN) endangered under the IUCN Red List. *Nyctalus leisleri*, known in Europe to be a long-range (1000 km) migrating species, is also considered sedentary in Canary.

The BGF installation is located at 6.35 km of the nearest coast: it will be in a very visible position from coastline, and its nocturnal lights system is able to attract nocturnal insects as moths and consequently their predators, certainly able to cover the distance from the land. On the platform bats are at risk of collision with rotating blades, which speed surpass their avoiding capacity.

Bat mortality has frequently been reported as associated to wind turbines, and bats have been found on wind farm in North Sea, at relevant distance from the coast. Two causes of bat deaths have been documented: collision with blades and barotraumas caused by rapid air pressure reduction near moving turbine blades (Baerwald et al., 2009; Arnett et al., 2008; Horn et al., 2008).

The most impacted genera are *Pipistrellus*, *Nyctalus* and *Eptesicus*. It remains unclear whether collisions occur fortuitously or do wind turbines attract bats. Recent studies suggest that some bats, at least from the genus *Nyctalus*, can be attracted to wind turbines (Hochradel et al., 2015). Some of the main characteristics of the wind turbine influence the mortality of bats: the diameter of the rotor, the size of the tower, the ground clearance and the blade tip speed which can exceed 300 km/h. Studies show that bat activity at turbines increases with net energy production (Voigt et al., 2015). Other conditions can increase bat mortality as weather, season and time of the day (Amorim et al., 2012).

Minimizing collisions is critically important to both bat conservation and public acceptance of wind- energy development. Presently, mitigation actions as blade feathering and increase of cut-in wind speeds offer an ecologically sound and economical strategy for reducing bat fatalities (Rodrigues et al., 2014). Cutting-out the generator from the grid when bat activity is high has demonstrated an effective reductions of bat collisions (Arnett et al., 2010). Integrated automatic systems based on models processing variables others in addition to wind speed (time of night, bat activity) and meteorological data are now available (Brinkmann et al., 2011). When intense bat activity is detected, wind turbines can be stopped automatically. Increasing the cut-in speed and feathering blades to quickly slow rotor to the selected cut-in speed, gives a substantial reduction in bat collisions. The advantage of the feathering turbine blades is that it could be implemented at many wind farms where turbines have SCADA systems capable of relatively easy programming. The blades can remain almost completely stopped until the increased cut-in speed is reached over an average number of minutes (usually 5-10 min). Several studies have shown a 50 % reduction in mortality of bats when the cut-in speed was delayed by 1.5 m/s. Generally, it can be stated that bat activity is decreasing only at wind speeds higher than 6 m/s (Voigt et al., 2015).

At wind speeds below operational cut-in speeds, turbines are generally “freewheeling”. Although turbines are not producing any electricity while freewheeling, they still may rotate at high speeds that are lethal to bats. Thus, altering turbine operations to eliminate blade movement at or below normal cut-in speed also may reduce bat fatalities without raising cut-in speeds. Normally operating turbine blades are angled perpendicular to the wind at all times.

More recently, studies have tested the effectiveness of ultrasonic acoustic deterrent for reducing bat fatalities at wind energy facilities (Arnett et al., 2013). The emission of ultrasonic broadband

can modify the behaviour of bats by discouraging them to approach the sound source, or indirectly by reducing the hunting time spent near the turbine because insects are repulsed by ultrasounds.

However, this mitigation measure has some limitations. Deterrence by ultrasound is limited by distance (efficiency up to 15 meters) and weather conditions like humidity. Further, effectiveness is different between bat species.

5.1.3 Impact on reptiles

Juvenile loggerhead turtles have been identified in feeding grounds off the Canary Islands. These juvenile turtles share feeding grounds with juveniles of the same species belonging to other Atlantic and/or Mediterranean populations (Carreras et al., 2011). Loggerheads originally from the eastern American coast are frequently observed in the Atlantic archipelagos of the Canaries (López-Jurado, 1992), where they spend their pelagic juvenile life stage. Furthermore, the waters of the Canary Current hold a remarkable diversity of sea turtles of different origin, as well as turtles from the southeast of the United States of America (Bolten et al., 1998), the Caribbean or the Gulf of Guinea (Monzón-Argüello et al., 2010). These feeding aggregations host individuals from distant populations.

The loggerhead turtles in the Canary region are genetically different from the other populations in the Atlantic Ocean and in the Mediterranean Sea (Shamblin et al., 2014). This genetic distinctiveness indicates a significant reproductive isolation, with little or no gene flow with other populations (Monzón-Argüello et al., 2010). The long lives of sea turtles make them especially vulnerable to depletion and their vast oceanic ranges make them especially difficult to manage.

All sea turtle species present in the Canary are globally considered as Endangered (EN) (IUCN, 2014).

The loggerhead turtle *Caretta caretta* is present in the Canary waters. Its abundance has recently been estimated by the MISTIC SEAS II Project, and is of 1.482 individuals. No estimations are available for *Chelonia mydas*.

As described in the section concerning Marseille site (see section on impact on Reptiles), *Caretta caretta* is sensitive from 50 to 800 Hz, but only at intensity above 100-150 dB. The only part of the spectrum that would be emitted by the BGF platform at intensity above 100 dB is between 200 and 400 Hz. Turtles do not have any vocalization, thus transmitted noise would only be able to displace individuals from an area of biological significance (mating, feeding or transit) only at such level above the 100 dB, levels that can only be reached at very close distance to disturb individuals. At 100 m of distance from the source, with a loss of 30 dB, sound would no longer be perceived by turtles.

The BGF site is not facing any nesting area, thus mating can not be expected there, and the relevant deep make it suitable only for pelagic feeding or transit, activities that would not be prevented by the presence of the BGF platform.

5.1.4 Impact on benthic communities

The species selected for farming in BGF platform in Arinaga is *Sparus auratus*. Market size, above 400g, is reached after 11-12 months, depending of first month of stocking. Maximum biomass per cage is estimated in 1,142 ton, while the maximum monthly feed distribution is 1218 ton at year 1. The biomass peak, 3,064 ton, is reached at year 1.

Table 17: Production cycle at year N°1

Month	Year 1											
	(Stock 1)		(Stock 2)		(Stock 3)		(Stock 4)		(Stock 5)		(Stock 6)	
	Hold (tonne)	Feed (tonne)										
Jan	66	72										
Feb	106	102										
Mar	163	125	66	79								
Apr	233	165	110	114								
May	324	202	173	153	66	94						
Jun	437	248	258	203	118	140						
Jul	574	281	371	246	196	188	66	109				
Aug	731	300	508	275	300	229	127	153				
Sep	897	322	660	305	427	271	212	204	66	115		
Oct	1076	156	830	287	578	266	326	220	130	144		
Nov	625		989	275	726	261	448	229	210	169	66	94
Dec			1142	141	870	255	575	234	304	188	118	120
Jan			649		1012	215	705	202	408	172	185	122
Feb					1132	128	817	229	504	204	253	157
Mar					637		944	231	617	213	340	175
Apr							1073	137	735	244	438	212
May							613		871	267	556	243
Jun									1019	157	690	281
Jul									597		846	304
Aug											1015	165
Sep											599	
Oct												
Nov												
Dec												

Table 18: Production cycle at year N°2

Month	Year 2												
	(Stock 1)		(Stock 2)		(Stock 3)		(Stock 4)		(Stock 5)		(Stock 6)		
	Hold (tonne)	Feed (tonne)											
Jan													
Feb													
Mar													
Apr													
May													
Jun													
Jul													
Aug													
Sep													
Oct													
Nov													
Dec													
Jan	66	72											
Feb	106	102											
Mar	163	125	66	79									
Apr	233	165	110	114									
May	324	202	173	153	66	94							
Jun	437	248	258	203	118	140							
Jul	574	281	371	246	196	188	66	109					
Aug	731	300	508	275	300	229	127	153					
Sep	897	322	660	305	427	271	212	204	66	115			
Oct	1076	156	830	287	578	266	326	220	130	144			
Nov	625		989	275	726	261	448	229	210	169	66	94	
Dec			1142	141	870	255	575	234	304	188	118	120	

Table 19: Feed distributed and total biomass

Month	Temp	Total Monthly FEED (tons)	Total Annual FEED (tonnes)	Total Monthly Holding (tons)
Jan		72		66
Feb		102		106
Mar		204		229
Apr		279		343
May		449		564
Jun		591		813
Jul		823		1.208
Aug		957		1.665
Sep		1.218		2.263
Oct		1.074		2.940
Nov		1.027		3.064
Dec		937	7.732	3.010
Jan		783		3.025
Feb		820		2.811
Mar		824		2.768
Apr		872		2.588
May		959		2.603
Jun		1.028		2.523
Jul		1.126		2.651
Aug		1.122		2.680
Sep		1.218		2.862
Oct		1.074		2.940
Nov		1.027		3.064
Dec		937	11.792	3.010

The farming cycle of Sea bream in BGF has been designed to lead to a gross fish production of 3.000 tons per year. This result is reached in Arinaga after the 2nd year of production by a stocking policy of 4 batches of grossly 3.330.000 fingerlings each per year, starting by an average weight of 20 g (See D 9.1).

Figure 47: Average weight on cage

Figure 48: Fish density in cages

The above result is reached by maximizing the yield per cage, moving quickly to market all fish at size (>400 g), and re-stocking the empty cage, maintaining a correct farming density (<15 kg/m3).

The available cages in BGF farming system are 6. Fish are grown in the same cage until they reach a maximum of biomass of 1200 ton: over this threshold the stock is harvested within 2 months.

Therefore, the evolution of overall biomass in the farm is conditioned by the above farming and harvesting policy in association, that determine a sudden decrease in standing stock in some months: the resulting biomass evolution is beyond the possibility of any modelling.

In fact, while the growth of fish can be predicted, the harvesting policy after attaining the desired size is not connected to any biological law, but just an operators' choice.

Figure 49: Total biomass in cages

Figure 50: Monthly feed consumption

The simulation of the depositions originating from the BGF fish farm has been performed by the dedicated software Aquamodel. The farmed species is the seabream, and its growth model has been adapted to the farming cycle supplied by the BGF partner Sagro Aquaculture, in the frame of D 9.1. Sinking speeds of faeces and uneaten food are similar to seabass.

The flow field adopted is similar to the one used in Marseille, since the same level of detail is not available for Canary waters: however, the flowfield has been forced by a strong semidiurnal tidal component, with speeds of 0.8 m/sec, that often overtop the inertial flowfield. Therefore, the used flowfield is not referred to Canary Islands, but has been used as a generic flowfield encompassing moderate currents (up to 1 m/sec) under a semidiurnal tide regime. In a subsequent step, this simulation will be re-run using a 2-dimensional flow field, derived from data originated by different sources (Copernicus, BODC).

Table 20: Coefficients used for benthic respiration

Benthic coefficient	Unit	Value
TOC sediment	%dryW	0.001
Oxygen at bottom	ppm	4
Ambient TOC deposition	g C/m ² /day	0.2
Oxygen in seawater	ppm	6
Aerobic biomass	g C/m ²	0.26
Anaerobic biomass	g C/m ²	0.05
Sediment CO ₂	g/m ²	0
Sulfide in sediment	mM/m ³	0
Mixing depth winter-summer	M	100-60
Surface temperature	°C	16-28

Bottom temperature	°C	14-16
Inorganic Nitrogen	Micro-Moles/m ³	0.3

Table 21: Coefficients used for deposition

Depositional coefficients	Unit	Faecal	Feed
Sinking speed	cm/sec	1	8
Deposition threshold	cm/sec	4	8
Re-suspension threshold	cm/sec	8	10
TOC Consolidation rate	%/day	0.01	0.05
TOC Oxidation rate	%/day	0.01	0.01
Feed Carbon content	% dry weight		0.53
Feed Water content	% dry weight		0.1
Feed Waste %	%		3

The Cumulative waste deposition over the seabottom

The following maps report the total amount in time of total organic carbon present over the seabottom. This map has to be intended as the overall organic carbon deposition, originating from faeces and uneaten food, and resulting only from the depositional processes without taking into account benthic respiration processes.

Snapshots are displayed at a rate of four/year, at month 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27,30, 33, 36, starting from the first month when depositions take place. Current vectors are referred at 22,5m of depth, below BGF platform at maximum current exposition of nets. Cages are outlined at the center of map.

Figure 51: Cumulative wastes; date March, 1st year

Figure 52: Cumulative wastes; date June, 1st year

Figure 53: Cumulative wastes; date September 1st year

Figure 54: Cumulative wastes; date December 1st year

Figure 55: Cumulative wastes; date March, 2nd year

Figure 56: Cumulative wastes; date June, 2nd year

Figure 57: Cumulative wastes; date September, 2nd year

Figure 58: Cumulative wastes; date December, 2nd year

The TOC Total Organic Carbon

The following maps report the fraction of total organic carbon present over the seabottom. This map has to be intended as the overall organic carbon presence, resulting from a balance between depositional and benthic respiration processes. In other words, these maps represent the final results of depositional minus respiration processes, and display the carbon standing stock, thus summarizing the modification of benthic features due to aquaculture activities.

Snapshots are displayed at a rate of four/year, at month 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27,30, 33, 36, starting from the first date when TOC appears. Current vectors are referred at 22,5m of depth, below BGF platform at maximum current exposition of nets. Cages are outlined at the center of map.

Figure 59: Total Organic Carbon; date March, 1st year

Figure 60: Total Organic Carbon; date June, 1st year

Figure 61: Total Organic Carbon; date September, 1st year

Figure 62: Total Organic Carbon; date December, 1st year

Figure 63: Total Organic Carbon; date March, 2nd year

Figure 64: Total Organic Carbon; date June, 2nd year

Figure 65: Total Organic Carbon; date September, 2nd year

Figure 66: Total Organic Carbon; date December, 2nd year

Effects on benthic communities

The map on benthic communities at broad scale (EMODnet, see figure 21 and figure 23) reports for the BGF area a rocky bottom, at a depth of 90 m. The benthic community is not exactly defined, since the belt below the infralittoral plan and the first part of circalittoral (approximately to -50 m) is not yet systematically investigated and mapped by EMODnet.

However, the maps describe the bottom nature as a rocky bottom; from similitudes in near areas, it can be inferred that the Scleractinian of the genus *Dendrophyllia* dominates the community. While *D. ramea* is restricted in Canary waters to the -70 m, the genus *D. cornigera* is characteristic of deeper bottom down to 240 m. A survey by Oceana (2011) has described the 2 communities, restricting the *D. ramea* to rocky bottoms with low sedimentation.

Figure 67: *Dendrophyllia ramea* colonies (source: Oceana, OSPAR workshop 2011)

The species present are:

Porifera: *Acanthella acuta*, *Adreus fascicularis*, *Aplysina aerophoba*, *Axinella damicornis*, *Axinella polypoides*, *Cliona celata*, *Corticium candelabrum*, *Crambe crambe*, *Dysidea avara*, *Haliclona* sp., *Hemimycale columella*, *Hexadella racovitzai*, *Ircinia oros*, *Phorbas fictitius*, *Phorbas tenacior*;

Cnidaria: *Alcyonium acaule*, *Astroides calycularis*, *Balanophyllia regia*, *Caryophyllia inornata*, *Caryophyllia smithii*, *Cladopsammia rolandi*, *Dendrophyllia cornigera*, *Diphasia margareta*, *Ellisella paraplexauroides*, *Eudendrium rameum*, *Eunicella gazella*, *Eunicella labiata*, *Eunicella singularis*, *Eunicella verrucosa*, *Gymnangium montagui*, *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*, *Maasella edwardsi*, *Nemertesia antennina*, *Paralcyonium spinulosum*, *Paramuricea clavata*, *Parazoanthus axinellae*, *Parerythropodium coralloides*, *Pennaria disticha*, *Polycyathus muelleriae*, *Phyllangia americana mouchezii*, *Sertularella gayi*, *Sertularella mediterranea*. Other terms are not of any bionomic relevance.

The *Dendrophyllia cornigera* forest occurs in a very broad bathymetric range, occupying both the deep circalittoral and upper bathyal zones. These forests can have a very variable density, the densest parts being located on the circalittoral area, whilst colonies appear much more dispersed at the ends of the bathymetric distribution range (70-240 m). Due to the fact that they occupy a broader bathymetric range than other species that are part of the community, the species composition of the community can vary with the depth. The tri-dimensional complexity of the undisturbed community seems to be enhanced by the species of Cnidaria (hard and soft corals) and Porifera that elevate over the sea bottom, offering physical support to other species and increasing

the availability of ecological niches.

Figure 68: A *Dendrophyllia cornigera* bottom, with abundant *Phakellia ventilabrum* sponges
(source: Oceana, OSPAR workshop 2011)

The Circalittoral species found are:

- Porifera: *Artemisina transiens*, *Axinella polypoides*, *Phakellia* cf. *robusta*, *Phakellia ventilabrum*;
- Cnidaria: *Eunicella verrucosa*, *Caryophyllia cyathus*, *Leptogorgia sarmentosa*

The Bathyal species found are:

- Porifera: *Antho dichotoma*, *Geodia* sp., *Phakellia* cf. *robusta*, *Phakellia ventilabrum*, *Tethya citrina*;
- Cnidaria: *Antipathes dichotoma*; *Acanthogorgia hirsuta*; *Amphianthus dohrnii*; *Bebryce mollis*; *Caryophyllia cyathus*; *Diphasia margareta*; *Eunicella verrucosa*; *Parantipathes hirondelle*.

The BGF site is located at a depth of -90 m, where we may expect that the Circalittoral plan fade into the bathyal plan, and the two specific pools are in part overlapping. In general, these communities are poor known, and even its bionomic status is still unclear, being by various authors' attributes to the "Roche du large" or to "Roche Bathyal", following Pérès and Picard. Both these communities lives under a very low rate of organic enrichment, and such pressure of human origin is probably rare in these biotopes and not investigated. It can be hardly found information on specific resilience and resistance to organic enrichment and sedimentation, thus community sensitivity can only be matter of hypothesis. Moreover, the case of BGF is peculiar, being the sea slope in Gran canaria very steep, thus forcing to locate the BGF at a relevant depth, where only roky bottoms exist, and where fish farms are unusual.

However, the depositional models commonly used to depict effects on benthic communities have been developed for soft-bottom community, where benthic respiration is mediated by sediment bioturbation. This factor can be considered as non-existing on hard bottoms, and all metazoans/microbial organic matter degradation has to be intended to happen at the water-substrata interface. At the same time, the behaviour of the benthic boundary layer, the depositional and resuspension threshold of sediment matter can hardly be compared between a sediment surface and a tri-dimensional benthos. Therefore, from the depositional model applied we can safely infer the area of influence of organic matter, but the likelihood of benthic accumulation, highlighted by the TOC, may be rather weak.

As an effect of the BGF fish farm, it can be expected that an area under its influence will experience an intense rain of detritus, composed by faces (old detritus) and partially by uneaten feeds (fresh detritus not refractory).

While the Porifera are rather insensitive to increased sedimentation, to organic enrichment and even to low oxygen levels, Scleractinians and Anthipatharia suffer the high sedimentation rates and the organic enrichment of waters. A community modification may be expected, and at high sedimentation rates *Dendrophyllia spp.*, *Antipathes*, *Parantipathes* and *Leptogorgia* may be removed in favor of a higher abundance of the Porifera already present in the community.

Recruiting time of Porifera are rather quick, in order of 1-2 years, while both hard and soft corals have a slow recovery time, due to a slow growth. Recovering time, after cessation of high sedimentation, is expected to take several years, being one of the structuring species, *Dendrophyllia spp.*, a long live and slow growing colonial animal.

Based on maps of deposition calculated above, the area affected by the organic matter deposition is of **166368 m²**.

A mooring detail is not available for Gran Canaria site, but depths are similar to Marseille site, thus mooring arrangement is expected to be similar as well. Therefore, the mooring swept area is set at **166,728 m²**.

The total area affected by organic matter loads and by mechanical removal is:

$$\text{Total area affected: } 166,368 + 166,728 = \mathbf{333,096 \text{ m}^2}, (0.33 \text{ km}^2)$$

The area around Gran Canaria, which bathymetry is between -70 and -200 m (where is expected a similar community will exist, including the deep circalittoral and the upper bathyal plans) is equal to 422 km² approximately, as derived from bathymetric charts.

Figure 69: Broad Habitat map; red lines include deep circalittoral and upper bathyal planes, roughly corresponding to isobaths of -70 and -200 m. (See also Fig. 21 for legenda)

The ratio between the total area and the one affected by BGF is $= 0.33/582 * 100 = 0.08 \%$

Therefore, at least in terms of surface lost by the *Dendrophyllia* community, the area is small.

In conclusion, it can be expected that the benthic community in an area of 0.16 km^2 will be completely removed, due to mooring chains abrasion over the rocky bottom; a second area of 0.16 km^2 as well will be modified by the organic enrichment, losing the hard corals diversity and increasing the Porifera abundance.

5.1.5 Impact on pelagic communities

The dispersion of Total Dissolved Nitrogen has been computed on a scale of 2 km, a distance that has resulted to provide an effective nitrogen dilution due to the intense flow field.

On short scale, the computational unit has been set to describe the spatial dispersion pattern around the farm, on a scale of some km, where the most part of effects are usually evident.

The computational domain has been set as follow:

- The computational cells have been set in number of 41 x 41 x 6 units;
- Each cell has a size of 50 m x 50m x 15 m;

The total size of the computational volume is therefore of:

- 50 m x 41 cells = 2,050 m;
- 50 m x 41 cells = 2,050 m;
- 5 m x 24 cells = 90 m

The above has determined a computational total volume of 2,050 m x 2,050 m x 90 m.

The flow field adopted is similar to the one used in Marseille, since the same level of detail is not available for Canary waters: however, the flowfield has been forced by a strong semidiurnal tidal component, with speeds of 0.8 m/sec, that often overtop the inertial flowfield. In a subsequent and in future steps, this simulation will be re-run using a 2-dimensional flow field, derived from data originated by different sources (Copernicus, BODC).

The used flowfield data set is the from 01.01.2016 to 01.01.2018, from January to December. Computational step is at 1 hour, resulting maps are computed at steps of 1 day.

Nitrogen Dispersion

Figure 70: Nitrogen dispersion in January, 1st year

Figure 71: Nitrogen dispersion in February, 1st year

Figure 72: Nitrogen dispersion in March, 1st year

Figure 73: Nitrogen dispersion in April, 1st year

Figure 74: Nitrogen dispersion in May, 1st year

Figure 75: Nitrogen dispersion in June, 1st year

Figure 76: Nitrogen dispersion in July, 1st year

Figure 77: Nitrogen dispersion in August, 1st year

Figure 78: Nitrogen dispersion in September, 1st year

Figure 79: Nitrogen dispersion in October, 1st year

Figure 80: Nitrogen dispersion in November, 1st year

Figure 81: Nitrogen dispersion in December, 1st year

Figure 82: Nitrogen dispersion in January, 2nd year

Figure 83: Nitrogen dispersion in February, 2nd year

Figure 84: Nitrogen dispersion in March, 2nd year

Figure 85: Nitrogen dispersion in April, 2nd year

Figure 86: Nitrogen dispersion in May, 2nd year

Figure 87: Nitrogen dispersion in June, 2nd year

Figure 88: Nitrogen dispersion in July, 2nd year

Figure 89: Nitrogen dispersion in August, 2nd year

Figure 90: Nitrogen dispersion in September, 2nd year

Figure 91: Nitrogen dispersion in October, 2nd year

Figure 92: Nitrogen dispersion in November, 2nd year

Figure 93: Nitrogen dispersion in December, 2nd year

Considerations

The nitrogen dispersion is quick and only in some case moves beyond the computational limits. This is due to the intense circulation pattern, that bring Nitrogen concentration quickly to the level of surrounding waters, minimizing effects on pelagic communities.

The fast dilution does not allow for a sufficient contact time between planktonic microalgal community and Nitrogen-enriched waters, thus preventing the possibility of algal blooms. Throughout all the time series considered, the plume of excreted Nitrogen do not exceed the basal Nitrogen level.

Oxygen consumption

As per Nitrogen, the computation has been performed at time steps of one hour, at the same interval of current data. In this way, the information on movements due to semidiurnal tide components has been maintained. In the same time, this interval has requested a long computing time and generated as well a redundancy of images, beyond the aim of the present study.

Cages has been schematized as located between 0 and -35 m of depth, to account for oxygen consumption due the average biomass distribution in cage, and assuming that water flow can freely renew cages inner water volumes, without any barrier due to platform wall. This simulation represents the hypothesis of maximum undisturbed renewal due to natural flow field.

In order to describe the annual oxygen consumption pattern, a subset of images, sampled at a rate of one image /month has been extracted and presented.

Along the images, the arrows represent the current vector at 7.5 m of depth. Their length is proportional to the current speed, as in the side legend. Oxygen concentration pattern is represented in maps as sourcing from the middle of cage, at a depth of 7.5 m.

Maps have an area of 2,050 x 2,050 m.

Red line crossing image around the minimum con concentration represents the transect line, along which the section with Dissolved Oxygen concentration from surface to bottom is displayed. Dissolved Oxygen concentration is in mg/l.

Figure 94: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in January, 1st year

Figure 95: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in February, 1st year

Figure 96: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in March, 1st year

Figure 97: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in April, 1st year

Figure 98: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in May, 1st year

Figure 99: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in June, 1st year

Figure 100: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in July, 1st year

Figure 101: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in August, 1st year

Figure 102: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in September, 1st year

Figure 103: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in October, 1st year

Figure 104: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in November, 1st year

Figure 105: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in December, 1st year

Figure 106: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in January, 2nd year

Figure 107: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in February, 2nd year

Figure 108: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in March, 2nd year

Figure 109: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in April, 2nd year

Figure 110: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in May, 2nd year

Figure 111: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in June, 2nd year

Figure 112: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in July, 2nd year

Figure 113: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in August, 2nd year

Figure 114: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in September, 2nd year

Figure 115: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in October, 2nd year

Figure 116: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in November, 2nd year

Figure 117: Dispersion of Oxygen deprived waters in December, 2nd year

Considerations

The oxygen consumption due to high biomass confined in a restricted farming volume is intense, and it leads to a sensitive depletion when circulation pattern is weak (fig. 115). While the surrounding waters are quickly restored at basal Oxygen level, due to the mixing of waters, the area close to the farm (or inside this) seems to be in the need of a more intense renewal to support the high biomass on farming.

5.1.6 Impact on other uses of the sea

This assessment is postponed to a subsequent step, lacking at the moment several basic informations on platform operational life.

5.1.7 Impact on landscape

The method adopted is described in the Marseille study, see 5.1.1.7.

The following table shows the maximum theoretical visibility distances in kilometers of the BGF platform in relation to different potential altitudes of an observer, both at sea and on the coast.

Table 22: Maximum visibility rang of the BGF blade tip

Blade tip height (m)	Observer height (m)	Visibility range (nm -km)
205	2	32.2 - 59.63
205	10	35.8 - 66.30
205	20	38.5 - 71.30
205	30	40.5 - 75.0
205	50	43.8 - 81.1
205	150	54-100

On the basis of the calculation of the theoretical visibility, therefore, the BGF platform would theoretically be visible in a range of 80 km within an elevation of about 50 m above sealevel, given that no obstacles (buildings, trees, hills) prevent the view. Visibility of the platform and blade tip is possible from whole east coast of Gran Canaria. Visibility from Las Palmas is prevented by the coastal hills. From the west Coast of Tenerife, it would theoretically be visible from 150 m above sea level. In practice, a visibility range of 100 km is very seldom realized.

Figure 118: Visibility range of the BGF blade tip, for observers at 2, 10, 20, 30 and 50 m above sea level

Figure 119: LIDAR profile of the Gran Canaria Island, point of view from BGF platform

Figure 120: Island area of platform visibility

However it should be kept in mind that, in cases where the plant is located at the end of the field of vision, only the upper portion of the structures is actually visible which, as in the case of blade tip, it consists of elements of very reduced volume compared to the base. Additionally, the low contrast between blade color and horizon help to mask the visibility of the rotor.

The degree to which a particular anthropic element can be clearly perceived within an environmental context is called "visibility". The visibility of an element is strictly dependent on the intrinsic physical characteristics of the element (height, width) and on the observer's field of vision.

According to the generally adopted criterion, the visibility of an element within a given context is limited to cases in which the element occupies at least 5% of the complete visual field of the observer's eye.

The measurement of the visual field of the human eye is based on parameters that provide the basis for evaluating and interpreting the impact of an element, evaluating the extent to which the element itself occupies the central field of eye visibility (both horizontally and vertically).

Horizontal visual field

The visual field of each eye taken individually varies between an angle of 94 and 104 degrees, depending on the person. The maximum visual field of the human eye is therefore characterized by the sum of these two fields and therefore ranges between 188 and 208 degrees.

The central field of visibility for most people instead covers an angle between 50 and 60 degrees (see Figure 121). Within this angle, both eyes observe an object simultaneously. This creates a central field of greater magnitude.

This central field of visibility is called 'binocular field'; in this field the images are sharp, the perception of depth and the discrimination between colors are verified.

Figure 121: Visibility fields in horizontal plan

The visual impact of an element on the horizontal visual field of man therefore depends on the way in which this element impacts the central field of visibility. An element that occupies less than 5% of the central binocular field is usually insignificant for the purpose of assessing its impact in most of the contexts in which it is inserted (5% of 50 degrees = 2.5 degrees).

Vertical visual field

Evaluations similar to those described for the horizontal visual field of the human eye can be made for the vertical visual field. As shown in Figure 122 the vertical visual field of the human eye corresponds to an angle of 120 degrees (50 degrees above the standard line of sight, which stands at

0 degrees, and 70 degrees below the standard line of sight). The central field of visibility has a width of 55 degrees, while the normal visual cone varies between 10 degrees below the standard line of sight if the observer is standing and 15 degrees below the standard line of sight if the observer is seated.

Figure 122: Visibility fields in vertical plan

The visual impact of an element on man's vertical visual field therefore depends on the way in which this element impacts the central field of visibility, as for the horizontal visual field. An element that occupies less than 5% of the normal visual cone occupies a minimum portion of the vertical visual field and is therefore visible only if concentrating directly on the element (5% of 10 degrees = 0.5 degrees).

Visibility based on the horizontal field of view

The visual impact of the offshore structures in project on the horizontal visual field is evaluated considering the maximum horizontal dimension that is the value of the diagonal of the plant:

- BGF Platform: 265 m;

A visual element can be categorized as:

- Visually dominant: the element has a dominant role within the visual field;
- Potentially distinguishable: the element is distinguishable and the level of disturbance

strongly depends from the degree of contrast with the surrounding landscape;

- Insignificant: the element, although visible, does not significantly interfere with the view of the landscape.

The results show that at the distance to which the offshore structure is placed, the landscape disturbance introduced by them can be considered insignificant, as it is limited to a minimum portion of the horizontal field of view. In particular, considering that the BGF platform has a height of 8.6 m, the visibility range is 22.6 km for an observer at 10 m, say, can hardly be seen from the nearest coast.

At the minimum distances of 24.5 km for the platform from the nearest land, in case of exceptional visibility, this will occupy at most about 0.6° of the horizontal field of view. To reach a significant visibility, say have the BGF platform covering 5 % of his visual field, the observer has to get closer than 7 km from BGF.

Visibility based on the vertical visual field

An analogous reasoning can be conducted for the vertical visual field, in order to verify at what distance the considered element is reduced to an imperceptible component of the field of view. The trigonometric calculation was carried out considering the maximum heights of offshore structures, ie:

- BGF wind turbine blade tip : 208 m;

Similarly to what emerged for the horizontal field of view, the result of the analysis of the vertical field of view shows that, at the distance to which the offshore structure is placed, its visibility from the coast is not significant, being necessary to get closer than 5.2 km to the BGF platform to get an angle wider than 2.5° . From the nearest coast, the vertical visible angle for a structure of 208 m is $> 0.5^\circ$. The disturbance to the landscape introduced can be considered insignificant, as it is limited at a minimum percentage of the vertical visual field.

However, it should be noted that the BGF platform would be located at a distance of 5 km from other wind farm located onshore on an industrialized area. It should not be perceived as an alien element, but may be partially integrated in an industrialized landscape.

5.1.8 Risk of major accidents

This paragraph will be addressed in a later stage, when the design of devices preventing external intrusions or fish escapees will be better defined.

The assessment of this impact will be postponed to a more mature platform design stage.

5.2. RANK OF COMPONENTS

The four components taken in account in the present study, will be affected by impacts caused by the BGF activity at different order of magnitude:

- Seawater
- Marine communities
- Terrestrial communities
- Landscape

However, it appropriate to assign a rank of importance to any resource involved into the BGF operational life, with the aim of highlighting or decreasing its intrinsic value on the basis of two criteria, the Rank A and Rank B respectively.

Rank A is a criterion that aims to objectively assign a weight to the resource, based on its availability and functionality; the selected ranks from 1 to 5 are described in Table 23 below:

Table 23: Rank A

Rank A	Resource feature	Value assigned
1	Common	0.75
2	Common locally	1.5
3	Rare	2.25
4	Protected	3
5	Strategic/Structural	3.75

The rationale of this ranking system stay in the evaluation of ecosystemic importance of the resource.

Rank B is a criterion that accounts for the stakeholders' interest in the resource conservation, somehow aggregating a concern on the state of the resource. Ranks are 1 to 5, as shown in Table 24 below:

Table 24: Rank B

Rank B	Resource feature	Value assigned
1	Scarce- no concern	0.25
2	Low - Some stakeholders' secondary concern	0.5
3	Medium – Most of stakeholders' secondary concern	0.75
4	High - Some stakeholders' primary concern	1
5	Maximum- Most of stakeholders' primary concern	1.25

The Ranks A and B are added to obtain the definitive resource rank. Definitive rank value range between 1 and 5.

Definitive ranks will be used as correction factors to determine the overall impact on the resource.

Table 25: Definitive rank values

Component	Resources	Rank A	Rank B	Definitive rank
Sea water	Nutrients	0,75	0.25	1
	Oxygen	0.75	0.25	1
Marine communities	Phytoplankton	1.5	0.5	2
	Benthos	3	1	4
	Odontocetes	3.75	1.25	5
	Mysticetes	3.75	1	4.75
	Fish	1.5	1	2.5
	Seals	3.75	1	4.75
	Sea Turtles	3.75	1	4.75
	Pelagic birds	3	1	4
	Migratory birds	3	1	4
	Bats	3.75	1	4.75
Landscape	Visibility	2.25	1.25	4

This rank assignment is based on consideration drawn from the specificity of the environmental context and of the legal frame where the BGF is expected to be installed, with some difference from the other two sites. The turistic relevant activity in the archipelago based on natural amenities, the presence of iconic animals as turtles and cetaceans, the relevant turistic pressure and the public concern on conservationist themes have driven the categorization of the ranks, leading to a high weight to pressures involving animal conservation. Note that ranks assigned here differ from those used in Marseille and Port Ellen: the high community diversity and the relevant landscape values in a touristic context make the ranks' attribution more conservative.

This procedure maintains in itself a certain degree of subjectivity, unfortunately not completely avoidable in impact evaluation procedures.

5.3 IMPACT MATRIX

The impact matrix is calculated as result of several matrixes, showing the detailed characteristics of the impact and concurring in determining the severity of impact. The used method is a simplification of the Leopold Matrix (Leopold et *al.*, 1971), adding 2 rank coefficients to weight the impact significance. The impact feature matrices (Frequency, Extension, Duration, Reversibility) are similar to those recommended in UNI EN ISO 14001 application.

Frequency: it indicates how frequently the stressors acts, or how many times the activity generate the pressure.

FREQUENCY	
1	RARE, 2 TIMES/YRS
2	INTERMITTENT, 4 TIMES/YRS
3	REGULAR, MONTHLY
4	RIPETITIVE, 1-2 TIMES/WEEK
5	CONTINUOUS, 3 TIMES/WEEK

Spatial extention: it display the amplitude of geographical effects of the stressors, e.g. for migrating bird is approaching the species areal.

SPATIAL EXTENSION	
1	ISOLATED, ON SITE
2	CONFINED, INFLUENCING LOCAL COMMUNITY
3	LOCAL
4	REGIONAL, BEYOND LOCAL COMMUNITY
5	GLOBAL

Duration: indicates the lasting in time of stressors effect, e.g for reproducing animals, until new specimens reach sexual maturity in the same population.

DURATION	
1	LOW TERM
2	3-12 MONTHS
3	1-3 YEARS
4	> 3 YEARS
5	LONG LASTING

Reversibility, indicating if the effect can be recovered and at which degree.

REVERSIBILITY	
1	TOTALLY REVERSIBLE
2	HIGHLY REVERSIBLE
3	AVERAGE REVERSIBLE
4	LOW REVERSIBLE
5	NOT REVERSIBLE

For each factor and stressor, the four above matrices are applied, and the resulting numbers are added. The sum gives a value between 0 and 20, that determine the severity if impact, basing on the following ranges:

SEVERITY		
Sum of values, range		
0-4	NO CONSEQUENCES	1
5-8	LIGHT, LOW DANGER	2
9-12	MODERATE, POSSIBLE TO RESTORE	3
13-16	HEAVY, DIFFICULT TO RESTORE	4
17-20	VERY HEAVY, POTENTIALLY FATAL	5

The probability scale indicates the probability assigned to the pressure agent to cause the impact, e.g. the probability of a rotating blade to hit a bird in presence of avoidance

PROBABILITY	
1	REMOTE, <11%
2	LOW, 12-33%
3	MODERATE, 34-67%
4	HIGH, 68-90%
5	VERY HIGH, >90%

The resulting values (from 1 to 5) of severity, multiplied by the probability of the event, gives as result a number between 1 and 25, representing the Significativity (or magnitude) of the Impact:

SIGNIFICATIVITY
1-5 LOW SIGNIFICATIVITY
6-15 SIGNIFICANT
16-25 VERY SIGNIFICANT

This last number, multiplied by the weight resulting from the Rank A and B combined (see table 41), gives the overall impact, varying between 0 and 100.

OVERALL IMPACT
NOT RELEVANT, 1-20
LOW, 21-40
MODERATE, 41-60
RELEVANT, 61-80
HEAVY, 81-100

5.3.1 Impact of aquaculture activities

NUTRIENTS RELEASE IN WATER COLUMN

Seawater	Nutrients
Frequency	5
Extension	1
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	5
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	1
Overall impact	Not relevant

OXYGEN CONSUMPTION IN WATER COLUMN

Seawater	Oxygen
Frequency	3
Extension	1
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2

Probability	5
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	1
Overall impact	Not relevant

PHYTOPLANKTON GROWTH

Marine communities	Phytoplankton
Frequency	5
Extension	1
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	5
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	2
Overall impact	Low

BENTHIC COMMUNITIES

Marine communities	Benthos
Frequency	5
Extension	1
Duration	5
Reversibility	3
Severity	4
Probability	4
Significativity	Very Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Relevant

PELAGIC BIRDS

Marine communities	Pelagic birds
Frequency	5
Extension	3
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	4
Probability	2

Significativity	Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Low

FISH

Marine communities	Fish
Frequency	5
Extension	2
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	3
Probability	4
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	2.5
Overall impact	Low

VISIBILITY

Landscape	Visibility
Frequency	5
Extension	2
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	4
Probability	3
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Moderate

5.3.2 Impact of noise on marine communities**ODONTOCETES**

Marine communities	Odontocetes
Frequency	3
Extension	1

Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	4
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	5
Overall impact	Low

MYSTICETES

Marine communities	Mysticetes
Frequency	3
Extension	3
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	3
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	4.75
Overall impact	Low

FISH

Marine communities	Fish
Frequency	5
Extension	1
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	3
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	2.5
Overall impact	Not relevant

SEA TURTLES

Marine communities	Sea Turtles
Frequency	4
Extension	1
Duration	1

Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	2
Significativity	Low significativity
Total rank	4.75
Overall impact	Not relevant

5.3.3 Impact of wind farm

PELAGIC BIRDS

Marine communities	Pelagic birds
Frequency	5
Extension	4
Duration	5
Reversibility	2
Severity	4
Probability	2
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Low

MIGRATORY BIRDS

Terrestrial communities	Migratory birds
Frequency	2
Extension	5
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	4
Probability	1
Significativity	Low Significativity
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Not relevant

BATS

Terrestrial communities	Bats
Frequency	2
Extension	4
Duration	5
Reversibility	4
Severity	4
Probability	1
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Low

VISIBILITY

Landscape	Visibility
Frequency	5
Extension	2
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	4
Probability	5
Significativity	Very Significant
Total rank	3.5
Overall impact	Relevant

5.3.4 Impact of entangling structures on marine communities**FISH**

Marine communities	Fish
Frequency	3
Extension	1
Duration	3
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	2
Significativity	Low Significativity
Total rank	2.5
Overall impact	Not relevant

PELAGIC BIRDS

Marine communities	Pelagic birds
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Frequency	4
Extension	4
Duration	5
Reversibility	1
Severity	4
Probability	2
Significativity	Significant
Total rank	3.75
Overall impact	Low

5.3.5 Impact of electromagnetic fields on marine communities

FISH

Marine communities	Fish
Frequency	3
Extension	2
Duration	1
Reversibility	1
Severity	2
Probability	2
Significativity	Low Significativity
Total rank	2.5
Overall impact	Not relevant

5.3.6 Impact of moorings on marine communities

BENTHOS

Marine communities	Benthos
Frequency	5
Extension	1
Duration	5
Reversibility	3
Severity	4
Probability	5
Significativity	Very Significant
Total rank	4
Overall impact	Relevant

Table 26: Matrix of overall impacts. O = not relevant; Green = low impact; Yellow = moderate impact; Orange = relevant impact

Component	<i>Resources</i>	Aquaculture	Noise	Rotor blades	Entangling structures	Electromagnetic fields	Moorings
Sea water	<i>Nutrients</i>	O					
	<i>Oxygen</i>	O					
Marine communities	<i>Phytoplankton</i>	Green					
	<i>Benthos</i>	Orange					Orange
	<i>Odontocetes</i>		Green				
	<i>Mysticetes</i>		Green				
	<i>Fish</i>	Green	O		O	O	
	<i>Seals</i>						
	<i>Sea Turtles</i>		O				
Terrestrial communities	<i>Pelagic birds</i>	Green		Green	Green		
	<i>Migratory birds</i>			O			
	<i>Bats</i>			Green			
Landscape	<i>Visibility</i>	Yellow		Orange			

5.4 MITIGATION MEASURES

Cetaceans and fish are subject to a low level of impact, and the only mitigation consists in selecting machinery at the lowest possible noise level. The sound emissions seem not so different from those emitted by a ship, but at a lower intensity. While a ship move away, making its impact transitory in space and time, the BGF remains stationary, adding its noise signature to the ambient noise already present.

The possibility of entangling is evaluated as low at this stage, and a further assessment will be run when the definitive design of nets and fish farm submerged ancillaries will be ready. In fact, a risk of entanglement and subsequent drowning may be expected for those animals (cetaceans, diving birds) entering from the bottom side the swimming pool: it is not yed clear whether they can easily find the way out, and if their diving time is long enough to reach the open waters and the surface to breath.

The impacts on landscape of the platform structure and of the wind turbine are calculated as moderate and relevant respectively. These impacts can hardly be mitigated, as they are common to all offshore installation: the BGF platform is a massive structure with a very high mast and blades, which tip is potentially visible from very long distances. In the present location, the BGF is visible by the whole east coast of Gran canaria, while is not visible by the city of La Palma.

Due to the peculiar slope of the Gran Canaria seabottom, the BGF is located at only 6.5 km from the coast, and it can be argued that the structure will be completely visible from the coastline. The only possible mitigation consists in a displacement at greater distance from the coast, provided that costs for cabling, mooring and staff displacent remain acceptable.

Moorings and organic deposition affect a rather large area of seabed, that equates 0.33 km². Both the impact of organic deposition on seabed and of mooring on benthic communities can be regarded as relevant, since the area host a hard coral deep community, that is not able to withstand any accumulation of organic debris, nor a mechanical removal. The long recovery time makes this impact of particular environmental concern. The possible mitigation consists in a modification of the mooring arrangements, shortening the chain length laying on seabottom, or considering the feasibility of a VLA system.

A very low risk of collision has been calculated for some species of pelagic birds, and the risk is probably enhanced by the presence of the fish farm, attracting birds by its own structure and feeding opportunities. Migratory birds are at the present state of knowledge, of any concern, and this is due on one hand by a lack of knowledge on birds' movements, on the other to the very small blade-swept area, compared to the width of a possible migration flock. The light system may rise a concern on nocturnal pelagic feeding birds, that could be attracted in case of an incorrect light system setting.

Possible mitigations:

Bird/Bat collision risk:

- Keep rotating blades at the maximum possible height above sealevel;
- Keep rotation speed at lowest possible;
- Feather and arrest blades below productive wind speed;
- Prevent birds resting on platform surfaces, nets or cages;
- Avoid releasing at sea of feeds, fish or carcasses;
- Implement acoustic scaring devices;
- Avoid lights directed to sky or seawater
- Avoid Metal-halide and LED lights
- Avoid highest part of visible spectrum (red/reddish colour)
- Adopt lights possibly close to green color at lowest possible intensity
- Adopt flashing and on demand lights for passages whenever possible
- Implement a radar system for detecting approaching flocks in poor visibility conditions
- Install shut-off lights + other devices in case of bird flocks approaching

Benthic impacts

- Decrease mooring footprint on seabottom
- Move platform further offshore
- Increase effluent dilution

Visibility

- Decrease contrast of blades against horizon

Constraints:

- Blade height increase improve bird collision risk, but impair landscape impact;
- Low contrast blades improve landscape impact, but decrease visibility for birds, thus increasing collision risk.
- Moving offshore increase environmental cost of connection and cost of moorings

5.5 SUMMARY OF ENCOUNTERED DIFFICULTIES/ISSUES

This study has been performed on the basis of an overall platform design that is not yet reaching the definitive level, thus describing the general platform features but still missing a number of specific details. As a consequence, several sections of the study have remained at a general level too, postponing a more detailed assessment at the Project's end, and as a consequence of a detailed design availability.

This study is based completely on data found in literature, and no terrain activities of any kind are forecast within this Work package. Data are mainly retrieved from official websites or available papers on the web, and may be insufficient in temporal coverage or details.

Data to fit the Band Model are those available on papers, as bird density at sea, flight heights, proportion at rotor height and night activity per species. A local influence on bird behaviour may exist, but can not be taken into account presently. In the same way, migrators behaviour may depend from local (and highly variable) conditions, as the real migration path. Bird presence offshore is inferred from published papers or also from feeding ranges in literature, and is reported as highly variable depending from local opportunities. Bird density increasing following BGF operations, is here considered as fully logical, but supported by a limited number of references.

Wind turbine productivity is based on data collected from a local database referred to the Gran Canaria airport, at a distance of 20 km, with similar wind exposition. Data at 10m height have been recalculated to 100 m height.

Data on bat presence offshore is largely absent, and a quantitative collision risk assessment is unfeasible, although a collision risk may be hypothesized.

The model used for effluent estimation has been fitted with a flowfield derived from Copernicus website, and built for the Mediterranean site. Therefore, the used flowfield is not referred to Canary Islands, but has been used as a generic flowfield encompassing moderate currents (up to 1 m/sec) under a semidiurnal tide regime. However, model application needs to be validated on local or similar conditions, and at the present stage confidence on obtained simulations are to be kept within the limit of likelihood of the model, in itself rather simplistic to be able to take in account the real complexity of open-sea dynamics. Nevertheless, the model can be positively considered on a near-field range.

Wind turbine noise production is deduced from a scant literature, and models of attenuation are generic and not considering speed noise modification due to local water column and bottom features, as well the shape of the emitting body. Resonance and combined machinery noise effects can not be considered at this stage, even when their coexistence is logical.

Landscape viewshed can only be estimated from maps, while a proper assessment would need some activities and a photographic survey on place.

Last, the assessment of impacts maintains in itself a certain degree of subjectivity, that unfortunately can not be totally eliminated.

CHAPTER 6: FINAL RECOMMENDATIONS

The Canary Island is characterized by a peculiar environment, which richness in terms of florofaunistic and landscape diversity is the basis of a flourishing turistic industry, one of the main islands' income. The siting of a massive structure as the BGF in a site where it maintains the complete visibility from the coast gives some constraint, and a process of improvement has to be undertaken, either in refining the design and in adjusting the siting. Unfortunately the relevant bottom slope makes the selection of an alternative site very difficult.

Particular attention should be paid during subsequent design phases in preventing that wild animals would take advantage from platform's structure and operation to approach it frequently, feed on residuals or simply be attracted by lights or emerged or submerged structures. Even at low impact risk, it can be reminded that Canary waters have a high density of cetaceans and turtles, and they are the basis of an intense whale-watching activity. Cumulative effects between the BGF presence and other human sea-based activity have to be taken in account in subsequent assesment, to investigate the possibility of species displacement from ecologically important grounds.

The BGF platform, as multi-funcional unit, presents a degree of complexity uncommon for marine structures, and whose environmental combined effects have not been extensively investigated so far. This work represents a first environmental assesssment based on the platform features known at the present stage of design, useful to focus on the main potential impact of such a complex installation. This assement will be updated in the project progress, as new platform features, potentially interacting with marine environment, will emerge.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION

The impact assessment performed at the present stage of design, when mostly of the general platform features are known, demonstrates that the general concept of the structure do not results in any particular concerns on its environmental acceptability, and the impact assessed are mainly site-specific.

The height of the nacelle and the blade tip, even increasing long distance visibility, on the other hands remains outside the flight heigths of most of marine birds, decreasing collision probability. The platform is located at 6.5 km offshore, and its wind turbine will unfortunately result completely visible from the coast.

The peculiar nature of the seabottom requests a mitigation action to decrease the impact of the mooring system on benthic communities.

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